

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

Statistical Briefings Austria

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Austria on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

Figure 1: Origin and Share of Total Population of Different Nationalities in Austria

Source: Statistics Austria (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Austria

In 1961, the number of migrants, i.e. foreign nationals living in Austria, slightly exceeded the number of 100,000. This corresponded to a share of about 1.4 % of the total population. In the second half of the 1960s and at the beginning of the 1970s, the number and share of the foreign population increased relatively strongly due to the targeted recruitment of workers from the former Yugoslavia and Turkey. In 1974, a temporary peak was reached with about 311,700 foreign nationals (4.1 % of the total population at that time). It was not until the strong wave of immigration in the early 1990s that the proportion of foreigners jumped to over 8 %. After a brief stagnation in the second half of the 1990s, the number of foreign nationals in Austria has increased again since the turn of the millennium, with the 10 % threshold for the share of foreigners being exceeded for the first time at the beginning of 2008.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 1,486,223 persons with non-Austrian citizenship were living in Austria. This corresponded to a share of around 16.7 % vs. 83.3 % of Austria's total population. Among non-Austrian nationals, slightly more than half (778,443 persons) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries, including a total of 199,993 Germans, who formed the largest group of foreigners in Austria with a share of 13.5 % (or 2.2 % of total population). A total of 707,780 individuals (or 8.0 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), having a nationality that is neither Austrians, EU citizen nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, Austria is therefore lying above the average.

Considering the nationalities of TCN, Serbians (122,115 persons; share of 1.4 %) are making up the largest nationality group ahead of Turks (117,607 persons; share of 1.3 %) and Bosnians (96,583 persons; share of 1.1 %). Rank four to eleven follow considerably further behind: Syria

(0.6 %), Afghanistan (0.5 %), Russia (0.5 %), Kosovo, Northern Macedonia (both 0.3 %), Iran, China, Iraq (each 0.2 %). In total almost 4 of 5 TCNs living in Austria belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Austria.

Population Development

The number of inhabitants in Austria has increased in the past and will continue to grow in the future. As of January 1, 2020, there were 8,901,064 persons registered in Austria. This corresponds to an increase of 837,424 citizens (+10.4 %) within about 20 years since 2002 (before eastward enlargement of EU in 2004). The main cause of population growth is immigration to Austria (EU-28, EFTA & TCN), as the birth rate is only slightly higher than the death rate of the domestic population (see Figure 2 (a)).

Analyzing regional units (districts), the strong dispersion is striking. The median Austrian population development is 0,0 %, i.e. half of the districts has grown, and the other half has shrunk. The Austrian population is relocating to the cities and metropolitan areas of Vienna, Linz, Salzburg, Innsbruck and Bregenz along the east-west axis, whereas in the south there is an internal migration from rural areas to cities. The cities and metropolitan areas of Graz and Klagenfurt, where growth and stagnation have occurred, are notable exceptions to this trend. The total number of Austrians living in Austria slightly increased by 81.462 inhabitants (+1.1 %; see Figure 2 (b)).

EU (incl. UK) and EFTA citizens are the main factor behind population growth in Austria (+520,588 inh., +201,9 %). From a regional perspective the range is +51,8 % (minimum) to +396,4 % (maximum). Similarly to the Austrians, this group of population lives in or close to cities. Germans (2.2 %), Romanians (1.4 %) and Hungarians (1.0 % of total population) account for the largest share (see Figure 2 (c)).

TCN account for approx. 8 % at the beginning of 2020. Immigrants from Serbia (1.4 %), Turkey (1.3 %) and Bosnia (1.1 %) are the largest national groups. TCNs became more relevant in the past

20 years as their number increased by 235,374. Like total population urbanization growth as a result of TCN immigration only takes place in a few regions, i.e. cities and metropolitan areas (see Figure 2 (d)).

Figure 2: Population Development (Δ 2002 to 2020)

Source: Statistics Austria (2020a), own illustration

Summing up, both, domestic and foreign population groups tend to (re-)locate in cities and metropolitan regions. This is at the expense of rural areas which are experiencing an overall decline in population. In particular, this is the case for the southernmost province of Carinthia, which will

shrink in the future (up to current population forecasts).

From a regional perspective, the areas with the strongest decline in population are located in the federal states of Lower Austria (Waldviertel), Styria (Mur-Mürzfurche) and Carinthia (except metropolitan area of Klagenfurt-Villach). These regions belong to the periphery and have a poor economic structure. They suffer from higher depopulation and birth rate deficits. In a total of four districts, the population is projected to decline by 10 % or more by 2040, namely in Wolfsberg (-11.6 %), Spittal an der Drau (-11.4 %), Hermagor (-13.4 %) and Murau (-14.6 %; see Figure 3 (a)).

Figure 3: Projections of population growth (Δ 2020 to 2040)
(a)

(b)

(c)

Source: ÖROK (2019), own illustration

Up to 2040 predominantly metropolitan areas will grow. In addition to the Vienna metropolitan area,

which spans to northern Burgenland, the population will also increase in the regions of the provincial capitals of Graz, Salzburg, Innsbruck and Bregenz, as well as in the central Upper Austrian region of Linz-Wels and in the Carinthian cities of Klagenfurt and Villach. In these regions, the population will grow steadily until 2040. The main reason for this is the strong external immigration, as well as mostly positive balances of internal migration and birth surpluses. Besides urbanization tourist regions in the west, i.e. Tyrol and Vorarlberg, also tend to grow (see Figure 3 (a)).

Vienna and its surrounding areas expect the highest growth rate of domestic-born population whereas projected shrinking regions correspond to those which experienced a decline in the past (see Figure 2 (b)). Again Murau has the greatest decline of 14.6 % until 2040, followed by the peripheral regions of Carinthia, Salzburg and Styria (see Figure 3 (b))

Similar to the domestic-born population, the foreign-born population will settle primarily in or near the cities of Vienna, Linz, Graz, Salzburg and Innsbruck, whereas it performs below-average but positive in rural areas (except for Waidhofen an der Thaya; see Figure 3 (c)).

Population Structure

While the debate about changing demographic structures in most cases turns around population ageing and the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc. a focus must be taken on the relevance of labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years, in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking work.

Starting from 5.924.377 people in this age group as of Jan. 1, 2020, the maximum will be reached at the beginning of 2021 with 5.932.642 persons (+0.14 %). Thereafter, the labor force potential will decline, as more people will move from

working age to retirement age in the 2020s than will be added at younger ages or through immigration. As a result, the number of 15-64 year-olds in 2040 will already be -4.7 % lower than in 2020, at 5.644.119 inhabitants (-280.258 inh.).

Further analysis on a regional level reveals that except for Vienna (+2.9 %) the potential labor force will decline in each federal state till 2040, if the projections for the population born in Austria and abroad are considered (see Figure 4 (a)-(c)). The southern provinces Carinthia (-15.7 %) and Styria (-9.3 %) suffer the highest losses followed by Burgenland (-7.3 %). All other states, Upper Austria, Tyrol (both -5.4 %), Lower Austria (-4.5 %) and Vorarlberg (-5.2 %) operate at the same level.

Figure 4: Projections of Working Age Population (15 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040)

Differentiated by the country of birth, the projections show total decline of 543.906 inh. (-12.1 %)

of domestic born labor force. There are great disparities between the federal states as there is a tendency of Austrians relocating to Vienna (only -6.8 %) and its metropolitan areas in Lower Austria (only -9.6 %). The decline in the other provinces ranges from -11.9 % (Vorarlberg) to -21.6 % (Carinthia; see Figure 4 (b)). The situation is different for the population born abroad as it is projected to rise by +263.648 inh. (+18.6 %) all over Austria. Again there are striking regional differences as abroad born population rises by almost one third (+29.2 %) in Burgenland followed by Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Tyrol, Styria (range from +22.8 % to +20.1 %) and Carinthia (17.9 %) and Salzburg (+17.8 %). Vienna (+15.4 %) and Vorarlberg (+15.1 %) are expecting the lowest growth rates (see Figure 4 (b)).

These figures underline the high relevance of migration, especially for rural regions, concerning the development of the working age population. Without immigration, its population between 15 and 64 years would shrink even more dramatically, being a challenge from an economic point of view (see Figure 4 (a)).

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be “dependent” on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 14 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being working age from 15 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in 2020 in Austria is 50,2 %. The dependency rate is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are prospering economy and low child ratios. Most metropolitan regions in Austria are also characterized by relatively low rates (e.g. Vienna: 45,1 %). High dependency ratios are found in regions where the share of children and the elderly (65 years and older) is above average. These regions are mainly found in Carinthia and Burgenland (both 54.7 %). As a result of ageing societies, the total-age dependency ratios will rise in the future by 17 percentage points (pp) to 67,2 % in 2040.

Figure 5: Total-Age Dependency Ratio (Δ 2020 to 2040)

Source: Statistics Austria (2020b), own illustration

Considering the nine Austrian regions, the increase varies from 8.8 pp (Vienna) to almost 25 pp, with highest ratios in Burgenland (23.7 pp) and Carinthia (24.6 pp) in 2040; see Figure 5 (a)). Figure 5 (b) and (c) differentiate between Austrian and abroad born total-age dependency ratios. Without immigration the dependency ratios would evolve worse than with because of the high share of domestic age group 65 years or older (range from 13.4 pp to 30.8 pp vs. 5.1 pp (Tyrol) to 9.9 pp (Carinthia)).

¹ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020b).

² Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of Austria's domestic population is 31.2 %, which is only slightly above that of the total population (31.1 %). Compared to the EU-27 (27.9 %) Austria has an above-average tertiary education rate. Austria ranks 14th within the EU-27, ahead of its neighboring countries Slovenia (29.3 %), Germany (26.0 %) and Hungary (22.5 %). Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and Cyprus (40.0 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities¹ than in towns and suburbs², which in turn is higher than in rural areas³. In rural areas in Austria, only 25.6 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 29.8 % in towns & suburbs and 38.8 % in cities. In contrast, secondary degrees are more common in less densely populated areas. While less than 40.9 % of city residents have secondary, i.e. upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 3 to 4) attainment level, 51.0 % and 57.4 % of residents in towns & suburbs and rural areas do. Primary educational attainment level has a comparable low relevance as in cities approx. only 1 out of 5 residents in Austria belongs to this group, in towns and suburbs and rural areas the share is even lower.

In cities, where most of the Non EU-27 citizens live, more than 40.6 % have only primary education, i.e. less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (ISCED levels 0 to 2, see Table 1). This share is even higher in towns & suburbs (48.5 %) and rural areas (48.1 %). On contrary, only 25.6 % of Non EU-27 citizens have a degree from university, but this value is still much higher than in suburban (14.8 %) and rural

density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020c; Eurostat 2020d).

³ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat 2020e; Eurostat 2020f).

(17.3 %) regions. Differences of educational attainment level between Austrians and EU-27 residents range within a narrow band from 1.0 pp to 4.9 pp and are therefore comparable.). In total, EU-27 citizens (38.3 %) residing in Austria have a higher tertiary education rate than domestic population (31.2 %) whereas Non EU-27 rank last (21.7 %).

Table 1: Working Age Population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Austrians	16.6%	42.9%	40.6%
	EU-27	14.7%	39.8%	45.5%
	Non EU-27	40.6%	33.8%	25.6%
	Total	20.2%	40.9%	38.8%
Towns & suburbs	Austrians	16.5%	52.6%	31.0%
	EU-27	18.8%	49.2%	32.0%
	Non EU-27	48.5%	36.7%	14.8%
	Total	19.2%	51.0%	29.8%
Rural areas	Austrians	16.5%	58.0%	25.5%
	EU-27	13.9%	55.6%	30.4%
	Non EU-27	48.1%	34.6%	17.3%
	Total	17.0%	57.4%	25.6%

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

The high relevance of education for employment and income, is also valid for Austria and its regions. In total, about 188,000 (45.7 % female) persons were unemployed in Austria in 2019 according to the labor force survey (LFS). Compared to the previous year, this corresponds to a reduction of - 6.9 %. In relation to the labor force potential, this results in an unemployment rate of 4.3 % (female: 4.2 %; male: 4.4%). The comparative value for the EU-27 is 6.6 % (female: 6.9 %; male: 6.3 %; age group 20 to 64 years). Vienna has by far the highest unemployment rate at 9.0 % (female: 9.1 %; male: 9.9 %), followed by Lower Austria (3.8 %; female: 3.7 %; male: 3.9 %), Carinthia (3.7 %; female: 4.4 %; male: 3.0 %) and Burgenland (3.6 %). Tyrol (1.9 %; 2.0 % female; 1.7 % male) and Salzburg (2.2 %) are the provinces with the lowest unemployment rates (see Figure 6).

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less

likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for Austria: Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (10.0 %) and this situation has remained constant for years. Conversely, people with tertiary education have the lowest unemployment rate (2.8 %), those with secondary a value of 3.6 %. Similar results are observed at the European level (EU-27; see Figure 7).

Figure 6: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020g), own illustration

Figure 7: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (25 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020g), own illustration

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher is the employment rate, i.e. 84.7 % for tertiary, 76.1 % for secondary and 48.2 % for primary level. From an immigrational point of view, this observation holds for other citizenships as well, as the risk of unemployment decreases by the highest educational attainment. But Austrians have the highest employment rate for each educational attainment level (86.5 %; 76.7 %; 48.3 %),

followed by EU-27 citizens (81,9 %; 75.1 %; 52.9 %) and Non EU-27 citizens (65,5 %; 69.5 %; 45.8 %); the only exception is “less than primary, primary and lower secondary education” of Austrian and EU-27 citizens (48,3 % vs. 52.9 %; see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship 2019 (25 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020h), own illustration

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed at lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed.

In 2019, 10.2 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-27 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.4 %). Austria ranges with a value of 7,8% below the European average. The share of EU-27 citizens residing in Austria is two times as high (12,3 %)

⁴The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean.

and that of Non EU-27 is almost five times as high (24.4 %). In total, almost one half (48.7 %) of early school leavers, is jobless, but no relying statements can be made in regard to immigrational status because of missing data (Eurostat 2020i).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁴ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income.

This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level. Working persons in Austria at primary level earn less (mean: € 22,412 or median: € 21.190) than secondary (€ 27,750 or € 26,358) and tertiary levels (€ 34.051 or € 30.743); see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

As working Austrians have a higher educational attainment level than EU-27 and Non EU-27 this could be one reason (amongst others) that their mean (€ 30,361 vs. € 25,778 and € 21,064) and median (€ 27,997 vs. € 21,600 and € 19,474) equivalized net income is higher (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

A further analysis and decomposition of wage differentials between domestic and foreign workers done by Lehmer and Ludsteck (2013) reveals that

factors like seniority, promotions to better-paid occupations as well as job stability also have to be taken into account. These factors also cause an improvement in an individual's firm-specific human capital (training on the job) as the median age of foreign workers and therefore the length of time within the company is lower than domestic. However, these assumptions cannot be verified in the context of this analysis due to a lack of available data.

The indicator 'people at risk of poverty or social exclusion' corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity⁵. As Non-EU 28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than domestic residents and EU-28 almost 2 of 5 persons (38,4 %) belong to this group though the value of EU-27 is quite high as well (29.9 %). Austrians face the lowest risk of social exclusion and poverty (13.1 %; see Table 2).

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

Dimensions of Poverty and Social Exclusion			Citizenship		
Risk of Poverty	Material Deprivation	Work Intensity	Austria	EU-28	Non EU-28
At risk	Severe	Very low	0.3%	0.6%	2.9%
At risk	Severe	Not very low	0.4%	1.4%	3.1%
At risk	Non severe	Very low	1.6%	4.7%	7.4%
At risk	Non severe	Not very low	7.9%	20.5%	16.1%
Not at risk	Severe	Very low	0.3%	0.4%	1.0%
Not at risk	Severe	Not very low	0.5%	0.4%	4.4%
Not at risk	Non severe	Very low	2.1%	1.9%	3.5%
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion			13.1%	29.9%	38.4%
Not at risk	Non severe	Not very low	86.8%	69.9%	61.6%
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion			86.8%	69.9%	61.6%
Total			100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Eurostat (2020l), own illustration

A way to calculate gross domestic product (GDP) is, to sum up, all the income earned by factors of production from firms in the economy—the wages earned by labor; the interest paid to those who lend their savings to firms and the government;

the rent earned by those who lease their land or structures to firms; and dividends, the profits paid to the shareholders, the owners of the firms' physical capital. This is a valid measure because the money firms earn by selling goods and services

⁵ Persons are considered to be at risk of poverty after social transfers, if they have an equivalized disposable income below the risk-of-poverty threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalized disposable income. Persons are considered to be at risk of poverty after social transfers, if they have an equivalized disposable income below the risk-of-poverty

threshold, which is set at 60 % of the national median equivalized disposable income. People living in households with very low work intensity are those aged 0-59 living in households where the adults (aged 18-59) work 20% or less of their total work potential during the past year (Eurostat, 2020m).

must go somewhere; whatever is not paid as wages, interest or rent is profit. Ultimately, profits are paid out to shareholders as dividends (Krugman and Wells 2017).

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers' social contributions) was the largest income component of EU-27 GDP accounting for 47.5 % and 48.1 % in the euro area. Austria lies above European (both EU-27 and Euro area) average. Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 12.3 % (EU 11.9 %; Euro area 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 39.2 % of GDP in Austria, 40.6 % of GDP for the EU-27 and 40.4 % in the Euro area. Austrian GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 397.6 billion (+3.2%) in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 44,780 (Eurostat 2020m).

Within 20 years Austria's gross domestic product (GDP) increased by 29.2 %. In terms of regional GDP per capita, all provinces also recorded positive real growth, ranging from 1.1 % in Vienna to 26.7 % in Carinthia since 2002 (Austria: 18.9%). The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred in Salzburg (approx. € 53,600), succeeded by Vienna (approx. € 52,700). As in previous years, the eastern and southern provinces were below the national level of € 44,800 (Burgenland: € 31,600; Lower Austria: € 36,700; Carinthia: € 38,300, Styria: € 40,800; see Table 3).

Provinces with a high share of TCNs have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries or regions. This approach is suitable in cases where there is a significant difference in levels of prosperity, as can be observed among Austria provinces. The most prosperous region in

Austria is Salzburg (154 %); it is over 64/47/44 pp richer than Burgenland/Lower Austria/Carinthia. Vienna ranks second (150 %). The western regions Tyrol (136 %) and Vorarlberg (143 %) are also located at the top whereas Upper Austria (131 %) and Styria (118 %) are in the midfield (Eurostat 2020n).

Table 3: Nominal regional GDP (2019) and real growth rate (Δ 2002 to 2019)

Province	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate (Δ 2002 to 2019)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market	Real growth rate (Δ 2002 to 2019)
Burgenland	9,273	28.6%	31,600	22.1%
Carinthia	21,506	26.5%	38,300	26.7%
Lower Austria	61,706	30.7%	36,700	21.5%
Upper Austria	68,380	32.8%	46,000	24.6%
Salzburg	29,852	34.4%	53,600	26.2%
Styria	50,831	31.1%	40,800	26.0%
Tyrol	36,383	35.2%	48,100	23.1%
Vienna	100,348	21.3%	52,700	1.1%
Vorarlberg	19,162	37.8%	48,400	24.9%
Extra-Regio	135	-12.8%	.	.
Total	397,575	29.2%	44,800	18.9%

Source: Statistics Austria (2020c) and Statistics Austria (2020d), own illustration

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors. In recent decades, the Austrian economy has undergone a structural transformation, which is why another important sector has developed alongside the established sectors - the information and communications technology sector (ICT sector), which is composed

of subsectors of the production⁶ and services⁷ sectors.

In total, approx. 4.6 million people were employed (employees, marginal employed, freelance, self-employed) in 2019 in Austria. This corresponds to

an increase of +13.3 % compared to 2008. Almost three quarters (72.6 %) are employed in the service sector (3.4 million persons), where employment has increased by +17.6 % since 2008. Employment in manufacturing evolved below average (+8.3 %) and though primary sector increased

Table 4: Employment by economic activity 2019

Economic Activity	Employed persons in 2019	Share	Δ 08-19	Austrians	EU-28 & EFTA	TCN
Primary Sector	34.9	0.8%	35.7%	55.9%	36.6%	7.5%
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	34.9	0.8%	35.7%	55.9%	36.6%	7.5%
Secondary Sector	1064.1	22.9%	8.3%	78.4%	12.9%	8.7%
Mining and Quarrying	6.3	0.1%	-0.9%	88.5%	7.7%	3.8%
Manufacturing	685.3	14.8%	7.1%	80.7%	11.5%	7.9%
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	26.9	0.6%	-2.9%	95.4%	2.9%	1.7%
Water supply, sewerage, waste management	18.6	0.4%	23.9%	80.9%	10.6%	8.5%
Construction	327.0	7.0%	11.2%	71.8%	17.1%	11.1%
<i>ICT manufacturing</i>	13,328	0.4%	0.2%	82.5%	10.5%	7.0%
Tertiary Sector	3370.7	72.6%	17.6%	77.7%	14.0%	8.3%
Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles	652.9	14.1%	7.0%	80.4%	10.9%	8.7%
Transportation and storage	226.0	4.9%	5.5%	73.2%	15.1%	11.7%
Accommodation and food service activities	341.9	7.4%	28.3%	58.4%	25.7%	16.0%
Information and communication	120.8	2.6%	33.8%	83.4%	11.3%	5.4%
Financial and insurance activities	125.3	2.7%	-7.7%	90.2%	6.2%	3.7%
Real estate activities	57.3	1.2%	1.9%	78.1%	11.3%	10.6%
Professional, scientific and technical activities	261.6	5.6%	33.0%	83.5%	11.4%	5.1%
Administrative and support service activities	279.0	6.0%	28.1%	57.0%	23.8%	19.2%
Public administration and defense	593.4	12.8%	11.2%	94.8%	3.2%	2.0%
Education	134.4	2.9%	34.6%	77.8%	14.8%	7.4%
Human health and social work activities	380.1	8.2%	49.3%	71.1%	23.9%	5.1%
Arts, entertainment and recreation	63.4	1.4%	33.1%	74.9%	16.9%	8.2%
Other service activities	126.2	2.7%	2.5%	81.7%	10.4%	7.9%
Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods- and services	7.6	0.2%	-58.8%	59.6%	26.1%	14.3%
Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies	0.8	0.0%	23.4%	48.2%	31.9%	20.0%
<i>ICT services</i>	84,869	2.3%	40.6%	83.7%	10.7%	6.9%
Others	174.5	3.8%	-22.3%	97.6%	1.7%	0.7%
Military and civil servants	4.7	0.1%	-37.4%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Parents karencz with working relationship	72.6	1.6%	-26.0%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Others	97.2	2.1%	-18.3%	95.7%	3.1%	1.2%
Total	4644.2	100.0%	13.3%	78.4%	13.5%	8.1%
<i>ICT total</i>	<i>98,197</i>	<i>2.6%</i>	<i>33.3%</i>	<i>83.5%</i>	<i>10.6%</i>	<i>6.9%</i>

Source: BMAFJ (2021)

⁶ Manufacture of electronic components and boards, Manufacture of computers and peripheral equipment, Manufacture of communication equipment, Manufacture of consumer electronics, Manufacture of magnetic and optical media (Eurostat 2020o).

⁷ Wholesale of information and communication equipment, Software publishing, Telecommunications, Computer programming, consultancy and related activities, Data processing, hosting and related activities; web portals, Repair of computers and communication equipment (Eurostat 2020o).

by 35.7 % it is of very low importance, i.e. only 0.8 % of total employment. Approx. 4 % belong to the category 'Others' ("military and civil servants", "parents karens" with "working relationship", "others"). 2.6 % work in the ICT, which performed very well (+33,3 %) in the past years mainly caused by services (+40.6 %) rather than manufacturing (+0.2 %; see Table 4).

A more detailed examination of the different sectors of the economy reveals that there have also been significant shifts within the sectors: the only declines in employment were recorded in the sectors "Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods- and services" (-58.8 %), "Financial and insurance activities" (-7.7 %), "Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply" (-2.9 %) and "Mining and Quarrying" (-0.9 %). "Human health and social work activities" (+49.3 %), "Education" (+34.6 %), "Professional, scientific and technical activities" (+33.0 %), "Administrative and support service activities" (+28.1 %), "Information and communication" (+33.8 %) as well as "Accommodation and food service activities" (+28.3 %), on the other hand, are among those economic sections with the largest absolute growth.

Further analysis by citizenship shows that almost 4 out of 5 blue- and white-collar workers of the secondary (78,4 %) and tertiary sector (77.7 %) are Austrians. The same holds for EU-27 & EFTA (12.9 % and 14.0 %) and TCN (8.7 %) and 8.3 % workers. Almost the same ratio applies to the ICT sector (83.5 %/10.6 %/6.9 %).

EU-28 & EFTA citizens are overrepresented (above 13.5 %) in "Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods- and services" (26.1 %), "Accommodation and food service activities" (25.7 %), "Human health and social work activities" (23.9 %), "Administrative and support service activities" (23.8 %), "Arts, entertainment and recreation" (16.9 %), "Construction" (17.1 %), "Transportation and Storage" (15.1 %) and "Education" (14.8 %).

⁸ High-tech industry and knowledge-intensive services describe manufacturing and services industries or

"Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies" (31.9 %) has very low absolute importance (only 770 persons in total or 0.02 %). In "Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply" (2.9 %), "Public administration and defense" (3.2 %), "Financial and insurance activities" (6.2 %), "Other service activities" (10.4 %), "Water supply, sewerage, waste management" (10.6 %), "Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles" (10.9 %), "Real estate activities", "Information and communication" (both 11.3 %), "Professional, scientific and technical activities" (11.4 %) and "Manufacturing" (11.5 %) EU-28 & EFTA workers have minor relevance (below 13.5 %). Summing up EU-28 & EFTA citizens are underrepresented in the secondary sector (except "Construction") whereas their skill and knowledge is more relevant in the tertiary sector.

TCNs preferably work in "Administrative and support service activities" (19,2 %), "Accommodation and food service activities" (16.0 %), "Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods- and services" (14.3 %), "Transportation and Storage" (11.7 %), "Construction" (11.1 %), "Real estate activities" (10.6 %) and "Water supply, sewerage, waste management" (8.5 %). From a sectoral point of view, TCNs have almost the same relevance in the secondary (8.7 %) and tertiary sector (8.3 %; difference of only 0.4 pp). Overall, the account for 8.1 % of all working people as they are slightly underrepresented in the primary sector (7.5 %)

These findings correlate with EU-28 & EFTA citizens except for high-tech industry and knowledge-intensive services⁸ where a higher educational attainment level is necessary. The greatest variation is between "Human health and social work activities" (18.8 pp), "Arts, entertainment and recreation" (8.7 pp) and "Information and communication" (5.9 pp). As a large number of "Information and Communication" belongs to the ICT sector they are also less engaged there (6.9 % vs. 10.6 %).

products traded broken down by technological intensity (Eurostat 2020p).

Lower Austria (84,5 %), Tyrol (83.5 %) and Salzburg (81.3 %) have the highest share of Austrians working in the secondary sector whereas Vienna (64.1 %), Carinthia (70.3 %) and Vorarlberg (73.0 %) have the lowest share. The number of TCNs exceeds the number of EU-28 & EFTA in Vorarlberg (14.3 % vs. 12.7 %) and almost in Salzburg (10.3 % vs. 10.5 %); in the remaining federal provinces EU-28 & EFTA outweighs TCN (see Figure 11 (a)).

Figure 11: Employment by economic sector and citizenship 2018

Source: BMFAJ (2021), own illustration

An analysis of the tertiary sector shows that EU-28 & EFTA citizens have a higher share of at least

0.9 pp (Vienna) whereas the greatest gap is in neighboring Burgenland (20.6 pp; see Figure 11 (b)).

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-27 and Non EU-27).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 3.18 % for Austria (2019) which is a slight increase of 0.13 percentage points to 2017. The total amount of research expenditures was € 12.7 billion, the largest share (47.6 % or 6.04 billion) was financed by Austrian companies. 24.6 % (or € 3.12 billion) were financed by the federal government. More than € 0,75 billion (or 6.0 %) were funded indirectly via research grants. 4.3 % (or € 0,55 billion) was provided by the local governments, 15.9 % (or € 2.02 billion) by foreign countries and 1.6 % (or € 0,2 billion) was financed by other sources. The majority of the funding from abroad came from foreign companies whose subsidiary companies conduct research in Austria and includes returns from EU research programs and initiatives as well (Eurostat 2020q).

Data on regional level (NUTS 2 or federal states) is published with a two year time lag. Styria was the province with the highest ratio in 2017 (4.87 %). Vienna followed in second place with 3.60 % just ahead of Upper Austria with 3.46 %. All other provinces were well behind and below the all-Austrian ratio of 3.05 %. Burgenland ranked last (0.85 %), with Salzburg (1.59 %), Vorarlberg (1.75 %) and Lower Austria (1.80 %) only slightly better. Tyrol's ratio is 2.88 %, just behind Carinthia (2.94 %, see Table 5).

Table 5: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures (€ mio.)	% of GDP
Burgenland	74.39	0.85%
Carinthia	584.18	2.94%
Lower Austria	1,047.41	1.80%
Upper Austria	2,191.16	3.46%
Salzburg	443.02	1.59%
Styria	2,320.33	4.87%
Tyrol	968.24	2.88%
Vorarlberg	317.88	1.75%
Vienna	3,343.17	3.60%
Total	11,289.78	3.05%

Source: Statistics Austria (2020f) and Eurostat (2020r), own illustration

In accordance to the research & development (R&D) funding structure almost two thirds (63.0% or 29,948 full time equivalent (FTE)) of the researchers work in the business enterprise sector. More than one of four researchers (28.4% or 13,513 FTE) works in the higher education sector, 7.7% (or 3,665 FTE) in the government sector and 0.8% (or 395 FTE) in the private non-profit sector. This makes a total of 47,521 FTE or 131,032 persons. Further analysis on educational attainment level reveals that most researchers (65.6%) have tertiary education but not doctoral or equivalent level; only 27.0% belong to the latter whereas 7.4% have less than primary, primary, secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: R&D researchers (full-time equivalent (FTE)) by sectors of performance and educational attainment level 2017 (ISCED2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020s), own illustration

Within the period from 2016 to 2018, 62.63% of enterprises in Austria developed and/or introduced new or improved goods or services, implemented new or improved business processes or conducted innovation activities. 34.6% of enterprises introduced new or improved goods or services onto the market in the reference period. In

2018, around 14.9% of total turnover concentrated on these product innovations. 6.3% of total turnover accounted for market novelties, 8.6% fell upon product innovations which were not new to the market, but only new to the enterprise. Altogether, 23% of the enterprises introduced at least one market novelty onto their market between 2016 and 2018. In 55% of the enterprises

new or improved business processes were introduced.⁹

€ 9.8 billion were spent in total on innovation activities. 83 % of those expenditures fell upon research and development (R&D) and 17 % onto further innovation activities, such as the acquisition of highly developed machinery or external knowledge respectively training or design activities for innovations.

18 % of all enterprises cooperated with other enterprises or institutions on their innovation activities. Universities or other higher education institutions were the cooperation partners reported prominently; 61 % of all innovators with innovation cooperation collaborated with this type of institution.

The “lack of skilled employees” as well as the setting of “different priorities within the own enterprise” were those hampering factors for innovations which were quoted most often by enterprises with a degree of “high importance” (Statistics Austria 2020g).

As the group of migrants (EU-27 or Non-EU-27) living in Austria has a lower share of tertiary education it is therefore likely that they are underrepresented in Austrian R&D personnel.

Conclusion

This Statistical Briefing examines the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Austria.

By 2040, Austria will have 9.4 million inhabitants. Without immigration from abroad, the population would then be 7.2 million, i.e. less than today. Austria's population will grow as a result of immigration solely. According to the forecasts, Austria's population will grow at a slightly higher rate in the future than in the recent past. The immigration will have the most impact in Vienna, which will be

populated by more than two million people in the second half of the 2020s. In general, urban and suburban regions are expected to grow in Austria at the expense of rural regions.

1.49 million immigrants live in Austria, or 16.7 % of the population. According to forecasts, their number will rise to 2.22 million by 2040 (+49.0 %). The share of foreign-born inhabitants thus increases to 22 % by 2040. The majority will come from EU & EFTA member states, but TCNs became more relevant in the recent past.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 1,486,223 persons with non-Austrian citizenship were living in Austria. This corresponds to a share of around 16.7 % of Austria's total population. Among non-Austrian nationals, slightly more than half came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries. 8.0 % of total population were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Austrians, EU citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Austria lying above the average.

In general, the pattern of education of the EU-28 and non-EU countries differs substantially from that of Austrians: The foreign population of third countries is disproportionately represented in primary and secondary education, whereas they are underrepresented in secondary and tertiary education levels (ISCED2011). Austria and the EU-27 do not differ much in terms of educational levels.

To a certain degree, this explains why inclusion in the labor market is lower among migrants than among nationals. In 2019, the employment rate for domestic workers (15 to 64 years old) was 76.7 %, for people from the EU-28 countries 75,1% and third countries 69.5%.

⁹ These business process innovations included; New or improved methods for producing goods or providing services; new or improved logistics, delivery or distribution methods; new or improved methods for information processing or communication; new or improved methods for accounting or

other administrative operations; new or improved business practices for organizing procedures or external relations; new or improved methods of organizing work responsibility, decision making or human resource management; new or improved marketing methods.

While domestic workers in 2019 were mostly employed in manufacturing and trade (both approx. 14 %), health care and social work (approx. 10 %) and construction (approx. 8 %), the same applies to migrant workers, with a majority of migrant workers working in manufacturing (approx. 16 %) and trade (approx. 15 %), closely followed by accommodation and food services (approx. 12 %) and construction (approx. 11 %).

As working Austrians and EU-28 citizens have a higher educational attainment level than Non EU-28, this could be one reason that their income is higher. As the TCNs immigrants are on average younger than Austrians, immigration increases the ratio of workers to retirees, therewith shielding the economy against the long-term financing challenge of social security.

The below average regional GDP growth rate, especially in rural provinces like Burgenland and Carinthia, is indirectly linked to immigration from abroad but preferably to internal migration from rural areas to cities (especially to the cities and metropolitan areas of Vienna and Graz). These emigrations tend to reinforce the erosion of the economic basis, as they have a negative impact on the potential workforce and the economic attractiveness of the region. Economic performance is

stagnating, accompanied by declining population figures. This development is also typical for rural regions of other provinces (Salzkammergut, Lungau, etc.).

Provinces with a high share of TCNs mostly have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. This finding correlates with the population density. The higher it is, the more economically attractive a regional entity is for both groups, domestic (Austrian) and foreign population (EU-28 & TCN).

Governments need to invest in education on the one hand and in research and development on the other, to enable long-term prosperity and growth. Currently the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) are estimated at 3.18 % (2019) which is a slight increase of 0.13 percentage points to 2017. But there is again a striking regional variation from densely populated areas with a high number of innovative enterprises (e.g. Vienna and Styria) to less densely populated provinces (e.g. Lower Austria and Burgenland).

Summing up, immigrants play a pivotal role in reviving and growing many rural areas communities, and with the appropriate policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

Statistical Briefings Bulgaria

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Bulgaria on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

BULGARIA

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Bulgaria

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Bulgaria

On January 1, 2020, a total of 104,642 persons with non-Bulgarian citizenship were living in Bulgaria. This corresponds to a share of 1.5 % of Bulgaria's total population. Among non-Bulgarian nationals, only 13.7 % (14,342 persons; 0.2 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (190 persons; 0.003 %). A total of 90,110 persons (or 1.3 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Bulgarians, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Bulgaria lying way below the average. Considering the nationalities of TCN, Russians (0,38 %) are above Turks (0.28 %), Syrians (0.20 %) and Ukrainians (0.11 %). In total, almost 9 out of 10 (87.2 %) TCN living in Bulgaria belong

to these nationalities; there is no data about citizenship available for 0.16 % of the population. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Bulgaria.

Population Development & Population Structure

The number of inhabitants in Bulgaria has already decreased in the past and this development is projected to continue in the future. As of January 1, 2020, there were 6,951,482 persons registered in Bulgaria. This corresponds to a decrease of 1,283,355 citizens (-15.1 %) within the last 20 years since 2000 (before eastward enlargement of EU in 2004). The main causes of population decline are emigration of Bulgarian inhabitants to prosperous countries and low fertility rates.

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2000 to 2020), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

A long-term analysis of population development since the turn of the new millennium reveals clear regional differences. Varna (+6.7 %) and Sofia (+9.7 %) are the only Bulgarian NUTS 3 regions experiencing population growth since 2000. Sofia as the capital has the highest growth rate. Conversely, all other regions recorded a sharp decline in population. Relative reductions were highest for the northwestern regions Vidin (-40.3 %), Vratsa (-37.6 %) and Montana (-33.6 %; see Figure 2).

There are three main causes that explain foregone developments: (1) a migratory movement from economically less developed Eastern European countries to prosperous regions of European Union and North America (2) Ongoing rural-urban migration increasingly taking place within Bulgaria (Varna and Sofia) (3) a sharp decline in birth rates after 1990.

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and

the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., one relevant aspect is labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

As Figure 3 (a)-(c) indicate, the decrease in the working-age population within the regions is mainly caused by the decrease in the Bulgarian population (-600,300 inh.). As the share of foreigners is very small and decreased in the past as well (-3,400 inh.) immigration has no impact to alleviate or worsen the problem. Summing up, both, domestic population groups are (re-)locating in cities and metropolitan regions (especially Sofia and

Varna). This is at the expense of rural areas which are experiencing an overall decline in population.

From a regional perspective the areas with the highest working-age population declines are located in the north, i.e. northwestern (-30.3%), northern central (-23.8%), and east, i.e. south-eastern (-13.5%) and northeastern (-10.3%).

In other words, this is the case for all regions except for the southwestern part of Bulgaria where Sofia is located with a stagnating population in working-age (0.0%). These past developments underline the high relevance of migration concerning the development of the working-age population especially for rural regions. Immigration of non-Bulgarians was of negligible relevance in the past as the share of foreigners is quite low. Due to the out migration of Bulgarians to North America and Central Europe the labor force potential, i.e. populations between 20 and 64 years shrunk dramatically in the past, being a challenge from an economic point of view (see Figure 3 (a) and (b)). Also, the future projections up to 2040 (Figure 4) give reason for concern. Except of a projected stagnating development in Sofia, all Bulgarian regions show a decline in working-age population – up to even almost 50%.

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be “dependent” on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being in working age from 20 to 64 years, capable of providing this support. The total-age dependency ratio in 2020 in Bulgaria is 68.2%. The dependency ratio is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are a more prosperous economy, i.e. a high ratio of working people, and low child ratios. Most metropolitan regions in Bulgaria are also characterized by relatively low rates (e.g., Sofia: 57.50%). High dependency ratios are found in regions where the share of children and the elderly (65 years and older) is above average. These regions are mainly Vidin (86.57%), Lovech

(82.69%) and Pleven (81.72%). As a result of ageing societies, the total-age dependency ratio will rise in the future by 13.8 pp to 82.1% in 2040 resulting in implications for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., fiscal policy).

Figure 3: Working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2003 to 2019), NUTS 2
(a)

(b)

(c)

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

Figure 4: Projections of working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of Bulgaria's domestic population is 24.6 %, which is only slightly below that of the total population (24.7 %). Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) Bulgaria has a below-average tertiary education rate. Bulgaria ranks 21th within the EU-28, ahead of Portugal (23.8 %), Slovakia (23.1 %) and Hungary (22.5 %). Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities¹ than in towns and suburbs²,

which in turn is higher than in rural areas³. In rural areas in Bulgaria, only 8.3 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 20.5 % in towns & suburbs and 36.1 % in cities.

In contrast, secondary degrees are more common in less densely populated areas. While less than 50.6 % of city residents have secondary, i.e. upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 3 to 4) attainment level, 59.2 % and 53.6 % of residents in towns & suburbs and rural areas do so. Due to lack of data no statements can be made in regard to immigrants and/or foreigners living in Bulgaria (see Table 1).

¹ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020e).

² Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population

density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020f; Eurostat 2020g).

³ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat 2020h; Eurostat 2020i).

Table 1: Working-age population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Bulgarians	13.4%	50.6%	36.1%
	EU-28	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Non EU-28	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Total	13.4%	50.6%	36.1%
Towns & suburbs	Bulgarians	20.3%	59.2%	20.5%
	EU-28	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Non EU-28	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Total	20.3%	59.2%	20.5%
Rural	Bulgarians	38.1%	53.6%	8.3%
	EU-28	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Non EU-28	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
	Total	38.1%	53.6%	8.3%

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

The unemployment rate in Bulgaria is 4.2 %, being below the EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, North Western has the highest unemployment rate at 10.6 % (female: 9.2 %; male: 11.9 %), followed by Northeastern (5.9 %; female: 6.6. %; male: 5.3 %) and Northern Central (5.1 %; female: 4.8 %; male: 5.4 %). Southwestern (2.2 %; female: 1.9 %; male: 2.5%), Southeastern (2.5 %; female: 2.3 %; male: 4.5%) and Southern Central (3.0 %; female: 2.8 %; male: 3.2 %) are the provinces with the lowest unemployment rates (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be

seen for Bulgaria. Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (13.0 %) and this situation has remained constant for years. Conversely, people with tertiary education have the lowest unemployment rate (1.9 %), those with secondary education a value of 3.4 %. The same trend can be observed at the European level (EU-28; Figure 6).

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher the employment rate, i.e. 88.5 % for tertiary, 76.0 % for secondary and 51.2 % for primary level. No reliable statements can be made due to a lack of data probably caused by the low number of foreigners living in Bulgaria.

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female:

8.6 %). Bulgaria ranges with a value of 13.9 % above the European average. In total, almost two thirds (63.3 %) of all early leavers are jobless but no relying statements can be made in regard to migrational status because of missing data (Eurostat 2020l).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁴ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income. Working persons in Bulgaria at primary level earn less (mean: € 2,868; median: € 2,532) than secondary (€ 5,544 or € 4,819) and tertiary levels (€ 10,030 or € 7,282; see Figure 7). The mean equivalized net income of Bulgarians is higher than of foreigners (€ 6,194 vs. € 5,551) though it is the opposite when analyzing the median (€ 4,899 vs. € 4,799). Therefore, no clear and reliable statements can be made in regard to income which is probably because of the low number of foreigners living in Bulgaria (see Figure 8).

Figure 7: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020m), own illustration

⁴ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

The indicator ‘people at risk of poverty or social exclusion’ corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. Almost one quarter of foreigners (24.7 %) belongs to this group whereas the situation for the domestic population is slightly worse (+7.8 pp or 32.5 %) are comparably low (see Table 2). Due to a lack of data no statements can be made in regard to EU-28 citizens or TCNs.

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers’ social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 %. Bulgaria (43.7 %) lies below European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 11.5 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 44.8 % of GDP in Bulgaria, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. Bulgarian GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 61.2 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 8,780 (Eurostat 2020p).

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty			
		At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Bulgaria		Foreign country	
Very low	Severe	2.6	0.6	0.8	0.0
Not very low	Severe	8.6	9.3	3.9	1.2
Very low	Non severe	1.4	1.1	1.8	0.8
Not very low	Non severe	8.9		16.2	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		32.5		24.7	
		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		67.5		75.4
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		67.5		75.4	
Total		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

Table 3: Nominal regional GDP 2019 and real growth rate (Δ 2002 to 2019)

Region	Total		Per Capita	
	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices (Index, 2015=100; Δ 2002 to 2019)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market prices	Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average
Northern and Eastern Bulgaria	21,623	33.4	6,200	38
Northwestern	3,939	11.1	5,400	32
Northern Central	4,557	31.7	5,900	35
Northeastern	6,308	44.3	6,800	41
Southeastern	6,819	36.5	6,600	40
South-Western and South Central Bulgaria	39,617	69.9	11,300	68
Southwestern	30,951	75.2	14,800	89
Southern Central	8,666	51.6	6,200	37
Bulgaria	61,240	56.2	8,800	53

Source: Eurostat (2020q), own illustration;
Eurostat (2020r), own illustration

Within the last 20 years Bulgaria's gross value added (GVA) increased by +56.2 % (real growth rate). In terms of regional GVA all NUTS 2 regions recorded positive real growth, ranging from +11.1 % in North Western to +75.2 % in Southeastern since 2000. The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred also in Southeastern (approx. € 14,800) succeeded by Northeastern

(approx. € 6,800). As in previous years, all regions except Southwestern were below the national level of € 8,800.

Provinces with a high share of foreigners have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries or regions. There are significant differences in levels of prosperity among Bulgarian NUTS 2 regions. The most prosperous region in Bulgaria is Southwestern (89 %); it is over 57/54/52 pp richer than North Western/ Northern Central/ Southern Central. Northeastern ranks second (41 %) and Southeastern third (40 %; see Table 3).

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors.

In total, approx. 2.3 million people were employed in 2019 in Bulgaria. This corresponds to an increase of +3.0 % compared to 2015. Almost two thirds (65.7 %) are employed in the service sector, where employment has increased by +5.2 % since 2015. Employment in secondary and primary sec-

tor shrunk by -0.9 % and -1.7 %. Generally speaking “Agriculture, forestry and fishing” is of very low importance, i.e. only 3.0 % of total employment (see Table 4).

A more detailed examination of the different sectors of the economy reveals that there have also been significant shifts within the sectors: the only declines in employment were recorded in the sections " Mining and quarrying" (-22.3 %), "Education" (-1.7 %), " Agriculture, forestry and fishing" (-

1.7 %), “Manufacturing” (-1.4 %) and “Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply” (-1.4 %). " Information and communication" (+29.1 %), " Professional, scientific and technical activities" (+11.3 %) as well as " Accommodation and food service activities" (+10.8 %), on the other hand, are among those economic sections with the largest absolute growth. There is no information available about the citizenship of the workers (see Table 4).

Table 4: Employment by economic activity 2019

Economic Activity	Employed persons in 2019	Share	Δ 15-19
Primary Sector	69,726	3.0%	-1.7%
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	69,726	3.0%	-1.7%
Secondary Sector	726,309	31.3%	-0.9%
Mining and quarrying	19,137	0.8%	-22.3%
Manufacturing	505,119	21.7%	-1.4%
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	29,834	1.3%	-1.4%
Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities	36,955	1.6%	5.8%
Construction	135,264	5.8%	3.6%
Tertiary Sector	1,526,526	65.7%	5.2%
Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	379,575	16.3%	1.6%
Transportation and storage	149,934	6.5%	5.9%
Accommodation and food service activities	122,458	5.3%	10.8%
Information and communication	102,249	4.4%	29.1%
Financial and insurance activities	56,872	2.4%	2.3%
Real estate activities	23,971	1.0%	5.0%
Professional, scientific and technical activities	82,840	3.6%	11.3%
Administrative and support service activities	116,941	5.0%	8.0%
Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	112,322	4.8%	0.2%
Education	162,757	7.0%	-1.7%
Human health and social work activities	140,448	6.0%	2.5%
Arts, entertainment and recreation	36,989	1.6%	9.2%
Other service activities	39,170	1.7%	7.1%
Total	2,322,561	100.0%	3.0%

Source: NSI (2021), own illustration

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 0.76 % for Bulgaria (2018) which is a slight increase of 0.02 pp to 2017. The total amount of research expenditures was € 423.8 million, the largest share (43.4 %) was financed by the business enterprise sector. 32.9 % were financed by foreign countries (rest of the world) and 23.7 %

were funded by the government sector (Eurostat 2020s).

Regional data is published on NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 level. Southwestern was the province with the highest ratio in 2018 (1.14 %). Northwestern followed in second place with 0.49 % just ahead of Southern Central (0.44 %) and Northeastern (0.43 %). The ratio in the remaining provinces is 0.32 % (Northern Central and South Eastern; see Table 5).

In accordance to the R&D funding structure almost one half (43.4 %) of the researchers work in the business enterprise sector. Approx. one third (30.6 %) works in the government sector, one quarter (25.3 %) in the higher education sector and 0.6 % in the private non-profit sector. This makes a total of 15,094 full-time equivalent (FTE). Further analysis on educational attainment level

reveals that most researchers (54.5 %) have tertiary education but not doctoral or equivalent level; 41.1 % belong to the latter whereas 4.4 % have less than primary, primary, secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (see Figure 9).

Table 5: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
Northern and Eastern Bulgaria	79.7	0.38%
Northwestern	19.1	0.49%
Northern Central	13.6	0.32%
Northeastern	25.4	0.43%
Southeastern	21.5	0.32%
South-Western and South Central Bulgaria	344.1	0.98%
Southwestern	308.8	1.14%
Southern Central	35.3	0.44%
Bulgaria	423.8	0.76%

Source: Eurostat (2020t), own illustration

Figure 9: R&D researchers (full-time equivalent (FTE)) by sectors of performance and educational attainment level 2017 (ISCED2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020u), own illustration

Conclusion

This Statistical Briefings examines the economic and spatial importance and impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Bulgaria.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 104,642 persons with non-Bulgarian citizenship were living in Bulgaria. This corresponds to a share of 1.5 % of Bulgaria's total population. Among non-Bulgarian nationals, only 13.7 % came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA. A total of 90,110 persons (or 1.3 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Bulgarians, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens.

Within the last 20 years the population decline of Bulgaria has mainly been dominated by emigration of Bulgarians to more prosperous regions and

countries. From 2003 to 2019 almost all Bulgarian NUTS 2 regions suffered heavily with regard to the working-age population. As the share of immigrants was of low importance in the past, foreigners as TCN had almost no impact on the development of the labor force potential (population aged between 20 and 64 years).

Projections regarding the working-age population up to 2040 give reason for concern; with the exception of Sofia (with a stagnating projection) all regions will further loose people aged between 20 and 65 years. A decrease in emigration as well as an increase in immigration of TCN could therefore play a pivotal role in reviving its (rural) areas.

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MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Finland on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

FINLAND

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Finland

Source: Eurostat (2020a)

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Finland

On January 1, 2020, a total of 267,629 persons with non-Finnish citizenship were living in Finland. This corresponds to a share of 4.8 % of Finland's total population. Among non-Finnish nationals, 37.8 % (101,072 persons; 1.8 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (1,553 persons; 0.03 %). A total of 165,004 persons (or 3.0 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Finnish, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Finland lying below the average.

Considering the nationalities of TCN, Russians (0.52 %) are above Iraqis (0.25 %), Chinese (incl. Hong Kong; 0.18 %), Thai (0.14 %) and Indians (0.12 %). In total, 40.5 % of TCN living in Finland belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an

overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Finland.

Population Development & Population Structure

The number of inhabitants in Finland increased in the past but according to recent projections a decrease of population will take place in the future. As of January 1, 2020, there were 5,525,292 persons registered in Finland. This corresponds to an increase of 353,990 citizens (+ 6.8 %) within the last 20 years since 2000 (before eastward enlargement of EU in 2004).

A long-term analysis of population development since the turn of the new millennium reveals clear regional differences. Helsinki-Uusimaa (+19.96 %),

Åland (+ 14.90 %)¹ and Pirkanmaa (+14.03 %) recorded the highest increase of population. Approx. half of the regions recorded population growth, others registered a considerable population

downturn: Kainuu (-14.43 %), Etelä-Savo (-13.91 %) and Kymenlaakso (-8.32 %; see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2000 to 2020), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

¹ The Åland Islands is an autonomous Finnish region and holds a special legal status in the EU (Government of Åland Island, 2020). It has its own operation program under the Cohesion Policy receiving funding from the European Regional Development Fund and the European Social Fund

(CEC, 2020). Over the last 15 year, Åland Islands is one of the Nordic regions displaying the highest rate of regional development. Despite being rural and remote, Åland Islands is a wealthy and well-off region (Rauhut and Costa, 2021).

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., another economically relevant aspect is the labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

As Figure 3 (a)-(d) indicate, the working-age population in Finland already decreased within the time period considered (-49,800 inh.). The decline would have been even higher without immigration from EU-28 (except Finnish; +28,300 inh.) and non-EU 28 (+52,900 inh.) countries, as the working-age population of Finnish people shrank since 2006 (-133,000 inh.). From a regional perspective, Helsinki-Uusimaa (+9.5 %) was the only region growing, while Åland (+0.6 %) almost stagnated. Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi (-8.3 %), Etelä-Suomi (-7.2 %) and Länsi-Suomi (-3.2 %) recorded the highest declines.

Figure 3: Working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2006 to 2019)

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

According to current forecasts the decrease of labor force potential does not stop in the future. Working-age population is projected to decrease by – 3.3 % until 2040. There are only 3 regions which are projected to grow in the future, i.e. Helsinki-Uusimaa (8.13 %), Åland (+ 5.08 %) and Pirkanmaa (1.03 %; see Figure 4).

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be “dependent” on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being at working age from 20 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in Finland in 2020 is 74.4 %. The dependency rate is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are a more prosperous economy, i.e. more people in working-age, and low child ratios. Most metropolitan regions in Finland are also characterized by relatively low ratios. High dependency ratios are found in Etelä-Pohjanmaa (90.50 %), Etelä-Savo (93.53 %) and Keski-Pohjanmaa (92.45%). As a result of the ageing society, the total-age dependency ratios will rise in the future by 2.4 pp to 77.0 % in 2040, resulting in implications/challenges for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., expenditures for pensions).

Figure 4: Projections of working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of Finland's domestic population is 39.1 %, which is only slightly above that of the total population (38.5 %). Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) Finland ranks 5th within the EU-28 next to Cyprus (40.0 %), ahead of Lithuania (37.9 %), Sweden (37.8 %) and Estonia (36.5 %). Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities than in towns and suburbs, which in turn is higher than in rural areas. In rural areas² in Finland, only 30.7 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 35.7 % in towns & suburbs³ and 45.6 % in cities⁴. While less than 39.7 % of city residents have secondary, i.e. upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 3 to 4) attainment level, 46.8 % and 49.6 % of residents in towns & suburbs and rural areas do. Primary educational attainment level has low relevance as approx. only 1 out of 5 residents in Finland belongs to this group.

Concerning the educational attainment level of TCN, big differences can be recorded. In cities, where most of the non-EU-28 citizens live, approx. 40 % (39.0 %) only have primary education. This share is even higher in towns & suburbs (49.5 %) and rural areas (45.2 %). On the contrary, only 25.6 % of non-EU-28 citizens living in cities have a university degree but this value is still much higher than in suburban (18.4 %) regions. Differences of educational attainment level between Finnish and EU-28 residents range within a broad band from 1.8 pp to 16.8 pp and are therefore scarcely comparable, too (see Table 1). In total, EU-28 (28.8 %)

and non-EU-28 (23.7 %) citizens have a lower tertiary education rate than the domestic population (39.1 %).

Table 1: Working-age population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Finnish	13.1%	40.0%	46.9%
	EU-28	29.9%	35.7%	34.4%
	Non EU-28	39.0%	35.3%	25.6%
	Total	14.6%	39.7%	45.6%
Towns & suburbs	Finnish	16.8%	47.1%	36.2%
	EU-28	33.4%	43.8%	22.9%
	Non EU-28	49.5%	32.2%	18.4%
	Total	17.5%	46.8%	35.7%
Rural	Finnish	19.3%	49.7%	31.0%
	EU-28	35.3%	47.9%	n.a.
	Non EU-28	45.2%	35.0%	n.a.
	Total	19.7%	49.6%	30.7%

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

The unemployment rate in Finland is 6.1 %, being close to EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi has the highest unemployment rate at 7.3 % (female: 5.9 %; male: 8.5 %). All other regions range close to each other, with Helsinki-Uusimaa recording the lowest rate (5.7 %; female: 5.6 %; male: 5.9 %; see Figure 5).

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for Finland. Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (12.4 %). Conversely, people with tertiary education have the lowest unemployment rate (4.0 %), those with secondary a value of 7.1 %. Similar results are observed at the European level (EU-28; see Figure 6)

² A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat 2020e; Eurostat 2020f).

³ Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous

grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020g; Eurostat 2020h).

⁴ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020i).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment level, the higher the employment rate, i.e. 86.2 % for tertiary, 74.6 % for secondary and 52.0 % for primary level. From an immigrational point of view, this observation holds for other citizenships

as well, as the risk of unemployment decreases by the highest educational attainment.

As Figure 7 shows, Finns have the highest employment rate for tertiary educational attainment level (86.7 %), but EU-28 ranks first for primary (76.6 % vs. 52.2 %) and secondary educational attainment level (80.3 % vs. 74.9 %). Non-EU-28 citizens have the lowest employment rate on each level (62.6 %; 58.1 %; 40.2 %).

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

Figure 7: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020l), own illustration

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). Finland ranges with a value of 7.3 % below the European average. The share of EU-28 citizens residing in Finland and that of non-EU-28 residents is slightly higher than that of the domestic population (7.1 %). In total, approx. 60 % (58.9 %) of early school leavers are jobless, but no relying statements can be made in regard to the immigrational status due to missing data (Eurostat 2020m).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁵ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income.

Working persons in Finland at primary educational level earn less (mean: € 24,150; median: € 21,093) than secondary (mean: € 26,793; median: € 24,941) and tertiary levels (mean: € 35,692; median: € 32,027; see Figure 8). As working Finnish people have a higher educational attainment level (in regard to tertiary education rate) than EU-28 and non-EU-28 (see Table 1) this could be one reason (amongst others) that their mean (€ 30,000 vs. € 28,531 and € 21,449) and median (€ 27,170 vs. € 23,028 and € 18,882) equivalized net income is higher (see Figure 9).

⁵ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

A further analysis and decomposition of wage differentials between domestic and foreign workers done by Lehmer and Ludsteck (2013) reveals that factors like seniority, promotions to better-paid occupations as well as job stability also have to be taken into account. These factors cause an improvement in an individual's firm-specific

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty							
		At risk		Not at risk		At risk		Not at risk	
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Finland		EU-28		Non EU-28			
Very low	Severe	0.4	0.4	2.0	0.6	4.7	2.7		
Not very low	Severe	0.4	1.0	0.7	1.0	0.0	3.2		
Very low	Non severe	3.3	2.4	0.0	5.2	8.8	5.2		
Not very low	Non severe	7.6		8.2		9.9			
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		15.5		17.7		34.5			
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk			
Not very low	Non severe		84.5		82.3		65.4		
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		84.5		82.3		65.4			
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0			

Source: Eurostat (2020p), own illustration

human capital (training on the job) as the median age of foreign workers and therefore the length of time within the company is lower than for domestic ones. However, these assumptions cannot be verified in the context of this analysis due to a lack of available data.

The indicator 'people at risk of poverty or social exclusion' corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. As non-EU 28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than domestic and EU-28 residents, more than one third (34.5 %) belongs to this group. EU-28 citizens (17.7 %) and Finnish (15.5 %) face the lowest risk of social exclusion and poverty (see Table 2).

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers' social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 %. Finland (46.6 %) lies below the European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 12.8 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 40.6 % of GDP in Austria, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. Finnish GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 240.3 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 43,510 (Eurostat 2020tq).

Table 3 provides information about nominal regional GDP and real growth rates, whereas the federal states (NUTS 1) are grey-shaded. Within 20

years Finland's gross value added (GVA) increased by 23,4 % (real growth rate). In terms of regional

Table 3: Nominal regional GDP (2019) and real growth rate (Δ 2002)

Region	Total		Per Capita	
	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices (Index, 2015=100; Δ 2002 to 2019)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market prices	Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average
Manner-Suomi	239,126	23.5	43,500	111
Länsi-Suomi	52,967	20.1	38,400	98
Helsinki-Uusimaa	94,961	29.9	56,500	144
Etelä-Suomi	44,756	16.6	38,900	99
Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi	46,442	21.5	36,200	93
Åland	1,359	12.2	45,500	116
Finland	240,561	23.4	43,600	111

Source: Eurostat (2020r), own illustration; Eurostat (2020s), own illustration

GVA all provinces also recorded positive real growth, ranging from 12.2 % in Åland to 29.9 % in Helsinki-Uusimaa since 2000. The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred also in Helsinki-Uusimaa (approx. € 56,500) succeeded by Åland (approx. € 45,500). As in previous years, all other provinces were below the national level of € 43,600 (Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi: € 36,200; Länsi-Suomi: € 38,400; Etelä-Suomi: € 38,900; see Table 3).

Table 4: Employment by economic activity 2019

Occupational Groups	Employed persons in 2018	Share	Δ 10-18	Finnish	EU-28 & EFTA	TCN
Armed forces	8,015	0.3%	-21.9%	99.6%	0.1%	0.3%
Managers	95,823	4.0%	14.0%	96.0%	1.7%	2.3%
Professionals	483,791	20.4%	14.3%	94.4%	2.0%	3.6%
Technicians and associate professionals	430,756	18.1%	2.3%	96.5%	1.2%	2.3%
Clerical support workers	130,288	5.5%	-23.6%	95.9%	1.3%	2.8%
Service and sales workers	479,199	20.2%	1.9%	92.5%	2.0%	5.5%
Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers	53,533	2.3%	-28.0%	94.1%	1.8%	4.1%
Craft and related trades workers	245,237	10.3%	-2.4%	91.4%	4.7%	3.9%
Plant and machine operators, and assemblers	202,202	8.5%	-5.2%	93.2%	2.4%	4.4%
Elementary occupations	155,083	6.5%	-1.6%	82.9%	5.0%	12.1%
Unknown	89,741	3.8%	81.4%	88.2%	4.2%	7.7%
Total	2,373,668	100.0%	2.1%	93.2%	2.4%	4.5%

Source: StatFin (2019), own calculations and illustration

Provinces with a high share of TCN have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries or regions. There are significant differences in levels of prosperity among Finnish provinces. The most prosperous region in Finland is Helsinki-Uusimaa (144 %); it is over 51/46/45/28 pp richer than Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi/Länsi-Suomi/Etelä-Suomi/Åland; see Table 3).

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In total, approx. 2.4 million people were employed in 2018 in Finland. This corresponds to an increase of +2.1 % compared to 2010. Up to occupational groups more than two thirds (69.0 %) work as "Professionals" (20.4 %), "Service and sales workers" (20.2 %), "Technicians and associate professionals" (18.1 %) and "Craft and related trades workers" (10.3 %). The highest growth rates are in the groups of "Professionals" (14.3 %) and "Managers" (14.0 %) whereas "Technicians and associate professionals" (2.3 %) and "Service and sales workers" (1.9 %) evolved at average level. All remain groups diminished with the highest declines

in "Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers" (-28.0 %) and "Clerical support workers" (-23.6 %; see Table 3).

Further analysis by citizenship shows that 2.4 % belong to the group of EU-28 & EFTA (2.4 %) or TCN (4.5 %). EU-28 & EFTA citizens are overrepresented in "Craft and related trades workers" (4.7 %) and "Elementary occupations" (5.0 %). TCN tend to work in the same categories (3.9 % and 12.1 %) but also in "Service and sales workers" (5.5 %), "Plant and machine operators, and assemblers" (4.4 %) and "Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers" (4.1 %). Due to a lack of information the category "Unknown" is excluded from the analysis.

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditures on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 2.79 % for Finland (2019) which is a slight increase of 0.06 percentage points to 2017. The total amount of research expenditures was € 6.72 billion, the largest share (54,5 %) was

financed by the business enterprise sector. 28.0 % were financed by the government sector. 15.4 % were financed by foreign countries (rest of the world) and 1.8 % were funded by the private non-profit sector (Eurostat (2020u)).

Data on regional level (NUTS 2) is published with a one year time lag. Helsinki-Uusimaa is the province with the highest ratio in 2018 (3.48 %) succeeded by Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi (2.56 %) and Länsi-Suomi (2.54 %). Etelä-Suomi (1.72 %) takes fifth and Åland (only 0.41 %) last place, see Table 5).

Table 5: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
Manner-Suomi	6,432.3	2.76%
Länsi-Suomi	1,320.8	2.54%
Helsinki-Uusimaa	3,177.2	3.48%
Etelä-Suomi	756.1	1.72%
Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi	1,178.2	2.56%
Åland	5.6	0.41%
Finland	6,437.7	2.76%

Source: Source: Eurostat (2020t), own illustration

Conclusion

This Statistical Briefing examines the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Finland.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 267,629 persons with non-Finnish citizenship were living in Finland. This corresponds to a share of 4.8 % of Finland's total population. Among non-Finnish nationals, 37.8 % (1.8 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (0.03 %). 3.0 % of total population were third country nationals, being individuals who are neither Finnish, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Finland lying below the average.

Within the last 20 years the working-age population in Finland did already decrease. Although all regions recorded an immigration of EU-28 and Non-EU-28 residents, this development could not be stopped due to the comparable high decrease of Finnish people in working-age.

Despite the relevance of migration for labor supply, the employment rate of TCN is much lower compared to Finnish and EU-28 citizens. One relevant factor to be considered here is the lower educational attainment level of migrants, with the consecutive effects of lower income levels and a higher risk of poverty.

The pattern of education of TCN differs substantially from that of Finnish nationals: The foreign population of third countries is disproportionately represented in primary education, whereas they are underrepresented in secondary and tertiary educational levels.

From a spatial point of view, the concentration of better-educated migrants is highest in Finnish cities. Provinces with a higher ratio of TCN are also characterized by higher economic growth, being more attractive for TCN on the one hand and offering more labor supply on the other hand.

The below average regional GVA growth rate, especially in rural provinces like Etelä-Suomi is indirectly linked to immigration from abroad but preferably to internal migration from rural areas to cities and metropolitan areas. These emigration flows tend to reinforce the erosion of the economic basis, because they have a negative impact on the potential workforce and the economic attractiveness of the region. Economic performance is stagnating, accompanied by declining population figures.

Governments need to invest in education and in research and development (R&D) to enable long-term prosperity and growth. Currently the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) are estimated at 2.79 % for Finland (2019) which is a slight increase of 0.06 percentage points to 2017. But there is again a striking regional variation from densely populated areas with a high number of innovative enterprises (e.g. Helsinki-Uusimaa) to less densely populated provinces.

Summing up, immigrants in Finland play a significant role in reviving rural areas, and with the appropriate policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Germany on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

GERMANY

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Germany

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Germany

On January 1, 2020, a total of 10,398,022 persons with non-German citizenship were living in Germany. This corresponded to a share of 12.5 % of Germany's total population. Among non-German nationals, almost one half (4,454,418 persons; 6.1 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (51,411 persons; 0.07 %). A total of 5,892,193 persons (or 7.1 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCNs), being individuals who are neither Germans, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCNs in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) was 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Germany was above the average.

Considering the nationalities of TCNs, Turks (1.59 %) are above Syrians (0.91 %), Russians (0.28 %), Afghans (0.27 %), Iraqis (0.27 %) and

Bosnians and Herzegovinians (0.24 %). In total, almost more than one half of TCNs living in Germany belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Germany.

Population Development & Population Structure

While the number of inhabitants in Germany has increased in the past, it is projected to decrease in the future. As of January 1, 2020, there were 83,166,711 persons registered in Germany. This corresponds to an increase of 1,003,236 citizens (+1.22 %) within the last 20 years since 2000 (before the eastward enlargement of the EU in 2004).

The main cause of population growth is immigration to Germany (EU-28, EFTA & third countries) as the birth rate is only slightly higher than the death rate of the domestic population.

A long-term analysis of population development since the turn of the new millennium reveals clear regional differences. 54.9 % of German NUTS 3-regions have more inhabitants than in 2000. Potsdam located near the capital Berlin has the highest growth rate (29.1 %). Regions surrounding Munich as well as the former German Democratic Republic (GDR) cities of Dresden and Leipzig followed a similar trajectory. Conversely, most of the eastern German regions recorded a sharp decline in population. Relative reductions were highest for Oberspreewald-Lausitz in Brandenburg (26.2%); also nearby NUTS 3-regions shrunk by more than 20 %.

There are three main causes that explain foregone developments: (1) a migratory movement from Eastern to Western Germany took place in the past for the benefit of many regions in the former German *Länder* (federal states, NUTS 1). It has become less significant as net migration has been balanced in recent years. (2) Ongoing rural-urban migration increasingly taking place within Eastern Germany and (3) a sharp decline in birth rates after 1990.

Rural and socio-economically weak regions in Western Germany also experienced a loss in the number of inhabitants. On the one hand, these areas are located far away from prosperous regions and their centers or, on the other hand, population shrank as a result of structural change (e.g. Ruhr region; see Figure 2).

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., one prominent field lies on the relevance of labour supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labour (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labour force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

Analyzing the working-age population at NUTS 1 level, the strong dispersion is striking. The median German working-age population development is 0.0 %, i.e. half of the *Länder* has grown, and the

other half has shrunk. As can be seen in Figure 3 (a) the working-age population increased in the southern states and Berlin in particular, while a sharp decrease occurred in the Eastern States. In general, the German working-age population is relocating to the regions, cities and metropolitan areas of Swabia, Upper Bavaria, Darmstadt, Stuttgart, and Trier etc. (NUTS 2).

As Figure 3 (b)-(d) indicate, the increase in the working-age population within the regions is mainly caused by the increase in the non-German population. Without immigration, all German states would have suffered from a downturn in working-age population, with the exception of Bavaria with a stagnating development. Summing up, many rural areas are experiencing an overall decline in population, often mainly triggered by (re)location trends to cities and metropolitan regions. In particular, this is the case for Eastern Germany, which is expected to shrink in the future especially in terms of working-age population.

From a regional perspective, the areas with the highest declines of working-age population are located in Brandenburg, i.e. Frankfurt (Oder) (-22.64 %), Oberspreewald-Lausitz (-21.32 %), Spree-Neiße (-19.06 %), Uckermark (-18.72 %) and Cottbus (-17.14 %). These regions, often considered peripheral, are characterised by the declining coal industry. They suffer from higher depopulation and birth rate deficits.

Analyzing working-age population developments up to 2040, solely the metropolitan areas are expected to grow, though there are differences between the eastern and western part of Germany. While the labour force potential will rapidly grow in the West, e.g. Cologne, Dortmund, Düsseldorf or Frankfurt, and the South, e.g. Augsburg, Munich, Nuremberg, Stuttgart, etc. the growth will be restrained in the East, e.g. Berlin, Dresden, Leipzig or Magdeburg (see Figure 4).

These past and future developments underline the high relevance of migration, especially for rural regions, concerning the development of the working-age population. Without immigration, its population between 20 and 64 years would shrink, even more dramatically, representing a challenge from an economic point of view.

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be ‘dependent’ on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being working age from 20 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in 2020 in Germany is 67.3 %. Due to prospering economy and

low child ratios, most metropolitan areas and cities in Germany are characterized by relatively low rates (e.g., Münster: 53.4 %). High dependency ratios, in contrast, are found in rural regions and regions where the share of children and the elderly (65 years and older) is above average. These regions are mainly found in Saxony (e.g., Görlitz 87.1 %). As a result of ageing societies, the total-age dependency ratios are expected to rise in the future by 20.2 pp to 87.5 % in 2040 resulting in implications for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., fiscal policy).

Figure 2: Population Development (Δ 2000 to 2020), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

Figure 3: Working-age Population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2006 to 2019)

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

Figure 4: Projections of Working-age Population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040) NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of Germany's domestic population is 26.7 %, which is only slightly above that of the total population (26.0 %). Compared to the EU-28 average (29.5 %), Germany has a below-average tertiary education rate. Germany ranks 20th within the EU-28, ahead of Bulgaria (24.7 %), Portugal (23.8 %) and Slovakia (23.1 %). Luxem-

bourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities¹ than in towns and suburbs², which in turn is higher than in rural areas. In rural

¹ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020e).

² Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the

population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020f; Eurostat 2020g).

areas³ in Germany, only 21.2 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 23.3 % in towns & suburbs and 31.7 % in cities. In contrast, secondary degrees are more common in less densely populated areas. While less than 48.2 % of city residents have secondary, i.e. upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 3 to 4) attainment level, 56.2 % and 62.1 % of residents in towns & suburbs and rural areas do so.

In cities, where most of the non-EU-28 citizens live, more than 40 % have only primary education, i.e. less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (ISCED levels 0 to 2, see Table 1). This share is even higher in towns & suburbs (51.2 %) and rural areas (52.4 %). On contrary, only 24.6 % of non-EU-28 citizens have a degree from university but this value is still much higher than in suburban (15.7 %) and rural (15.4 %) regions. Differences of educational attainment level between Germans and EU-28 citizens range within a broad band from 2.0 pp to 17.3 pp and are therefore scarcely comparable (see Table 1). In total, EU-28 (23.2 %) and non-EU-28 (20.7 %) citizens have a lower tertiary education rate than domestic population (26.7 %).

Table 1: Working-age population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Germans	15.4%	51.5%	33.1%
	EU-28	30.6%	41.2%	28.2%
	Non EU-28	43.5%	31.8%	24.6%
	Total	20.1%	48.2%	31.7%
Towns & suburbs	Germans	16.9%	58.8%	24.3%
	EU-28	34.2%	47.3%	18.5%
	Non EU-28	51.2%	33.0%	15.7%
	Total	20.5%	56.2%	23.3%
Rural	Germans	15.0%	63.5%	21.5%
	EU-28	29.8%	50.8%	19.5%
	Non EU-28	52.4%	32.2%	15.4%
	Total	16.7%	62.1%	21.2%

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

From a regional perspective, Berlin has the highest unemployment rate at 5.2 % (female: 4.8 %; male: 5.6 %), followed by Bremen (4.9 %; female: n.a. %; male: 6.4 %) and Saxony-Anhalt (4.6 %; female: 4.2 %; male: 5.1 %). Bavaria (2.0 %; female: 1.9 %; male: 2.1 %), Baden-Wuerttemberg (2.3 %; female: 2.1 %; male: 2.5 %) and Rhineland-Palatinate (2.6 %; female: 2.3 %; male: 2.9%) are the provinces with the lowest unemployment rates. For Trier, there is no data available (see Figure 5). In total, the unemployment rate of Germany is 3.1 % (female: 2.7 %; male: 3.5%).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for Germany. Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (8.3 %) and this situation has remained constant for years. Conversely, people with tertiary education have

³ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat 2020h; Eurostat 2020i).

the lowest unemployment rate (1.9 %), those with secondary a value of 2.7 %. The same trend can be observed at the European level (EU-28 average; see Figure 6), even though with higher unemployment rates.

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher the employment rate, i.e. 89.0 % for tertiary, 81.3 % for secondary and 61.8 % for primary level. This observation holds for other citizenships, too, as the risk of unemployment decreases by the level of educational attainment. But Germans have the highest employment rate for tertiary educational attainment level (90.7 %) while EU-28 citizens rank first for primary (73.4 % vs. 63.9 %) and secondary educational attainment level (82.9 % vs. 82.0 %). Non-EU-28 citizens have the lowest employment rate on each level (67.9 %; 66.6 %; 51.1 %; see Figure 7).

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings though intersectional aspects (e.g., gender, race, region) have to be taken into account as well.

⁴ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

Figure 7: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020l), own illustration

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the ‘Early Leavers from Education and Training’. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). With a value of 10.3 %, Germany ranges at the European average. The share of EU-28 citizens residing in Germany is more than double (24.9 %) and that of non-EU-28 citizens is also more than double (25.7 %) than that of the domestic population (7.6 %). In total, approx. 50 % (47.6 %) of all early leavers are jobless but because of missing data no relying statements can be made with regard to the immigration status (Eurostat 2020m).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁴ equivalized net income⁵, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income.

Working persons in Germany at primary level earn less (mean: € 19,521; median: € 18,136) than secondary (€ 25,326 or € 23,699) and tertiary levels (€

⁵ Geis-Thöne (2019) criticises using net income instead of gross income in this context, as taxes and social security contributions heavily depend on family structures.

32,907 or € 29,350; see Figure 8). Working Germans earn less than EU-28 but more than non-EU-28 citizens (mean: € 27,645 vs. € 29,841 and € 21,777; median: € 24,972 vs. € 26,729 and € 19,355; see Figure 9).

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

A further analysis and decomposition of wage differentials between domestic and foreign workers done by Lehmer and Ludsteck (2013) reveals that factors like seniority, promotions to better-paid occupations as well as job stability also have to be taken into account. These factors cause an improvement in an individual's firm-specific human

capital (training on the job) as the median age of foreign workers and therefore the length of time within the company is lower than for domestic ones. However, these assumptions cannot be verified in the context of this analysis due to a lack of available data.

The indicator 'people at risk of poverty or social exclusion' corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. As non-EU-28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than Germans and EU-28 citizens, more than one quarter (28.4 %) belongs to this group whereas the values of EU-28 (14.2 %) and domestic population (17.8 %) are comparably low (see Table 2; cf. Weidinger & Kordel 2021).

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers' social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 %. Germany (53.5 %) lies above European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 9.9 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 36.6 % of GDP in Germany, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. German GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 3,449.0 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 41,510 (Eurostat 2020q).

Table 2 provides information about nominal regional GDP and real growth rates, whereas the federal states (NUTS 1) are grey-shaded. Within 20 years Germany's gross value added (GVA) increased by 23.5 % (real growth rate). In terms of regional GVA all NUTS 2 regions also recorded positive real growth, ranging from 11.0 % in Saarland to 34.8 % in Leipzig since 2000. The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred in the northern provinces like Hamburg (approx. € 67,300) succeeded by regions in the south (Upper Bavaria; approx. € 59,700). The capital of Berlin ranks also at the top (approx. € 42,300). As in previous years, the eastern provinces of the former German Democratic Republic (GDR) were far below the national level of € 41,500 (Saxony-An-

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty					
		At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Germany		EU-28		Non EU-28	
Very low	Severe	0.8	0.1	1.1	0.2	0.5	2.7
Not very low	Severe	1.1	0.7	0.3	0.8	1.8	1.9
Very low	Non severe	2.8	1.6	2.5	1.5	5.2	1.1
Not very low	Non severe	10.7		7.8		15.2	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		17.8		14.2		28.4	
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		82.2		85.8		71.6
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		82.2		85.8		71.6	
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020p), own illustration

Table 3: Nominal regional GDP (2019) and real growth rate (Δ 2000)

Region	Total		Per Capita	
	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices (Index, %)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market prices	Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average
Baden-Wuerttemberg	525,198	27.2	47,400	137
Stuttgart	224,062	28.2	54,000	157
Karlsruhe	128,375	24.8	45,700	133
Freiburg	89,751	24.9	39,600	115
Tübingen	83,009	30.9	44,600	129
Bavaria	634,609	31.0	48,400	141
Upper Bavaria	280,479	33.6	59,700	173
Lower Bavaria	49,463	30.4	39,800	116
Upper Palatinate	48,206	31.6	43,400	126
Upper Franconia	41,896	23.9	39,300	114
Middle Franconia	82,247	30.0	46,400	135
Lower Franconia	55,274	25.1	42,000	122
Swabia	77,043	29.9	40,700	118
Berlin	154,673	32.7	42,300	123
Brandenburg	74,838	22.6	29,700	86
Bremen	33,779	16.0	49,500	144
Hamburg	124,076	23.8	67,300	195
Hesse	295,533	16.5	47,100	137
Darmstadt	212,495	16.4	53,000	154
Giessen	37,151	17.0	35,500	103
Kassel	45,887	16.4	37,600	109
Mecklenburg-Hither Pomerania	46,711	18.2	29,000	84

Lower Saxony	307,510	25.8	38,500	112
Brunswick	80,135	34.1	50,200	146
Hanover	85,382	19.6	39,700	115
Lüneburg	49,594	22.0	28,900	84
Weser-Ems	92,399	26.9	36,500	106
North Rhine-Westphalia	715,854	17.8	39,900	116
Düsseldorf	221,024	15.3	42,500	123
Cologne	197,110	22.3	44,100	128
Münster	89,552	18.2	34,100	99
Detmold	80,219	18.8	39,000	113
Arnsberg	127,949	13.9	35,700	104
Rhineland-Palatinate	145,329	18.1	35,500	103
Koblenz	51,080	16.6	34,100	99
Trier	16,494	19.8	31,000	90
Rhine-Hesse-Palatinate	77,755	18.6	37,700	110
Saarland	36,383	11.0	36,800	107
Saxony	128,625	25.8	31,600	92
Dresden	51,383	26.4	32,200	93
Chemnitz	42,197	17.9	29,500	86
Leipzig	35,045	34.8	33,500	97
Saxony-Anhalt	63,725	12.7	28,900	84
Schleswig-Holstein	98,261	20.1	33,900	98
Thuringia	63,947	21.2	29,900	87
Germany	3,449,050	23.5	41,500	120

Source: Eurostat (2020r), own illustration; Eurostat (2020s), own illustration

halt: € 28,900; Mecklenburg-Hither Pomerania: € 29,000; Brandenburg: € 29,700; Thuringia: € 29,900; Saxony: € 31,600). Except for Hamburg (€ 67,300), Bremen (€ 49,500), Bavaria (€ 48,400) Baden-Wuerttemberg (€ 47,400), Hesse (€ 47,100) and Berlin (€ 42,300) all western provinces rank below German average.

Provinces with a high share of TCNs have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labour supply, i.e. a

greater number of working-age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called ‘cross-fertilization’, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries or regions. There are significant differences in levels of prosperity among German regions. The most prosperous region in Germany is Hamburg (195 %); it is over 111/109/108 pp richer than Mecklenburg-Hither Pomerania and Saxony-Anhalt/ Brandenburg/ Thuringia. Upper Bavaria ranks second (173 %) and Stuttgart third (157 %; see Table 3).

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors.

In total, approx. 33.7 million people were employed (employees are subject to social insurance contributions) in 2019 in Germany. This corresponds to an increase of +12.9 % compared to 2013. Almost three quarters (71.2 %) are employed in the service sector (24.0 million persons), where employment has increased by +15.1 % since 2013. Employment in manufacturing evolved below average (+7.8 %) and though primary sector increased by +8.2 %, it is of very low importance, i.e. only 0.7 % of total employment. Approx. 0.005 % belong to the category ‘Others’ (see Table 4).

Table 4: Employment by economic activity 2019

Economic Activity	Employed persons in 2019	Share	Δ 13-19	Germans	Foreigners
Primary Sector	225.67	0.7%	8.2%	82.9%	17.1%
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	225.67	0.7%	8.2%	82.9%	17.1%
Secondary Sector	9,474.13	28.1%	7.8%	87.9%	12.1%
Mining and quarrying	64.07	0.2%	-19.0%	93.7%	6.3%
Manufacturing	7,017.34	20.8%	6.3%	89.0%	10.9%
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	239.61	0.7%	1.3%	96.7%	3.3%
Water supply, sewerage, waste management	260.35	0.8%	12.6%	90.9%	9.1%
Construction	1,892.78	5.6%	15.5%	81.8%	18.1%
Tertiary Sector	24,038.63	71.2%	15.1%	87.3%	12.6%
Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles	4,581.30	13.6%	8.6%	89.4%	10.6%
Transportation and storage	1,868.85	5.5%	22.1%	79.3%	20.6%
Accommodation and food service activities	1,087.15	3.2%	23.2%	65.2%	34.6%
Information and communication	1,162.38	3.4%	27.9%	89.1%	10.8%
Financial and insurance activities	972.78	2.9%	-4.0%	95.6%	4.4%
Real estate activities	280.41	0.8%	21.0%	91.6%	8.4%
Professional, scientific and technical activities	2,323.63	6.9%	24.1%	91.0%	9.0%
Administrative and support service activities	2,276.60	6.7%	15.1%	70.7%	29.2%
Public administration and defense	1,872.72	5.6%	9.3%	97.1%	2.9%
Education	1,347.39	4.0%	15.9%	92.4%	7.6%
Human health and social work activities	5,044.47	15.0%	18.4%	91.8%	8.2%
Arts, entertainment and recreation	300.87	0.9%	21.3%	86.6%	13.4%
Other service activities	853.29	2.5%	6.2%	88.8%	11.2%
Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods- and services	49.06	0.1%	12.9%	73.3%	26.6%
Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies	17.73	0.1%	-17.9%	80.3%	19.5%
Others	1.69	0.0%	-67.4%	76.9%	22.8%
Others	1.69	0.0%	-67.4%	76.9%	22.8%
Total	33,740.12	100.0%	12.9%	87.4%	12.5%

Source: Federal Employment Agency (Bundesagentur für Arbeit Statistik) (2014, 2020a), own calculations and illustration

A more detailed examination of the different sectors of the economy reveals that there have also been significant shifts within the sectors: the only declines in employment were recorded in the sectors "Mining and quarrying" (-19.0 %), "Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies" (-17.9 %) and "Financial and insurance activities" (-4.0 %). "Information and communication" (+27.9 %), "Professional, scientific and technical activities" (+24.1 %), "Accommodation and food service activities" (+23.2 %), "Transportation and storage" (+22.1 %), "Arts, entertainment and recreation" (+21.3 %) as well as "Real estate activities" (+21.0 %), on the other hand, are among those economic sections with the largest absolute growth.

A further analysis by citizenship shows that almost 9 out of 10 employees of the secondary (87.9 %) and tertiary sector (87.3 %) are Germans. Conversely, non-Germans account for 12.1 % (secondary) and 12.6 % (tertiary); due to a lack of data no statements can be made in regard to TCNs.

Foreigners, i.e. all persons with non-German citizenship, are overrepresented (above 12.5 %) in "Accommodation and food service activities" (34.6 %), "Administrative and support service activities" (29.2 %), "Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods- and services" (26.6 %), "Transportation and storage" (20.6 %), "Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies" (19.5 %), "Construction" (18.1 %), "Agriculture, forestry and fishing" (17.1 %) and "Arts, entertainment and recreation" (13.4 %).

Figure 10: Employment by economic sector and citizenship 2019

Source: Federal Employment Agency (Bundesagentur für Arbeit Statistik) (2020b), own illustration

Mecklenburg-Hither Pomerania, Saxony-Anhalt (both 95,8 %), Saxony (95.2 %), Thuringia (95.1 %) and Brandenburg (94.6 %) have the highest share of Germans working in the secondary sector whereas Baden-Wuerttemberg (83.4 %), Hesse (84.3 %) and Berlin (85.4 %) have the lowest share. The number of non-EU-28 exceeds the number of EU-28 workers in Schleswig-Holstein (3.7 % vs. 3.2 %), North Rhine-Westphalia (6.3 % vs. 6.0 %), Bremen (5.5 % vs. 5.2 %), whereas the share is the same in Berlin (both 7.3 %) and Hamburg (both 5.6 %); in the remaining federal provinces EU-28 outweighs non-EU-28 employees (see Figure 10 (a)). An analysis of the tertiary sector shows that non-EU-28 employees are of more importance as the gap between them and EU-28 is only 0.2 pp (vs. 1.3 pp in the secondary sector). The highest gap is in Bavaria (2.3 pp), Saarland (2.2 pp), Baden-Wuerttemberg (1.9 pp) and Brandenburg (1.8 pp; see Figure 10 (b)).

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical growth and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research and development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28 citizens).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 3.12 % for Germany (2018) which is a slight increase of 0.07 percentage points to 2017. The total amount of research expenditures was € 100.67 billion, the largest share was financed by the business enterprise sector (66.0 %). 27.9 % were financed by the government sector. 5.8 % were financed by foreign countries (rest of the world) and 0.3 % were funded by the private non-profit sector (Eurostat 2020t).

Data on regional level (NUTS 2) and federal states level (NUTS 1) is published with a one-year time lag. Baden-Wuerttemberg was the province with the highest ratio in 2017 (5.7 %). Berlin followed in

Table 5: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
Baden-Wuerttemberg	27,895.3	5.70%
Stuttgart	15,918.8	7.69%
Karlsruhe	5,923.1	4.95%
Freiburg	2,313.3	2.75%
Tübingen	3,740.2	4.78%
Bavaria	18,684.3	3.12%
Upper Bavaria	10,695.7	4.03%
Lower Bavaria	631.6	1.34%
Upper Palatinate	1,134.9	2.47%
Upper Franconia	830.8	2.10%
Middle Franconia	2,745.7	3.60%
Lower Franconia	1,479.3	2.84%
Swabia	1,166.2	1.61%
Berlin	4,742.5	3.41%
Brandenburg	1,192.4	1.69%
Bremen	907.4	2.79%
Hamburg	2,495.8	2.16%
Hesse	8,174.5	2.93%
Darmstadt	6,561.1	3.27%
Giessen	901.1	2.61%
Kassel	712.3	1.63%
Mecklenburg-Hither Pomerania	784.0	1.81%
Lower Saxony	8,921.3	3.13%
Brunswick	5,876.0	8.52%
Hanover	1,812.2	2.25%
Lüneburg	425.9	0.90%
Weser-Ems	807.2	0.91%
North Rhine-Westphalia	14,319.2	2.11%
Düsseldorf	4,121.6	1.96%
Cologne	5,523.8	2.97%
Münster	1,043.6	1.22%
Detmold	1,495.8	1.98%
Arnsberg	2,134.4	1.76%
Rhineland-Palatinate	3,495.1	2.46%
Koblenz	343.6	0.69%
Trier	142.4	0.88%
Rhine-Hesse-Palatinate	3,009.0	3.97%
Saarland	618.6	1.76%
Saxony	3,393.7	2.81%
Dresden	1,990.8	4.13%
Chemnitz	750.5	1.86%
Leipzig	652.5	2.01%
Saxony-Anhalt	916.2	1.50%
Schleswig-Holstein	1,447.0	1.56%
Thuringia	1,358.8	2.21%
Germany	99,553.6	3.05%

Source: Eurostat (2020u), own illustration

second place with 3.41 % just ahead of Lower Saxony (3.13 %) and Bavaria (3.12 %). All other federal states were well behind and below the average German ratio of 3.05 %. Saxony-Anhalt ranked last (1.50 %) with Schleswig-Holstein (1.56 %), Brandenburg (1.69 %), Saarland (1.76 %) and

Mecklenburg-Hither Pomerania (1.81 %) only slightly better.

A deeper analysis (on NUTS 2 level) reveals that research and development (R&D) takes predominantly place in metropolitan areas of large cities as Braunschweig (8.52 %), Stuttgart (7.69 %), Karlsruhe (4.95 %), Tübingen (4.78 %) and Dresden (4.13 %). In absolute terms of R&D spending, Baden-Wuerttemberg also tops the list: € 27.90 billion of Germany's total research spending of € 99.55 billion in 2017 was spent in Baden-Wuerttemberg. It is followed by Bavaria (€ 18.68 billion) and North Rhine-Westphalia (€ 14.32 billion; see Table 5).

Available data for other countries has shown that employees in R&D have an above average share of foreigners compared to the total number of employed persons by economic activity.

Conclusion

This Statistical Briefings tried to give an overview on the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCNs) in Germany.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 10,398,022 persons (12.5 %) with non-German citizenship were living in Germany. Among non-German nationals, almost one half came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries. A total of 5,892,193 persons (or 7.1 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCNs), being individuals who are neither Germans, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens.

Within the last 20 years the population increase of Germany has mainly be dominated by immigration. From 2006 to 2019 all German regions profited heavily with regard to its working-age population. Without immigration, all German regions would have suffered from a decrease in its population aged between 20 and 65 years (with the exception of Bavaria with a stagnating development).

Despite the relevance of migration for labour supply, the employment rate of TCNs is much lower compared to Germans and EU-28 citizens, while we find a much higher unemployment rate. One relevant factor to be considered here is the lower

educational attainment level of migrants, with the consecutive effects of lower income levels and a higher risk of poverty. The pattern of education of the EU-28 and non-EU-28 citizens differs substantially from that of Germans: The foreign population of third countries is disproportionately represented in primary and secondary education, whereas they are underrepresented in tertiary education levels.

From a spatial point of view, the concentration of better-educated migrants is highest in German cities. Provinces with a higher ratio of TCNs are also characterized by higher economic growth, being more attractive for TCNs on the one hand and offering more labour supply on the other hand.

The below average regional GVA growth rate, especially in rural provinces like Saxony-Anhalt, Schleswig-Holstein or Thuringia is indirectly linked to immigration from abroad as well as to out-migration from rural areas to cities and metropolitan areas. These emigration flows tend to reinforce the erosion of the economic basis, because they have a negative impact on the potential workforce and the economic attractiveness of the region. Economic performance is stagnating, accompanied by declining population figures. This development does not take place in regions of former GDR solely but also in certain regions of Western Germany.

As a result, governments need to invest in education on the one hand and in research and development (R&D) on the other, to enable long-term prosperity and growth impulses. Currently, the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) are estimated at 3.12 % (2018) which is a slight increase of 0.07 percentage points compared to 2017. But there is again a striking regional variation from densely populated areas with high investments and innovative enterprises (e.g. Baden-Wuerttemberg and Berlin) to less densely populated provinces (e.g. Saxony-Anhalt and Schleswig-Holstein).

Summing up, immigrants in Germany play a pivotal role in reviving areas with a natural population downturn, and with the 'right' policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

Statistical Briefings Italy

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Italy on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

ITALY

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Italy

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCN) in Italy

On January 1, 2020, a total of 5,039,218 persons with non-Italian citizenship were living in Italy.¹ This corresponds to a share of 8.4 % of Italy's total population. Among non-Italian nationals, almost one third (1,504,521 persons; 2.5 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (8,931 persons; 0.01 %). A total of 3,525,766 persons (or 5.9 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Italians, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Italy lying above the average.

Considering the nationalities of TCN, Albanians (0.71 %) are above Moroccans (0.69 %), Chinese (incl. Hong Kong; 0.48 %), Ukrainians (0.38 %) and Philippines (0.26 %). In total, almost one half of TCN (42.9 %) living in Italy belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Italy.

Population Development & Population Structure

While the number of inhabitants in Italy has increased in the past, it is projected to decrease in the future. As of January 1, 2020, there were 59,641,488 persons registered in Italy. This corresponds to an increase of 2,717,964 citizens (+4.8 %) within the last 20 years since 2000 (before eastward enlargement of EU in 2004).

¹ Moreover, according to recent estimations, in 2020 approx. another 650.000 immigrants were living in Italy irregularly (ISPI, 2020).

The main cause of population growth is immigration to Italy (EU-28, EFTA & TCN), as the birth rate is only slightly higher than the death rate of the domestic population.

A long-term analysis of population development since the turn of the new millennium reveals clear regional differences. 38.2 % of Italian NUTS 3 regions have less inhabitants in 2020 than in 2001. The southern regions Medio Campidano (-10.5 %), Enna (-10.1 %), Vibo Valentia (-10.0 %), Potenza (-9.2 %) and Carbonia-Iglesias (-8.9 %) recorded the highest decline. The more prosperous regions in the north seem to be more attractive as the highest population growth rates can be found in Reggio nell'Emilia (+17.8 %), Rimini (+16.9 %), Lodi (+16.0 %), Parma (+15.9 %) and Bolzano (+15.5 %; see Figure 2).

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., one relevant aspect is labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

As Figure 3 (a)-(d) indicate, the increase in the working-age population within the regions is mainly caused by the increase in the non-Italian population. Without immigration, all Italian NUTS 2 regions would have suffered from a downturn in working-age population, with the exception of Bolzano (+1.3 % since 2007), one of the Italian case study regions of the project MATILDE. Both, domestic and foreign population groups, are (re-)locating to cities and metropolitan regions. This is at the expense of rural areas which are experiencing an overall decline in population. In particular, this is the case for Northern Italy, which

will shrink in the future especially in terms of working age population.

Analyzing working age population developments up to 2040 solely Bolzano (+2.73 %) will grow in the future. In all other regions the labor force potential will shrink. The highest decline in population will take place in the southern regions Carbonia-Iglesias (-31.91 %), Medio Campidano (-30.40 %), Oristano (-28.76 %), Nuoro (-27.92 %) and Ogliastra (-25.89 %; see Figure 4).

These past and future developments underline the high relevance of migration, especially for rural regions, concerning the development of the working age population. Without immigration, their population between 20 and 64 years would shrink even more dramatically, being a challenge from an economic point of view.

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be "dependent" on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being working age from 20 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in 2020 in Italy is 69,3 %. The dependency rate is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are a prosperous economy, i.e. more working people, and low child ratios. Most metropolitan regions in Italy are also characterized by relatively low rates (e.g., Roma 65.65 %). High dependency ratios are found in regions where the share of children and the elderly (65 years and older) is above average. These regions are mainly found in the North (e.g., Trieste 77.13 %). As a result of ageing societies, the total-age dependency ratios will rise in the future by 20.6 pp to 89.9 % in 2040, resulting in implications for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., pension system).

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2001 to 2020), NUTS 3

Δ 2001 to 2020
Growth -10.5% 17.8%

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Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

Figure 3: Working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2007 to 2019)

(a) Total -11,800 inh.

(c) Non EU-28 +1,081,100 inh.

(b) Italians -1,824,100 inh.

(d) EU-28 +731,300 inh.

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of the population with Italian citizenship is 18.2 %, which is only slightly above that of the total population (17.4 %). Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) Italy has a way below average tertiary education rate. Italy ranks 27th within the EU-28 next to Czech Republic (21.6 %) and Romania (16.0 %), which ranks last. Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities² than in towns and suburbs³, which in turn is higher than in rural areas⁴. In rural areas in Italy only 12.3 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 15.2 % in towns & suburbs and 24.1 % in cities. Secondary degrees are almost evenly spread over cities (40.6 %), towns and suburbs (43.7 %) as well as rural areas (44.0 %). But the regional differences in primary educational levels are striking. While less than 35.2 % of city residents have primary, i.e. less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (ISCED2011 levels 0 to 2) attainment level, 41.1 % and 43.8 % of residents in towns & suburbs and rural areas do.

In cities, where most of the non-EU-28 citizens live, more than 35.2 % have only primary education. This share is even higher in towns & suburbs (41.1 %) and rural areas (43.8 %). On contrary, only 13.2 % of non-EU-28 citizens have a degree from university but this value is still much higher than in suburban (8.5 %) and rural (8.4 %) regions. Differences of educational attainment level between Italian and EU-28 residents range within a band from 0.3 pp to 8.5 pp with the highest variations between secondary and tertiary levels of education (see Table 1). In total, EU-28 (11.3 %) and non-EU-28 (10.5 %) citizens have a lower tertiary education rate than the domestic population (18.2 %).

The unemployment rate in Italy is 9.9 %, being above the EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, Calabria has the highest unemployment rate at 20.9 % (female: 22.6 %; male: 20.0 %), followed by Sicilia (19.9 %; female: 22.5 %; male: 18.3 %) and Campania (19.9 %; female: 22.4 %; male: 18.3 %). Provincia Autonoma di Bolzano/Bozen (2.8 %; 3.1 % female; 2.5 % male) and Trento (4.9 %; 6.0 % female; 4.0 % male) are the provinces with the lowest level of unemployment (see Figure 5).

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for Italy. Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (13.7 %). Conversely, people with tertiary education have the lowest unemployment rate (5.9 %), those with secondary a value of 9.2 %. The same trend can be observed at the European level (EU-28; see Figure 6), even though with lower unemployment rates.

Table 1: Working-age Population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Italian	33.0%	41.5%	25.5%
	EU-28	33.4%	49.6%	17.0%
	Non EU-28	57.3%	29.5%	13.2%
	Total	35.2%	40.6%	24.1%
Towns & suburbs	Italian	39.3%	44.8%	15.9%
	EU-28	39.6%	51.1%	9.3%
	Non EU-28	65.6%	25.9%	8.5%
	Total	41.1%	43.7%	15.2%
Rural	Italian	42.6%	44.8%	12.6%
	EU-28	43.1%	48.4%	8.5%
	Non EU-28	67.1%	24.5%	8.4%
	Total	43.8%	44.0%	12.3%

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

² A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020e).

³ Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population

density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020f; Eurostat 2020g).

⁴ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat, 2020h; Eurostat, 2020i).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher the employment rate, i.e. 78.9 % for tertiary, 66.3 % for secondary and 52.1 % for primary level. From an immigrational point of view, this observation holds for other citizenships as well, as the risk of unemployment decreases by the level of educational attainment. But Italians have the highest employment rate for tertiary educational attainment level (79.7 %) while EU-28/non-EU-28 rank first for secondary/primary educational attainment level (67.4 %/62.9 %). Non-EU-28 citizens have the lowest employment rate on secondary and tertiary level (both 64.7 %; see Figure 7).

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings. Considering migrants the recognition of educational degrees might be an additional problem.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

Figure 7: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020l), own illustration

education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). Italy ranks with a value of 13.5 % above the European average. The share of EU-28 citizens residing in Italy is almost three times as high (30.8 %) and that of non-EU-28 is more than three times as high (38.5 %) than that of the domestic population (11.3 %). In total, almost two thirds (64.4 %) of all early leavers are jobless. An analysis by citizenship

shows low variation among foreigners (EU-28: 56.8 %; Non-EU-28: 55.6 %) but Italians record the highest value (67.3 %, Eurostat 2020m).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁵ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income. Working persons in Italy at primary level earn less (mean: € 15,682; median: € 14,377) than secondary (€ 20,013 or € 18,227) and tertiary levels (€ 26,854 or € 23,491; see Figure 8). As working Italians have a higher educational attainment level than EU-28 and non-EU-28 (see Figure 7) this could be one reason (amongst others) that their mean (€ 20,472 vs. € 16,232 and € 13,414) and median (€ 18,423 vs. € 13,398 and € 12,387) equivalized net income is higher.

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

The indicator ‘people at risk of poverty or social exclusion’ corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity.

⁵ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

As non-EU 28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than domestic residents and EU-28, more than 2 out of 5 persons (42.6 %) belong to this group, though the value of EU-28 is quite high as well (29.9 %). Italians face the lowest risk of social exclusion and poverty (24.1 %; see Table 2).

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers’ social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 %. Italy (40.2 %) lies below European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 12.7 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 47.1 % of GDP in Italy, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. Italian GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 1,790.9 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 29,680 (Eurostat 2020q).

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty					
		At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Italians		EU-28		Non EU-28	
Very low	Severe	1.8	0.3	2.1	0.1	1.6	0.6
Not very low	Severe	2.0	3.0	4.5	3.5	5.9	6.8
Very low	Non severe	2.7	2.6	2.9	1.4	2.4	0.5
Not very low	Non severe	11.7		15.4		24.8	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		24.1		29.9		42.6	
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		76.0		70.1		57.3
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		76.0		70.1		57.3	
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020p), own illustration

Within 20 years Italy's gross value added (GVA) increased by only +5.2 % (real growth rate). In terms of regional GVA the majority of NUTS 2 regions recorded positive real growth rates, ranging from +1.0 % in Friuli-Venezia Giulia to +24.1 % Bolzano/Bozen since 2000; but with exception of the Northeast there are regions all over Italy facing a decline in economic growth. Especially the South (-5.6 %) faced severe difficulties as Basilicata (+2.2 %) was the only among 5 regions growing within the past 20 years with Molise (-15.7 %) and Calabria (-10.6 %) having the greatest decline (see Table 3).

The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred also in Bolzano/Bozen (approx. € 48,000) succeeded by Lombardia (approx. € 39,500) and another northeastern region, Trento (approx. € 38,700). As in previous years, the southern provinces were far below the national level of € 29,700 (e.g. Calabria: € 17,400; Sicilia: € 17,900; Campania: € 18,900) but also regions in the center (Umbria: € 26,400; Marche: € 27,800) performed below average. Except for Umbria and Marche all central, northwestern and northeastern regions rank above average (see Table 3).

Provinces with a high share of TCN have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Table 3: Nominal regional GDP (2019) and real growth rate (Δ 2002 to 2019)

Region	Total		Per Capita	
	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices (Index, 2015=100; Δ 2002 to 2019)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market prices	Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average
Nord-Ovest	591,170	9.1	36,700	118
Piemonte	137,782	2.3	31,700	102
Valle d'Aosta	4,868	-3.1	38,700	125
Liguria	49,741	-6.8	32,200	104
Lombardia	398,779	13.6	39,500	127
Nord-Est	413,866	10.1	35,500	114
Bolzano	25,516	24.1	48,000	155
Trento	20,967	10.8	38,700	125
Veneto	164,860	8.0	33,600	108
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	38,772	1.0	32,000	103
Emilia-Romagna	163,751	12.1	36,700	118
Centro	385,226	5.8	32,100	103
Toscana	118,727	5.9	31,900	103
Umbria	23,267	-6.4	26,400	85
Marche	42,392	2.5	27,800	90
Lazio	200,840	7.7	34,200	110
Sud	273,436	-5.6	19,600	63
Abruzzo	33,131	-1.6	25,300	82
Molise	6,490	-15.7	21,300	69
Campania	109,631	-6.5	18,900	61
Puglia	77,475	-4.3	19,300	62
Basilicata	13,090	2.2	23,400	75
Calabria	33,619	-10.6	17,400	56
Isole	124,621	-6.7	18,800	61
Sicilia	89,365	-8.8	17,900	58
Sardegna	35,256	-1.2	21,600	69
Italy	1,789,747	5.2	29,700	96

Source: Eurostat (2020r), own illustration; Eurostat (2020s), own illustration

Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries or regions. There are significant differences in levels of prosperity among Italian regions. The most prosperous region in Italy is also Bolzano/Bozen (155 %); it is over 99/97/94 pp richer than Calabria/Sicilia/Campania which are the poorest regions from an economic point of view. Lombardia ranks second (127 %) and Trento third (125 %; see Table 3).

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In total, approx. 23.46 million people were employed in 2019 in Italy. This corresponds to an increase of +1.2 % compared to 2008.

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors. Almost three quarters (70.2 %) are employed in the service sector, where employment has increased by +3.7 % since 2008. Employment in manufacturing shrunk by -3.9 % and has a share of 25.9 %. Though primary sector increased by +0.2 % it is of low importance, i.e. only 3.9 % of total employment (see Figure 11 (a)-(c) and Figure 11).

Further analysis by territories and citizenship shows that more than 1 of 10 workers (10.7 %) are foreigners. The absolute number is the highest in the northern part (1,465,667 inh.; 12.0 %) whereas the share is highest in the center (656,322 inh.; 13.2 %). Except for the northeastern part where the number of Italians almost stagnates (0.1 %) all remaining territories show a negative tendency especially in the southern part (Mezzogiorno: -7.0 %). In contrast, the number of foreigners evolves at a very high level ranging from 28.9 % (Nord-est) to 98.5 % (Mezzogiorno) within more than 10 years since 2008 (see Figure 11). From a sectoral point of view foreigners preferably work in the primary sector (18.3 %). Only 11.6 % work in the secondary sector and 10.0 % in the tertiary sector where their absolute number is highest (1,637,551 inh.). Especially in the central part of Italy almost 3 out of 10 workers (29.2 %) in the primary sector are foreigners. Except for the comparably low share of foreigners in the tertiary sec-

tor in Mezzogiorno (5.7 %) the dispersion across Italy is at a very low level (0.8 pp; see Figure 10). Due to a lack of data no reliable statements can be made in regard to TCNs.

Figure 10: Employment by economic sector and citizenship 2019

Source: Istat (2021), own calculations and illustration

Figure 11: Employment by nationalities and territories, 2008 and 2019

Source: Istat (2021), own calculations and illustration

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 1.42 % for Italy (2018) which is a slight increase of 0.05 percentage points to 2017.

The total amount of research expenditures was € 25.23 billion, the largest share (54.9 %) being financed by the business enterprise sector. 33.1 % were financed by the government sector. 10.6 % by foreign countries (rest of the world), 1.4 % and 0.7 % by private non-profit and higher education sector (Eurostat 2020t).

Regional data is published on NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 level. Piemonte has the highest ratio in 2018 (2.18 %). Emilia-Romagna (2.03 %) and Lazio (1.75 %) take second and third place, ahead of Friuli-Venezia Giulia (1.67 %), Trento (1.57 %) and Toscana (1.55 %). All other provinces are well behind and below the all-Italian ratio of 1.42 %. Sardegna ranks last (0.80 %) with Sicilia (0.82 %), Bol-

zano/Bozen (0.84 %), Abruzzo (0.91 %) and Umbria (1.03 %) only slightly better (see Table 4). For the MATILDE case study region Bolzano/Bozen the low level in R&D expenditures is particularly surprising, as Bolzano/Bozen has the highest GDP per capita in Italy.

In accordance to the research & development (R&D) funding structure almost one half (44.5 % or 62,478 full-time equivalent (FTE)) of the researchers work in the business enterprise sector. 15.8 % (or 22,118 FTE) work in the government sector and 3.1 % (or 4,421 FTE) in the private non-profit sector. The higher education sector (46.9 % or 62,542 FTE) is by far the greatest employer of researchers. This makes a total of 133,213 FTE. Further analysis on educational attainment level reveals that most researchers (67.0 %) have tertiary education but not doctoral or equivalent level; 8.8 % belong to the latter whereas 24.3 % have less than primary, primary, secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (see Figure 12).

As the group of migrants (EU-28 or non-EU-28) living in Italy has a lower share of tertiary education it is therefore likely that they are underrepresented in Italian R&D personnel.

Table 4: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Region	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
Nord-Ovest	8,892.1	1.53%
Piemonte	2,987.5	2.18%
Valle d'Aosta	23.7	0.48%
Liguria	672.7	1.35%
Lombardia	5,208.3	1.34%
Nord-Est	6,706.4	1.64%
Bolzano/Bozen	207.8	0.84%
Trento	321.5	1.57%
Veneto	2,263.4	1.39%
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	634.7	1.67%
Emilia-Romagna	3,279.0	2.03%
Centro	5,971.9	1.57%
Toscana	1,828.0	1.55%
Umbria	231.1	1.03%
Marche	458.0	1.06%
Lazio	3,454.7	1.75%
Sud	2,646.3	0.98%
Abruzzo	307.1	0.91%
Molise	81.6	1.26%
Campania	1,404.0	1.30%
Puglia	594.6	0.78%
Basilicata	79.2	0.63%
Calabria	179.8	0.54%
Isole	1,015.5	0.82%
Sicilia	735.2	0.82%
Sardegna	280.4	0.80%
Italy	25,232.2	1.42%

Source: Eurostat (2020u), own illustration

Figure 12: R&D researchers (full-time equivalent (FTE)) by sectors of performance and educational attainment level 2017 (ISCED2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020v), own illustration

Summary

This Statistical Briefings examines the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Italy.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 5,039,218 persons with non-Italian citizenship were officially living in Italy. This corresponds to a share of 8.4 % of Italy's total population. Moreover, estimations show 650.000 irregular migrants. Among non-Italian nationals, almost one third (2.5 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries. A total of 3,525,766 persons (or 5.9 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Italians, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Italy lying above the average.

Within the last 20 years the population increase of Italy has been dominated by immigration. From 2006 to 2019 all Italian regions profited heavily with regard to its working-age population. Without immigration, all Italian regions would have suffered from a decrease in its population aged between 20 and 65 years.

Despite the relevance of migration for labor supply, the employment rate of TCN is much lower compared to Italians and EU-28 citizens. One relevant factor to be considered here is the lower educational attainment level of migrants, with the consecutive effects of lower income levels and a higher risk of poverty.

The pattern of education of the EU-28 and non-EU-28 countries differs substantially from that of

Italy: the foreign population of third countries is disproportionately represented in primary education, whereas they are underrepresented in secondary and tertiary education levels.

From a spatial point of view, the concentration of better-educated migrants is highest in Italian cities. Provinces with a higher ratio of TCN are also characterized by higher economic growth, being more attractive for TNC on the one hand and offering more labor supply on the other hand.

The below average regional GVA growth rate, especially in rural regions is indirectly linked to immigration from abroad but preferably to internal migration from rural to cities and metropolitan areas. These emigration flows tend to reinforce the erosion of the economic basis, because they have a negative impact on the potential workforce and the economic attractiveness of the region. Economic performance is stagnating, accompanied by declining population figures.

Governments need to invest in education on the one hand and in research and development (R&D) on the other, to enable long-term prosperity and growth. Currently the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) are estimated at 1.42 % (2018) which is a slight increase of 0.05 pp to 2017. But there is again a striking regional variation in R&D expenditures.

Summing up, immigrants in Italy play a pivotal role in reviving rural areas, and with the appropriate policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

Statistical Briefings Norway

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Norway on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

NORWAY

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Norway

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Norway

As of January 1, 2020, a total of 940,580 persons with non-Norwegian citizenship were living in Norway. This corresponds to a share of 11.3 % of Norway's total population. Among non-Norwegian nationals, 61.7 % (580,042 persons; 6.9 % of the total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (excl. Norway; 15,615 persons; 0.2 %). A total of 426,535 persons (or 4.1 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Norwegian, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore the EFTA member state Norway lies below the EU average.

Considering the nationalities of TCN, Syrians (0.60 %) are above Eritreans (0.35 %), Philippians (0.24 %), Somalians (0.22 %) and Thai (0.22 %). In

total, more than 40 % (41.9 %) of TCN living in Norway belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Norway.

Population Development & Population Structure

The number of inhabitants in Norway increased in the past and this development is projected to continue according to current population forecasts. As of January 1, 2020, there were 5,367,580 persons registered in Norway. This corresponds to an increase of 889,083 citizens (+ 19.9 %) within the last 20 years since 2000 (before eastward enlargement of EU in 2004).

A long-term analysis of population development since 2015 reveals clear regional differences though all regions recorded a growth. Vestland (+2.4 %), Nordland (+2.4 %) and Troms og Finnmark (+3.3 %) grew at a comparably low level.

Compared to the under-average population growth recorded in the north, the situation is different in the south: Oslo (+ 30.9%), Viken (+ 28.1 %) as well as Rogaland (+ 22.1 %) have very high growth rates (see Figure 2).

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., another economically relevant aspect is the

labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2005 to 2019), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

As Figure 3 (a)-(d) indicate, the increase in the working-age population (+397,800 inh.) is dominated by immigration (EU-28: +203,800 inh.; non-EU-28: +85,800 inh.). Domestic population increased (+106,100 inh.) as well but on a smaller scale than immigrants. This makes Norway special, as most industrialized countries have already been

facing a shrinking domestic working-age population in the past. From a regional perspective, Oslo and Viken (+25.5%), Agder and Rogaland (+16.7%), Trøndelag (+15.0%) as well as Vestland (12.6%) are fast-growing areas, with lower growth rates in the remaining regions.

Figure 3: Working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2006 to 2019)

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

According to current forecasts, the increase of labor force potential does not stop in the future, though the growth rates are lower compared to the past. Working-age population will increase by +8.4 % until 2040. There are only five regions

which are projected to shrink at a comparably low rate in the future, i.e. Troms og Finnmark (-3.69 %), Innlandet (-2.69 %), Vestfold og Telemark (-1.78 %), Trøndelag (-1.63 %) and Vestland (-1.08 %; see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Projections of Working-age Population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040) NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be “dependent” on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly

(65 years old and upwards) – to the number of those individuals who are, being working age from 20 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in 2020 in Norway is 69.1 %. The dependency rate is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are a more prosperous economy, i.e. more people in working-age, and low child ratios. Most metropolitan regions in Norway (e.g., Oslo) are also characterized by relatively low rates. High dependency ratios are found in Vestland (80.08 %), Møre og Romsdal (76.50 %) and Innlandet (76.68 %). As a result of ageing societies, the total-age dependency ratios will rise in the future by 8.1 pp to 77.2 % in 2040 resulting in implications/challenges for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., expenditures for pensions.)

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of Norway's domestic population is 38.2 %, which is slightly above that of the total population (37.7 %). Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) Norway has a way above-average tertiary education rate. If Norway was EU-28 member it would approx. rank 6th ex aequo with Lithuania (37.9 %), ahead of Estonia (36.5 %), Belgium (36.0 %) and Spain (35.1 %). Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities¹ than in towns and suburbs², which in turn is higher than in rural areas. In rural areas³ in Norway, only 30.0 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 37.0 % in towns & suburbs and 48.9 % in cities. In contrast, secondary degrees are more common in less densely populated areas. While less than 31.8 % of city residents have secondary, i.e. upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 3 to 4) attainment level, 38.8 % and 43.5 % of residents in towns & suburbs and

rural areas do. Primary educational attainment level has low relevance as approx. only 1 out of 5 residents in Norway belongs to this group.

Concerning the educational attainment level of TCN, large differences can be recorded. In cities, where most of the Non-EU-28 citizens live, approx. 23.7 % have only primary education. This share is even higher in towns & suburbs (34.5 %) and rural areas (31.4 %). The shares of non-EU-28 citizens (40.3 %), EU-28 citizens (45.0 %) and Norwegians (49.6 %) with tertiary education living in cities are all on a very high level. On the contrary, only 25.7 % or 22.2 % of non-EU-28 citizens living in towns and suburbs or rural areas have a university degree. Differences of educational attainment level between Norwegians and EU-28 residents range within a broad band from 2.1 pp to 12.7 pp. (see Table 1). In total, EU-28 (37.6 %) and non-EU-28 (29.3 %) citizens have a lower tertiary education rate than domestic population (38.2 %).

Table 1: Working-age population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanization	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Norwegians	19.8%	30.4%	49.8%
	EU-28	11.9%	43.1%	45.0%
	Non EU-28	23.7%	35.9%	40.3%
	Total	19.3%	31.8%	48.9%
Towns & suburbs	Norwegians	24.1%	38.0%	37.9%
	EU-28	17.9%	46.3%	35.8%
	Non EU-28	34.5%	39.9%	25.7%
	Total	24.2%	38.8%	37.0%
Rural	Norwegians	26.9%	42.9%	30.2%
	EU-28	18.7%	48.8%	32.5%
	Non EU-28	31.4%	46.4%	22.2%
	Total	26.5%	43.5%	30.0%

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

¹ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020e).

² Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population

density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020f; Eurostat 2020g).

³ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat 2020h; Eurostat 2020i).

The unemployment rate in Norway is 3.3 %, being far below EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, Oslo and Viken has the highest unemployment rate at 3.6 % (female: 3.4 %; male: 3.8 %), followed by Agder and Rogaland (3.5 %; female: 3.4 %; male: 3.6 %). Troms of Finnmark and Nordland (2.6 %) has the lowest unemployment rates (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for Norway: Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (6.3 %). Conversely, people with tertiary education have the lowest unemployment rate (2.2 %), those with secondary a value of 3.4 %. Similar results are observed at the European level (EU-28; see Figure 6).

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher is the employment rate, i.e. 88.6 % for tertiary, 78.1 % for secondary and 60.8 % for primary level. From an immigrational point of view, this observation holds for other citizenships as well. But EU-28 citizens have the highest employment rate for all educational attainment levels (89.9 %; 85.2 %; 63.1 %) while Norwegians rank

second on each level (89,1 %; 78.8 %; 61.1 %) and non-EU-28 citizens have the lowest employment rates on each level (73.5 %; 54.0 %; 48.6 %; see Figure 7).

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

Figure 7: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020l), own illustration

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons

aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). EFTA member state Norway ranges with a value of 9.9 % below the EU average. In total, approx. one third (35.4 %) of early school leavers are jobless but due to missing data, no definitive statements can be made in regard to immigrational status (Eurostat 2020m).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁴ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income. Working persons in Norway at primary level earn less (mean: € 36,422; median: € 33,676) than secondary (mean: € 42,843; median: € 41,226) and tertiary levels (mean: € 50,139; median: € 45,501; see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

Distinguished by citizenship, Norwegians have a higher income compared to EU-28 and non-EU-28

⁴ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

citizens (mean: € 45,075 vs. € 38,604 and € 30,919; median: € 42,069 vs. € 36,742 and € 28,110; see Figure 9).

A further analysis and breakdown of wage differentials between domestic and foreign workers done by Lehmer and Ludsteck (2013) reveals that factors like seniority, promotions to better-paid occupations as well as job stability also have to be taken into account. These factors cause an improvement in an individual's firm-specific human capital (training on the job) as the median age of foreign workers and therefore the length of time within the company is lower than for domestic ones. However, these assumptions cannot be verified in the context of this analysis due to a lack of available data.

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

The indicator 'people at risk of poverty or social exclusion' corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. As non-EU-28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than domestic and EU-28 citizens almost 3 out of 5 persons (58.2 %) belong to this group, though the value of EU-28 is quite high as well

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty					
		At risk		Not at risk		At risk	
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Norway		EU-28		Non EU-28	
Very low	Severe	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.0	6.4	0.6
Not very low	Severe	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.5	1.3	2.2
Very low	Non severe	2.3	3.0	1.9	1.1	10.5	2.8
Not very low	Non severe	8.1		12.7		18.5	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		15.1		16.9		42.3	
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		84.9		83.2		57.7
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		84.9		83.2		57.7	
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020p), own illustration

(32.6 %). Norwegians face the lowest risk of social exclusion and poverty (13.8 %; see Table 2).

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers' social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 %. The EFTA country Norway (48.6 %) almost equals European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 10.5 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 40.9 % of GDP in Norway, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. Norwegian GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 362.2 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 67,730 (Eurostat 2020q).

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors.

In total, approx. 2.5 million people were employed in 2019 in Norway. This corresponds to an increase of +7.7 % compared to 2008. More than three quarters (77.6 %) are employed in the service sector, where employment has increased by +9.8 % since 2008. Employment in manufacturing evolved way below average (+3.1 %) and primary sector decreased by +25.4 % but it is of low importance, i.e. only 1.8 % of total employment. Approx. 0.7 %

belong to the category 'Others' where no further information is available (see Table 3).

A more detailed examination of the different sectors of the economy reveals that there have also been significant shifts within the sectors: the only declines in employment were recorded in the sections "Manufacture" (-17.7 %), "Transportation and storage" (-8.6 %) and "Financial and insurance activities" (-8.1 %). "Food and beverage service activities" (+38.6 %), "Mining and quarrying" (+35.7 %) as well as "Power and water supply, sewerage/remediation activities" (+24.6 %), on the other hand, are among those economic sections with the largest growth rates.

Due to non-available data no exact analyses are possible in regard to TCN. The analysis by region of birth shows that 19.5 % belong to the group of immigrants (foreign-born with two foreign-born parents). Norwegian-born to immigrant parents are of minor relevance as they account for only 0.9 %.

Immigrants are overrepresented (above 19.5 %) in "Cleaning activities" (71.2 %), "Temporary employment agency activities" (41.7 %; both subsections of "Administrative and support service activities" (37.1 %)), "Food and beverage service activities" (50.6 %), "Accommodation" (46.9 %), "Transportation and storage" (22.1 %) and "Construction" (21.6 %). From a sectoral point of view, immigrants have almost the same relevance in the secondary (18.9 %) and tertiary sector (17.3 %; difference of only 1.6 pp). But they are underrepresented in the primary sector (10.6 %; see Table 3).

Table 3: Employment by economic activity 2019

Economic Activity	Employed persons in 2019	Share	Δ 08-19	Norwegian	Born to immigrant parents	Immigrant
Primary Sector	46,495	1.8%	-25.4%	89.3%	0.1%	10.6%
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	46,495	1.8%	-25.4%	89.3%	0.1%	10.6%
Secondary Sector	500,496	19.9%	3.1%	80.6%	0.5%	18.9%
Mining and quarrying	57,551	2.3%	35.7%	87.9%	0.3%	11.7%
Manufacture	199,588	7.9%	-17.7%	80.1%	0.4%	19.4%
Power and water supply, sewerage/remediation activities	30,900	1.2%	24.6%	89.2%	0.4%	10.3%
Construction	212,457	8.4%	21.0%	77.8%	0.5%	21.6%
Tertiary Sector	1,950,013	77.6%	9.8%	81.4%	1.4%	17.3%
Domestic trade	306,302	12.2%	-3.2%	82.8%	1.9%	15.3%
Transportation and storage	126,876	5.0%	-8.6%	76.4%	1.5%	22.1%
Other passenger land transport	28,119	1.1%	3.1%	56.1%	2.3%	41.7%
Accommodation	24,734	1.0%	7.0%	52.3%	0.9%	46.9%
Food and beverage service activities	57,236	2.3%	38.6%	46.8%	2.6%	50.6%
Information and communication	96,192	3.8%	13.8%	84.9%	1.4%	13.6%
Financial and insurance activities	45,911	1.8%	-8.1%	91.0%	1.7%	7.3%
Real estate, professional, scientific and technical activities	161,816	6.4%	15.7%	84.7%	1.1%	14.2%
Administrative and support service activities	127,550	5.1%	5.6%	61.0%	1.9%	37.1%
Temporary employment agency activities	38,930	1.5%	-7.5%	55.9%	2.4%	41.7%
Cleaning activities	24,783	1.0%	28.3%	28.1%	0.6%	71.2%
Public administration and defence: compulsory social security	159,222	6.3%	17.4%	92.7%	1.0%	6.4%
Education	216,294	8.6%	15.0%	87.1%	0.9%	12.0%
Human health and social work activities	532,807	21.2%	16.2%	83.5%	1.2%	15.4%
Other service activities	95,073	3.8%	19.8%	81.6%	1.1%	17.3%
Others	17,501	0.7%	72.6%	79.6%	0.9%	19.5%
Total	2,514,505	100.0%	7.7%	81.4%	1.1%	17.5%

Source: Statistics Norway (2021)

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 2.05 % for Norway (2018) which is a slight decrease of 0.05 pp to 2017. The total amount of research expenditures was € 7.58 billion, the largest share (47.8 %) was financed by the government sector and 42.0 % by the business enterprise sector. 8.3 % were contributed by foreign countries (rest of the world). 1.5 % and 0.5 % were

funded by the private non-profit and the higher education sector (Eurostat 2020r).

Data on regional level (NUTS 2) is published with a one year time lag. Trøndelag is the province with the highest ratio in 2017 (4.79 %) succeeded by Oslo og Akershus (3.18 %) and Vestlandet (2.27 %). Except for Nord-Norge (2.00 %) all other provinces were well behind and below the all-Norwegian ratio of 2.10 %. Innlandet (0.92 %), Agder og Rogaland (1.50 %) and Sør-Østlandet (1.65 %) are the regions with the lowest ratios (see Table 4).

In accordance to the research & development (R&D) funding structure one half (48.9 %) of the researchers work in the business enterprise sector. Approx. one third (38.5 %) works in the higher education sector and the remaining 12.6 % in the governmental sector. This makes a total of 35,897 FTE (Eurostat 2020t).

Available data for other countries has shown that employees in R&D have an above average share of foreigners compared to the total number of employed persons by economic activity.

Table 4: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
Oslo og Akershus	3,098.3	3.18%
Innlandet	155.3	0.92%
Sør-Østlandet	718.4	1.65%
Agder og Rogaland	622.9	1.50%
Vestlandet	1,136.9	2.27%
Trøndelag	1,178.0	4.79%
Nord-Norge	507.1	2.00%
Norway	7,416.8	2.10%

Source: Eurostat (2020s), own illustration

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Available data for other countries has shown that employees in R&D have an above average share of foreigners compared to the total number of employed persons by economic activity.

Summary

This Statistical Briefings examines the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Norway.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 940,580 persons with non-Norwegian citizenship were living in Norway. This corresponded to a share of 11.3 % of Norway's total population. Among non-Norwegian nationals, 61.7 % (6.9 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (excl. Norway; 0.2 %). A total of 426,535 persons (or 4.1 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Norwegian, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK)

and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Norway records a comparably high rate of TCN.

Within the past two decades the increase in population of working-age in Norway has strongly be dominated by immigration, although also a natural population increase can be recorded for some regions.

Despite the relevance of migration for labor supply, the employment rate of TCN is much lower compared to Norwegian nationals and EU-28 citizens. One relevant factor to be considered here is the lower educational attainment level of migrants, with the consecutive effects of lower income levels and a higher risk of poverty.

The pattern of education of TCN differs substantially from that of Norwegian nationals: The foreign population of third country nationals are disproportionately represented in primary and secondary education, whereas they are underrepresented in tertiary education levels.

From a spatial point of view, the concentration of better-educated migrants is highest in Norwegian cities. Regions with a higher ratio of TCN are also characterized by higher economic growth, being more attractive for TCNs but also offering more labor supply.

Governments need to invest in education on the one hand and in research and development (R&D) on the other, to enable long-term prosperity and growth. Currently the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) are estimated at 2.05 % (2018) which is a slight decrease of 0.05 percentage points to 2017. But there is again a striking regional variation, from densely populated areas with a high number of innovative enterprises (e.g. Oslo) to less densely populated provinces (e.g. Innlandet)

Summing up, immigrants in Norway play a pivotal role in reviving rural areas, and with the appropriate policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Spain on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

SPAIN

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Spain

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Spain

On January 1, 2020, a total of 4,960,467 persons with non-Spanish citizenship were living in Spain. This corresponded to a share of 10.5 % of Spain's total population.

Among non-Spanish nationals, 39.5 % (1,958,662 persons; 4.1 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (30,775 persons; 0.06 %). A total of 2,971,030 persons (or 6.3 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Spanish, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Spain lying above the average.

Considering the nationalities of TCN, Moroccans (1.61 %) are above Colombians (0.55 %), Chinese (incl. Hong Kong; 0.42 %), Venezuelans (0.40 %) and Ecuadorians (0.28 %). In total, more than half of TCN (51.8 %) living in Spain belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Spain.

Population Development & Population Structure

The number of inhabitants in Spain increased in the past and this development is projected to continue in the future. As of January 1, 2020, there were 47,332,614 persons registered in Spain. This corresponds to an increase of 6,862,432 citizens (+17.0 %) within the last 20 years since 2000 (before eastward enlargement of EU in 2004).

A long-term analysis of population development since the turn of the new millennium reveals clear regional differences. Fuerteventura (+108.15 %), Eivissa, Formentera (+81.33 %), Lanzarote (+58.04 %), Guadalajara (+49.29 %) and Mallorca (+38.63 %) recorded the highest increase of population. Though the majority of regions (79.9 %) recorded population growth there are also some regions suffering from a decline. Zamora (-13.45 %), Ourense (-9.25 %), Lugo (-8.15 %), Palencia (-7.96 %) and León are most affected (see Figure 2).

On 1 January 2016, 60 % of Spanish municipalities had fewer than 1,001 inhabitants, occupied 40 %

of the country's surface and concentrated barely 3.1 % of the population. This reflects the "two Spains": the urbanized and populated (which includes the Mediterranean coast and islands), versus the empty interior. The rural exodus began at the end of the nineteenth century in zones close to urban and industrial centers of Catalonia and the Basque Country but, during the first half of the twentieth century, high fertility and declining mortality rates assured continuity and even demographic growth in rural spaces in general (Recaño 2017).

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2002 to 2020), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., another economically relevant aspect is the labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

As Figure 3 (a)-(d) indicate, the increase in the working-age population (+416,500) within the regions is mainly caused by the EU-28 (except Spanish; +367,200 inh.) and non-EU 28 (+174,300 inh.)

while the working-age population of Spanish people shrank since 2006 (-126,300 inh.). From a regional perspective, the areas with the highest population growths are Melilla (+25.8 %), Balearic Islands (19.1 %) and Canary Islands (+13.9 %). Principality of Asturias (-10.9 %), Castile-Leon (-8.2 %) and Basque Community (-7.4 %) recorded the highest declines.

Whereas there was an increase of labor force potential recorded in the past 20 years, this changes in the future as working-age population decreases by 6.2 % until 2040. There are only 5 regions (8.5 %) which are projected to grow in the future (see Figure 3 (a) and Figure 4).

Figure 3: Working-age Population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2006 to 2019) NUTS 2

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

Figure 4: Projections of Working-age Population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040) NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be “dependent” on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being working age from 20 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in 2020 in Spain is 64.6 %. The dependency rate is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are a more prosperous economy, i.e. more people in working-age, and low

child ratios. Most metropolitan regions in Spain are also characterized by relatively low rates. High dependency ratios are found in Ourense (80.89 %), Zamora (78.35 %) and Lugo (74.76 %). These provinces, together with others, constitute the rural spaces at risk of irreversible depopulation (Recaño, 2017). As a result of ageing societies, the total-age dependency ratios will rise in the future by 18.5 pp to 83.0 % in 2040 resulting in implications/challenges for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., expenditures for pensions).

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of Spain's domestic population is 36.5 %, which is only slightly above that of the total population (35.1 %). Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) Spain ranks 10th. Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities¹ than in towns and suburbs², which in turn is higher than in rural areas³. In rural areas in Spain, only 25.8 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 29.8 % in towns & suburbs and 40.6 % in cities. Secondary degrees are almost evenly spread over cities (25.7 %), towns and suburbs (25.1 %) as well as rural areas (23.9 %). But the regional differences in primary educational levels are striking. While less than 33.8 % of city residents have a primary, i.e. less than primary, primary and lower secondary education (ISCED2011 levels 0 to 2) attainment level, 45.0 % and 50.3 % of residents in towns & suburbs and rural areas do.

Concerning the educational attainment level of TCN, big differences can be recorded. In cities, where most of the non-EU-28 citizens live, more than 45 % have only primary education. This share is even higher in towns & suburbs (57.0 %) and rural areas (65.1 %). On contrary, only 24.7 % of non-EU-28 citizens have a degree from university, but this value is still much higher than in suburban (17.4 %) and rural (12.7 %) regions. Differences of educational attainment level between Spanish and EU-28 residents range within a broad band from 0.1 pp to 14.7 pp and are therefore scarcely comparable, too (see Table 1). In total, EU-28 (33.4 %) and non-EU-28 (21.6 %) citizens have a lower tertiary education rate than the domestic population (36.5 %).

¹ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020e).

² Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population

The unemployment rate in Spain is 13.8 %, being much above the EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, Melilla has the highest unemployment rate at 26.1 % (female: 31.9 %; male: 21.5 %), closely followed by Ceuta (25.4 %; female: 28.9 %; male: 22.9 %) and Extremadura (21.2 %; female: 27.4 %; male: 16.2 %). Navarre (8.0 %; 9.0 % female; 7.1 % male), Basque Community (8.9 %; 9.2 % female; 8.7 % male) and La Rioja (9.6 %; 9.7 % female; 9.6 % male) are the provinces with the lowest unemployment rates (see Figure 5).

Table 1: Working-age Population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Spanish	32.8%	24.9%	42.2%
	EU-28	23.0%	34.9%	42.1%
	Non EU-28	46.8%	28.5%	24.7%
	Total	33.8%	25.7%	40.6%
Towns & suburbs	Spanish	44.6%	24.2%	31.2%
	EU-28	33.8%	38.9%	27.3%
	Non EU-28	57.0%	25.6%	17.4%
	Total	45.0%	25.1%	29.8%
Rural	Spanish	50.2%	23.2%	26.6%
	EU-28	41.5%	36.8%	21.7%
	Non EU-28	65.1%	22.2%	12.7%
	Total	50.3%	23.9%	25.8%

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020f; Eurostat 2020g).

³ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat 2020h; Eurostat 2020i).

The approximation of unemployment rates by age, nationality and educational level shows that they are influenced by age, education, and immigrant status. The youngest groups (but also the oldest ones) have higher unemployment rates than the central age groups. People with only Spanish nationality show lower unemployment rates than foreign nationals (CES, 2019).

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for Spain. Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (19.8 %). Conversely, people with tertiary education have the lowest unemployment rate (8.7 %), those with secondary a value of 14.1 %. The same trend can be observed at the European level (EU-28; Figure 6).

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher the employment rate, i.e. 80.3 % for tertiary, 65.0 % for secondary and 57.8 % for primary level. From an immigrational point of view, this observation holds for other citizenships as well, as the risk of unemployment decreases by the level of educational attainment. But Spanish have the highest employment rate for tertiary educational attainment level (81.5 %) while EU-28

ranks first for primary (63.7 % vs. 57.8 %) and secondary educational attainment level (71.5 % vs. 64.8 %). non-EU-28 citizens have the lowest employment rate on each level (64.0 %; 62.0 %; 56.5 %; see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020l), own illustration

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). Spain ranges with a value of 17.3 % above the European average. The share of EU-28 citizens residing in Spain is twice as high (27.9 %) and that of non-EU-28 is more than two times as high (27.9 %) than that of the domestic population (14.7 %). In total, approx. 50 % (50.3 %) of all early leavers are jobless but no relying statements can be made in regard to immigrational status because of missing data (Eurostat 2020m).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁴ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income.

Working persons in Spain at primary level earn less (mean: € 13,252; median: € 12,143) than secondary (€ 16,518 or € 14,975) and tertiary levels (€ 23,035 or € 20,999; see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

As working Spanish people have a higher educational attainment level than EU-28 and non-EU-28 this could be one reason (amongst others) that their mean (€ 18,474 vs. € 12,182 and € 10,328) and median (€ 16,303 vs. € 9,897 and € 8,954) equivalized net income is higher (see Figure 9).

A further analysis and decomposition of wage differentials between domestic and foreign workers done by Lehmer and Ludsteck (2013) reveals that factors like seniority, promotions to better-paid occupations as well as job stability also have to be taken into account. These factors cause an improvement in an individual's firm-specific human

capital (training on the job) as the median age of foreign workers and therefore the length of time within the company is lower than for domestic ones. However, these assumptions cannot be verified in the context of this analysis due to a lack of available data.

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

In Spain, most indicators show that vulnerability among foreign immigrants is higher than among the local population, both in the workplace and in health, or other living conditions. Immigrants often work in low-income, precarious occupations, and tend to live in more overcrowded households (CES, 2019).

The indicator 'people at risk of poverty or social exclusion' corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. As non-EU 28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than domestic residents and EU-28 more than one half (54.0 %) belongs to this group though the value of EU-28 is quite high as well (46.7 %). Spanish face the lowest risk of social exclusion and poverty (21.6 %; see Table 2).

⁴ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty					
		At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Spanish		EU-28		Non EU-28	
Very low	Severe	1.0	0.3	1.4	0.1	4.9	0.2
Not very low	Severe	1.0	1.3	2.9	3.5	8.5	2.3
Very low	Non severe	3.2	3.5	4.0	0.6	4.5	1.4
Not very low	Non severe	11.3		34.2		32.2	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		21.6		46.7		54.0	
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		78.5		53.3		46.0
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		78.5		53.3		46.0	
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020p), own illustration

A way to calculate gross domestic product (GDP) is, to sum up, all the income earned by factors of production from firms in the economy—the wages earned by labor; the interest paid to those who lend their savings to firms and the government; the rent earned by those who lease their land or structures to firms; and dividends, the profits paid to the shareholders, the owners of the firms' physical capital. This is a valid measure because the money firms earn by selling goods and services must go somewhere; whatever is not paid as wages, interest or rent is profit. Ultimately, profits are paid out to shareholders as dividends (Krugman and Wells 2017).

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers' social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 %. Spain (45.9 %) lies below European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 10.2 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 43.9 % of GDP in Spain, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. Spanish GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 1,244.8 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 26,430 (Eurostat 2020q).

Within 20 years Spain's gross value added (GVA) increased by +29.8 % (real growth rate). In terms of regional GVA almost all NUTS 2 regions also recorded positive real growth rates, ranging from +17.3 % in Principality of Asturias to +38.8 % in Comunidad de Madrid since 2000; but there are also regions with a decline in economic growth in the

south (- 12.6 %; Melilla: - 14.8 %). The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred also in Madrid (approx. € 35,900) succeeded by northeastern regions (Basque Community (approx. € 34,100); Navarre (approx. € 32,100)).

As in previous years, the southern provinces were far below the national level of € 26,400 (Melilla: € 19,200; Andalusia: € 19,600; Murcia: € 21,600) but also regions in the center (Extremadura: € 19,500; Castile-La Mancha: € 21,000) as well as Canarias (€ 21,200) performed below average. Except for Valencian Community (€ 23,200) all eastern regions rank above average (Balearic Islands: € 28.200; Catalonia: € 31.100, see Table 3).

Provinces with a high share of TCN have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people (Amuedo-Dorantes & De la Rica 2007). In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries or regions. There are significant differences in levels of prosperity among Spanish regions. The most prosperous region in Spain is also the region of the capital Madrid (124 %). It is over 58/56/52 pp richer than Melilla/Andalusia/Castile-La Mancha and Ceuta, which are the poorest. Basque Community ranks second (118 %) and Navarre third (111 %; see Table 3).

**Table 3: Nominal regional GDP (2019)
and real growth rate (Δ 2002 to 2019)**

Region	Total		Per Capita	
	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices (Index, 2015=100; Δ 2002 to 2019)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market prices	Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average
Noroeste	102,382	25.7	23,800	82
Galicia	64,430	29.7	23,900	82
Principality of Asturias	23,765	17.3	23,300	80
Cantabria	14,187	21.4	24,400	84
Noreste	142,380	26.8	31,800	110
Basque Community	74,496	26.5	34,100	118
Navarre	20,974	31.0	32,100	111
La Rioja	8,867	23.9	28,200	97
Aragon	38,044	25.9	28,700	99
Comunidad de Madrid	240,130	38.8	35,900	124
Centro	123,292	25.7	22,400	77
Castile-Leon	59,795	19.1	24,900	86
Castile-La Mancha	42,820	34.0	21,000	72
Extremadura	20,677	28.0	19,500	67
Este	386,629	29.1	28,000	96
Catalonia	236,814	30.1	31,100	107
Valencian Community	116,015	26.6	23,200	80
Balearic Islands	33,799	29.6	28,200	97
Sur	201,608	28.5	19,900	69
Andalusia	165,865	28.0	19,600	68
Region of Murcia	32,356	34.0	21,600	75
Ceuta*	1,765	-12.6	20,900	72
Melilla*	1,622	-14.8	19,200	66
Canarias	47,164	24.5	21,200	73
Spain	1,244,772	29.8	26,400	91

Source: Eurostat (2020r), own calculations and illustration;
Eurostat (2020s), own calculations and illustration;

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors.

The majority (75.5 %) of the employed population works in the service sector in Spain in 2020, while in 2008 that figure was 64.5%, according to data from the Active Population Survey of the National Institute of Statistics (INE; see Table 4). Among the TCN, 74.5 % also work in the service sector, so the percentage is similar. 11.8 % of those employed in this sector are foreigners in Spain in 2020, while TCN represent 7.74 %. Between 2008 and 2020, the number of foreigners and TCN employed in the service sector has decreased in absolute numbers, due to the incidence of the Covid-19 pandemic. However, its proportion has increased in this economic sector, from 57.3 % to 73.5% among foreigners, and from 57.8 % to 74.5 % among TCN.

Regarding other economic sectors, TCN employed in agriculture represent 7.9 % of the total employed in 2020, compared to only 4.0 % of all workers holding Spanish nationality (3.6 % among employed persons with Spanish nationality) see Table 4). Also, TCN employed in industry are less represented (9.6% among TCN), compared to 14.7% of the total employed workers with Spanish nationality. In short, the weight of TCN in the labor market, compared to the native population, is similar in services, higher in agriculture and construction, and lower in industry. This reflects the predominance of these workers in manual and low-skilled activities, usually in jobs not demanded by the native population, which are difficult to fill (Cuadrado et al. 2008).

Almost 65 % of all employed workers in Spain are concentrated in five Autonomous Communities - NUTS 2 level - (Andalusia, Catalonia, Community of Madrid, Valencian Community and Galicia); most of these regions possess the highest growth and economic and demographic vitality in the country (see Figure 10). These five regions also concentrate 69 % of the employed TCN.

Table 4: Employed by nationality and economic sectors 2008 and 2020 (*)

2008								
Economic sectors	Total	Share	Spanish	Share	Foreigners	Share	Non EU-28	Share
Agriculture	960,475	4.2%	762,700	3.9%	194,450	5.7%	141,250	5.8%
Manufacturing	3,449,775	15.0%	3,051,025	15.7%	371,800	10.8%	247,625	10.2%
Construction	2,882,000	12.5%	2,123,925	11.0%	729,625	21.2%	515,800	21.3%
Services	14,903,625	64.6%	12,754,425	65.8%	1,975,300	57.5%	1,398,175	57.8%
Total	23,065,550	100.0%	19,388,550	100.0%	3,437,050	100.0%	2,420,125	100.0%
2020								
Economic sectors	Total	Share	Spanish	Share	Foreigners	Share	Non EU-28	Share
Agriculture	765,350	4.0%	589,075	3.6%	161,275	6.9%	118,750	7.9%
Manufacturing	2,698,225	14.1%	2,381,650	14.7%	250,625	10.8%	145,350	9.6%
Construction	1,244,075	6.5%	985,825	6.1%	203,325	8.8%	121,600	8.1%
Services	14,494,750	75.5%	12,228,500	75.6%	1,705,925	73.5%	1,122,225	74.5%
Total	19,202,425	100.0%	16,185,025	100.0%	2,321,100	100.0%	1,507,950	100.0%

(*) On the table, only people with one nationality (only Spanish or other), but not with double nationality.

Source: Economically Active Population Survey (EPA), 2008 and 2020; National Statistics Institute (INE).

Figure 10: Employment by nationalities and autonomous communities* 2020 (*)

(*) On the table, only people with one nationality (only Spanish or other), but not with double nationality.

Source: Economically Active Population Survey (EPA); National Statistics Institute (INE)

Apart from the Community of Madrid (with the capital), the more touristic and coastal regions have the bigger presence of TCN workers, and only seven of them (Catalonia, Community of Madrid, Andalusia, Valencian Community, Canary Islands,

Region of Murcia and Balearic Islands) concentrate 82.3 % of the employed TCN in the country (see Figure 10). On the contrary, their presence is much lower in inland and more depopulated regions.

Table 5: Workers' occupations by nationality and branches of economic activity 2020 (*)

Workers' occupations	Total	Share	Spanish	Share	EU-28	Share	Non EU-28	Share
Directors and managers	784,025	3.4%	693,275	3.7%	66,925	2.2%	25,299	1.2%
Scientific and intellectual technicians and professionals	3,852,250	16.9%	3,518,800	18.7%	247,550	8.0%	146,875	7.1%
Technicians; support professionals	2,296,600	10.1%	2,102,400	11.2%	147,875	4.8%	66,925	3.2%
Accounting, administrative and other clerical employees	2,185,050	9.6%	1,993,250	10.6%	128,375	4.2%	71,500	3.5%
Workers in catering, personal, protective services and vendors	4,651,475	20.5%	3,638,025	19.4%	783,150	25.4%	583,375	28.3%
Skilled workers in the agricultural, livestock, forestry and fishing sectors	450,900	2.0%	393,325	2.1%	49,300	1.6%	32,825	1.6%
Craftsmen and skilled workers in manufacturing and construction industries (except plant and machinery operators)	2,349,375	10.3%	1,905,900	10.2%	348,625	11.3%	201,500	9.8%
Plant and machinery operators and assemblers	1,613,850	7.1%	1,357,625	7.2%	200,400	6.5%	111,850	5.4%
Elementary occupations	2,911,550	12.8%	1,919,350	10.2%	791,125	25.7%	581,800	28.2%
Military occupations	115,300	0.5%	111,250	0.6%	5,000	0.2%	1,750	0.1%
They left their last job more than 1 year ago	1,219,200	5.4%	933,800	5.0%	233,225	7.6%	168,025	8.1%
Unemployed seeking first job	303,800	1.3%	209,225	1.1%	81,775	2.7%	71,075	3.4%
Total	22,733,325	100.0%	18,776,175	100.0%	3,078,825	100.0%	2,062,750	100.0%

(*) On the table, only people with one nationality (only Spanish or other), but not with double nationality.

Source: Economically Active Population Survey (EPA), 2020; National Statistics Institute (INE).

There is heavy demand in critical sectors of the job market, with an immediate and evident stratification. This means that Spanish workers are in the top segment of the job market, while TCN are in the second or bottom segment with insecure jobs, low wages, harsh working conditions, working on a temporary or even seasonal basis (CES 2019). Also, TCN workers have the most insecure jobs - normally from the countryside (from the agricultural and livestock sector), and this issue has become particularly evident during the health pandemic.

For example, after the economic crisis between 2007 and 2014, 20 % of jobs in Spain were destroyed. As many immigrants worked concentrated in the less qualified segment, less protected

and more exposed to economic fluctuations, many of them lost their jobs. This situation generated great inequality between foreigners and nationals in terms of employment and unemployment rates, in terms of proportion of employees in elementary occupations, proportion of temporary contracts, and income differences (Godenau et al. 2014).

According to the mentioned stratification, workers with Spanish nationality occupy more qualified, technical and professional positions ("Scientific and intellectual technicians and professionals", also "Technicians; support professionals", "Accounting, administrative and other clerical employees", and also "Workers in catering, personal, protective services and vendors"). On the con-

trary, the presence of TCN is greater in less qualified jobs, in the service sector ("Workers in catering, personal, protective services and vendors ") and in "Elementary occupations "(see Table 5).

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 1.24 % for Spain (2018), which is a slight increase of 0.03 percentage points to 2017. The total amount of research expenditures was € 14.95 billion, the largest share (49.2 %) was financed by the business enterprise sector. 37.9 % were financed by the government sector, 8.1 % by foreign countries (rest of the world) and 4.0 % by higher education and private non-profit sector (Eurostat 2020t).

Regional data is published on NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 level. Basque Community has the highest ratio in 2018 (2.01 %). The metropolitan area of Madrid and Navarre are second (1.70 %) just ahead of Catalonia (1.54 %), Castile-Leon (1.32 %) and Valencian Community (1.06 %). All other regions have ratios lower than 1.00 %. Canarias ranks last (0.47 %) with Castile-La Mancha (0.53 %), Extremadura (0.61 %), Principality of Asturias (0.81 %) and La Rioja (0.82 %) only slightly better, but there is no reliable data available for Ceuta and Melilla (see Table 6).

In accordance to the research & development (R&D) funding structure almost more than one third (37.2 % or 49.571 full-time equivalent (FTE))

of the researchers work in the business enterprise sector. 15.6 % (or 20,844 FTE) work in the government sector and 0.2 % (or 256 FTE) in the private non-profit sector. The higher education sector (46.9 % or 62,542 FTE) is by far the greatest employer of researchers. This makes a total of 133,213 FTE. Further analysis on educational attainment level reveals that most researchers (55.5 %) have tertiary education but not doctoral or equivalent level; 43.8 % belong to the latter whereas 1.2 % have less than primary, primary, secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (see Figure 11).

Table 6: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
Noroeste	897.0	0.90%
Galicia	591.0	0.94%
Principality of Asturias	188.0	0.81%
Cantabria	118.0	0.86%
Noreste	2,205.0	1.60%
Basque Community	1,451.0	2.01%
Navarre	344.0	1.70%
La Rioja	70.0	0.82%
Aragon	340.0	0.92%
Comunidad de Madrid	3,923.0	1.70%
Centro	1,104.0	0.93%
Castile-Leon	763.0	1.32%
Castile-La Mancha	219.0	0.53%
Extremadura	122.0	0.61%
Este	4,816.0	1.29%
Catalonia	3,513.0	1.54%
Valencian Community	1,174.0	1.06%
Balearic Islands	129.0	0.40%
Sur	1,787.0	0.91%
Andalusia	1,479.0	0.92%
Region of Murcia	303.0	0.96%
Ceuta*	:	0.00%
Melilla*	:	0.00%
Canarias	215.0	0.47%
Spain	14,946.0	1.24%

Source: Eurostat (2020u), own illustration

As the group of migrants (EU-28 or non-EU-28) living in Spain has a lower share of tertiary education it is therefore likely that they are underrepresented in Spanish R&D personnel.

Figure 11: R&D researchers (full-time equivalent (FTE)) by sectors of performance and educational attainment level 2017 (ISCED2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020v), own illustration

Summary

This Statistical Briefings examines the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Spain.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 4,960,467 persons with non-Spanish citizenship were living in Spain. This corresponded to a share of 10.5 % of Spain's total population. Among non-Spanish nationals, 39.5 % (4.1 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (0.06 %). A total of 2,971,030 persons (or 6.3 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Spanish, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Spain lying above the average.

Within the last 20 years the population increase of Spain has mainly be dominated by immigration. From 2006 to 2019 all Spanish regions profited heavily with regard to its working-age population. Without immigration, all regions would have suffered from a decrease in its population aged between 20 and 64 years.

Despite the relevance of migration for labor supply, the employment rate of TCN is much lower compared to Spanish nationals and EU-28 citizens. Also noteworthy is the strong segmentation of the labor market, which pushes immigrants to occupy jobs not desired by the native population. Another relevant factor to be considered is the lower educational attainment level of migrants, with the consecutive effects of lower income levels and a higher risk of poverty.

The pattern of education of TCN differs substantially from that of Spanish nationals: The foreign population of third countries is disproportionately represented in primary and secondary education, whereas they are underrepresented in tertiary education levels.

From a spatial point of view, the concentration of better-educated migrants is highest in Spanish cities. Provinces with a higher ratio of TCN are also characterized by higher economic growth, being more attractive for TCN on the one hand and offering more labor supply on the other hand.

The below average regional GVA growth rate, especially in rural provinces like Ceuta, Melilla is indirectly linked to immigration from abroad but primarily to internal migration from rural areas to cities and metropolitan areas. These emigration flows tend to reinforce the erosion of the economic basis, because they have a negative impact on the potential workforce and the economic attractiveness of the region. Economic performance is stagnating, accompanied by declining population figures.

As a result, governments need to invest in education on the one hand and in research and development (R&D) on the other, to enable long-term prosperity and growth impulses. Currently, the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) are estimated at 1.24 % (2018), which is a slight increase of 0.03 percentage points to 2017. But there is again a striking regional variation from densely populated areas

with a high number of innovative enterprises (e.g. Madrid, Basque Community) to less densely populated autonomous communities like Ceuta and Melilla.

Many rural areas in Spain suffer an acute problem of depopulation. In recent years, the arrival of foreign immigrant workers has contributed to alleviating the situation. Moreover, these immigrants find themselves in a very vulnerable situation with very limited resources; this is due to the lack of resources and to the difficulties associated with the provision of social services in depopulated rural areas (Sampedro & Camarero 2018).

Summing up, immigrants in Spain play a pivotal role in reviving rural areas, and with the appropriate policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

Statistical Briefings Sweden

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Sweden on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

SWEDEN

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Sweden

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCNs) in Sweden

On January 1, 2020, a total of 940,580 persons with non-Swedish citizenship were living in Sweden. This corresponds to a share of 9.1 % of Sweden's total population. Among non-Swedish nationals, 34.3 % (322,324 persons; 3.1 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (40,855 persons; 0.4 %). A total of 577,401 persons (or 5.60 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Swedish, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Sweden is at EU-28 average level.

Considering the nationalities of TCN, Syrians (1.13 %) are above Afghans (0.48 %), Eritreans (0.42 %), Somalis (0.30 %), and Iranians (0.26 %). In total, almost half (46.2 %) of TCN living in Sweden belong to these nationalities. Figure 1

gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Sweden.

Population Development & Population Structure

The number of inhabitants in Sweden increased in the past and this development is projected to continue according to current population forecasts. As of January 1, 2020, there were 10,327,589 persons registered in Sweden. This corresponds to an increase of 1,466,163 citizens (+16.5 %) within the last 20 years since 2000 (before eastward enlargement of EU in 2004).

A long-term analysis of population development since the turn of the new millennium reveals clear regional differences. Norrbottens län (-1.8 %) is the only Swedish region where the number of inhabitants declined, and stagnation took place in Västernorrlands län (+0.1 %). With under-average

population growth recorded in the north, the situation is different in the south: Uppsala län (+29.4%), Stockholms län (+29.3 %) as well as Skåne län (+ 21.2 %) have very high growth rates (see Figure 2).

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., another economically relevant aspect is labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

As Figure 3 (a)-(d) indicate, the increase in the working-age population (+492,200 inh.) is dominated by immigration (EU-28: +41,600 inh.; non-EU-28: +263,000 inh.). Domestic population increased as well (+170,700 inh.) but on a smaller scale than immigrants in total, though this makes Sweden special, as most of the industrialized countries had a tendency of shrinking domestic working-age population. From a regional perspective, Stockholm (+21.4 %), Sydsverige (+10.8 %) and Östra Mellansverige (+7.5 %) are the growing areas, stagnation takes place in Småland med öarna (1.3 %) and Norra Mellansverige (0.2 %), whereas Mellersta Norrland (-3.6 %) and Övre Norrland (-6.2 %) shrunk in the past.

According to current forecasts the increase of labor force potential does not stop in the future though the growth rates are not that high as they were in the past. Working-age population will evolve by 10.7 % until 2040. There are only two regions which are projected to shrink in the future, i.e. Västernorrlands län (-2.11 %) and Norrbottens län (-6.04 %; see Figure 4).

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be "dependent" on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being working age from 20 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in 2020 in Sweden is 76.5 %. The dependency rate is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are a more prosperous economy, i.e. more people in working-age, and low child ratios. Most metropolitan regions (e.g., Stockholm) in Sweden are also characterized by relatively low rates. High dependency ratios are found in Dalarnas län (88.3 %), Kalmar län (88.1 %) and Södermanlands län (87.1 %).

As a result of the ageing society, the total-age dependency ratios will rise in the future by 4.1 pp to 80.6 % in 2040, resulting in implications/challenges for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., expenditures for pensions).

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2002 to 2020), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

Figure 3: Working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2006 to 2019)

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

Figure 4: Projections of working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040) NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of Sweden's domestic population is 37.6 %, which is only slightly below that of the total population (37.8 %). Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) Sweden has a way above-average tertiary education rate. Sweden ranks 7th within the EU-28 next to Lithuania (37.9 %), ahead of Estonia (36.5 %), Belgium (36.0 %) and Spain (35.1 %). Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities¹ than in towns and suburbs², which in turn is higher than in rural areas. In rural areas³ in Sweden, only 28.5 % of individuals have university degrees, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), compared to 34.6 % in towns & suburbs and 47.3 % in cities. In contrast, secondary degrees are more common in less densely populated areas. While less than 35.1 % of city residents have secondary, i.e. upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 3 to 4) attainment level, 43.8 % and 47.5 % of residents in towns & suburbs and rural areas do. Primary educational attainment level has low relevance as approx. only 1 out of 5 residents in Sweden belongs to this group.

Concerning the educational attainment level of TCN, big differences can be recorded. In cities, where most of the non-EU-28 citizens live, approx. 40 % (39.8 %) have only primary education. This share is even higher in towns & suburbs (53.9 %) and rural areas (60.4 %). The shares of non-EU-28 citizens with primary or tertiary education (41.6 %) living in cities are almost the same. On contrary, only 28.5 % or 23.5 % of non-EU-28 citizens living in towns and suburbs or rural areas have a degree from university. Differences of educational attainment level between Swedish and EU-28 residents range within a broad band from

1.4 pp to 26.7 pp with the highest variations between secondary and tertiary levels of education (see Table 1). In total, EU-28 (56.4 %) have a higher tertiary education rate than domestic population (37.6 %) which ranks above non-EU-28 (32.6 %) citizens.

Table 1: Working-age Population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	Swedish	15.9%	37.0%	47.1%
	EU-28	14.5%	21.8%	63.6%
	Non EU-28	39.8%	18.6%	41.6%
	Total	17.7%	35.1%	47.3%
Towns & suburbs	Swedish	19.1%	46.5%	34.5%
	EU-28	22.6%	24.9%	52.5%
	Non EU-28	53.9%	17.7%	28.5%
	Total	21.6%	43.8%	34.6%
Rural	Swedish	21.4%	50.4%	28.2%
	EU-28	27.6%	23.7%	48.7%
	Non EU-28	60.4%	16.1%	23.5%
	Total	24.0%	47.5%	28.5%

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

The unemployment rate in Sweden is 6.0 %, being close to EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, Sydsverige has the highest unemployment rate at 8.1 % (female: 8.2 %; male: 7.9 %), followed by Norra Mellansverige (6.7 %; female: 6.6 %; male: 6.8 %) and Östra Mellansverige (6.3 %; female: 6.3 %; male: 6.3 %). Småland med öarna (5.1 %; 5.7 % female; 4.6 % male) and Stockholm (5.2 %) are the provinces with the lowest unemployment rates (see Figure 5).

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for Sweden. Those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (17.5 %). Conversely, people with tertiary education have

¹ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat 2020e).

² Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population

density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat 2020f; Eurostat 2020g).

³ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat 2020h; Eurostat 2020i).

the lowest unemployment rate (3.8 %), those with secondary a value of 4.9 %. Similar results are observed at the European level (EU-28; see Figure 6).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher is the employment rate, i.e. 88.8 % for tertiary, 82.9 % for secondary and 61.2 % for primary level. From an immigrational point of view, this observation holds for other citizenships as well, as the risk of unemployment decreases by the highest educational attainment. But Swedes have the highest employment rate for tertiary (90.5 %) and secondary (83.7 %) educational attainment level, while EU-28 ranks first for primary (69.2 % vs. 66.7 %). Non-EU-28 citizens have the lowest employment rate on each level (67.2 %; 62.6 %; 43.2 %; see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020l), own illustration

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). Sweden ranges with a value of 6.5 % below the European average. The share of non-EU-28 is

more than four times as high (21.0 %) than of the domestic population (4.8 %). In total, approx. 50 % (46.2 %) of early school leavers are jobless but no relying statements can be made in regard to immigrational status because of missing data (Eurostat 2020m).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁴ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income.

Working persons in Sweden at primary level earn less (mean: € 20,805; median: € 19,485) than secondary (mean: € 28,288; median: € 27,107) and tertiary levels (mean: € 32,825; median: € 29,901; see Figure 8). Working Swedish earn more than EU-28 and non-EU-28 citizens (mean: € 29,630 vs. € 23,253 and € 16,160; median: € 27,782 vs. € 21,590 and € 14,108; see Figure 9).

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

The indicator ‘people at risk of poverty or social exclusion’ corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households

⁴ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

with very low work intensity. As non-EU 28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than domestic and EU-28 residents almost 3 out of 5 persons (58.2 %) belong to this group, though the value of EU-28 is quite high as well (32.6 %). Swedish face the lowest risk of social exclusion and poverty (13.8 %; see Table 2).

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers’ social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 % in the euro area. Sweden (47.8 %) almost equals European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 20.3 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 31.9 % of GDP in Sweden, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. Swedish GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 474.6 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 46,170 (Eurostat 2020q).

Within 20 years Sweden’s gross value added (GVA) increased by 35.9 % (real growth rate). In terms of

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty					
		At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Sweden		EU-28		Non EU-28	
Very low	Severe	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.8	0.3
Not very low	Severe	0.2	0.3	1.2	1.0	1.6	2.0
Very low	Non severe	2.2	1.2	3.5	0.5	19.7	2.0
Not very low	Non severe	9.7		26.4		25.8	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		13.8		32.6		58.2	
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		86.2		67.5		41.8
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		86.2		67.5		41.8	
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020p), own illustration

Table 3: Nominal regional GDP (2019) and real growth rate (Δ 2002 to 2019)

Region	Total		Per Capita	
	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices (Index, 2015=100; Δ 2002 to 2019)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market prices	Purchasing power standard (PPS, EU27 from 2020), per inhabitant in percentage of the EU27 (from 2020) average
Östra Sverige	219,636	43.4	53,800	138
Stockholm	152,809	49.2	64,700	166
Östra Mellansverige	66,827	30.1	38,900	100
Södra Sverige	185,268	33.5	41,700	107
Småland med öarna	33,683	21.4	38,900	100
Sydsverige	60,234	32.9	39,400	101
Västsverige	91,351	38.4	44,600	115
Norra Sverige	69,464	18.4	39,600	102
Norra Mellansverige	31,358	17.0	36,600	94
Mellersta Norrland	14,834	18.2	39,500	101
Övre Norrland	23,272	20.6	44,700	115
Sweden	474,468	35.9	46,200	119

Source: Eurostat (2020r), own illustration; Eurostat (2020s), own illustration]

regional GVA all provinces recorded positive real growth, ranging from 17.0 % in Norra Mellansverige to 49.2 % in Stockholm since 2000. The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred also in Stockholm (approx. € 64,700) succeeded by Övre Norrland (approx. € 44,700). As in

previous years, the northern and southern provinces were all below the national level of € 46,200 (see Table 3).

Provinces with a high share of TCN have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Expressing GDP in PPS (purchasing power standards) eliminates differences in price levels between countries or regions. There are significant differences in levels of prosperity among Swedish provinces. The capital is the most prosperous region (166 %); it is over 72/66/65 pp richer than Norra Mellansverige/Småland med öarna and Östra Mellansverige/Sydsverige. Västsverige and Övre Norrland (both 115 %) rank second (see Table 3).

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors.

In total, approx. 5.1 million people were employed in 2019 in Sweden. More than three quarters (77.8 %) are employed in the service sector and 19.0 % in the production sector; only 1.9 % work in the primary sector (see Table 4).

A more detailed examination of the different sectors of the economy reveals that “Human health

and social work activities” (16.1 %), “Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles” (11.7 %), “Education” (10.9 %) and “Manufacturing” (10.6 %) are the most important economic sections in regard to employment.

Due to non-available data no exact analyses are possible in regard to TCN. The analysis by region of birth shows that 8.9 % belong to the group of Europeans except domestic born population which accounts for 80.3 %. 10.9 % are from the rest of the world.

Europeans are overrepresented (above 8.9 %) in “Administrative and support service activities”

(14.4 %), “Accommodation and food service activities” (12.6 %), “Construction” (11.1 %), “Transportation and storage” (10.1 %), “Manufacturing” (9.3 %) and “Human health and social work activities” (9.0 %) whereas all remaining sections are of lower importance. Citizens from the rest of the world tend to work in the same sections whereas their importance must be highlighted in “Accommodation and food service activities” (30.5 %), “Administrative and support service activities” (17.7 %), “Transportation and storage” (15.7 %) and “Human health and social work activities” (14.8 %; see Table 4).

Table 4: Employment by economic activity 2019

Economic Activity	Employed persons in 2019	Share	Swedish	Europeans	Rest-of-the-World
Primary Sector	97,686	1.9%	93.5%	4.8%	1.7%
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	97,686	1.9%	93.5%	4.8%	1.7%
Secondary Sector	962,500	19.0%	84.1%	9.7%	6.2%
Mining and quarrying	8,855	0.2%	95.1%	3.6%	1.3%
Manufacturing	538,988	10.6%	82.9%	9.3%	7.8%
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	28,420	0.6%	92.1%	4.5%	3.4%
Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities	23,334	0.5%	87.8%	7.1%	5.1%
Construction	362,903	7.2%	84.7%	11.1%	4.2%
Tertiary Sector	3,938,031	77.8%	79.1%	8.8%	12.1%
Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	594,358	11.7%	84.0%	7.2%	8.7%
Transportation and storage	241,112	4.8%	74.2%	10.1%	15.7%
Accommodation and food service activities	182,575	3.6%	56.9%	12.6%	30.5%
Information and communication	217,689	4.3%	81.7%	8.2%	10.1%
Financial and insurance activities	96,074	1.9%	87.9%	6.4%	5.7%
Real estate activities	86,306	1.7%	87.4%	6.7%	5.8%
Professional, scientific and technical activities	329,189	6.5%	84.4%	8.2%	7.4%
Administrative and support service activities	286,590	5.7%	67.9%	14.4%	17.7%
Public administration and defence; compulsory social security	305,484	6.0%	88.5%	5.7%	5.8%
Education	552,818	10.9%	79.8%	8.8%	11.4%
Human health and social work activities	814,709	16.1%	76.1%	9.0%	14.8%
Arts, entertainment and recreation	105,785	2.1%	86.8%	6.8%	6.4%
Other service activities, Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use; Activities of extra-territorial organisations and bodies	125,342	2.5%	77.7%	8.8%	13.5%
Others	63,337	1.3%	75.4%	8.3%	16.4%
Total	5,061,554	100.0%	80.3%	8.9%	10.9%

Source Statistics Sweden (2021), own calculations and illustrations

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 3.36 % for Sweden (2017) which is a slight increase of 0.11 percentage points to 2016. The total amount of research expenditures was € 16.14 billion, the largest share (60.7 %) was financed by the business enterprise sector. 25.0 % were funded by the government sector, 10.1 % by foreign countries (rest of the world), 3.3 % by private non-profit sector and only 0.6 % by the higher education sector (Eurostat 2020t).

Regional data is published on NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 level. Västsverige is the province with the highest ratio in 2017 (4.83 %) succeeded by Stockholm (3.75 %) and Östra Mellansverige (3.51 %). Except for Sydsverige (3.23 %) all other provinces were well behind and below the all-Swedish ratio of 3.36 %. Norra Mellansverige ranks last (1.20 %) with Övre Norrland (2.30 %) only slightly better (see Table 5).

Table 5: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
Manner-Suomi	6,432.3	2.76%
Östra Sverige	8,005.8	3.67%
Stockholm	5,566.0	3.75%
Östra Mellansverige	2,439.7	3.51%
Södra Sverige	7,064.9	3.71%
Småland med öarna	n.a.	n.a.
Sydsverige	1,962.2	3.23%
Västsverige	4,535.8	4.83%
Norra Sverige	1,052.8	1.48%
Norra Mellansverige	389.4	1.20%
Mellersta Norrland	n.a.	n.a.
Övre Norrland	540.3	2.30%
Sweden	16,142.2	3.36%

Source: Eurostat (2020u), own illustration

In accordance to the research & development (R&D) funding structure almost three quarters (70.9 % or 51,843 FTE) of the researchers work in the business enterprise sector. Approx. one quarter (23.9 % or 17,501 FTE) works in the higher education sector and the remaining in the government sector (5.2 % or 3,788 FTE) in the higher education sector. This makes a total of 73,132 FTE (Eurostat 2020v).

Summary

This Statistical Briefings examines the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Sweden.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 940,580 persons with non-Swedish citizenship were living in Sweden. This corresponds to a share of 9.1 % of Sweden's total population. Among non-Swedish nationals, 34.3 % (3.1 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (0.4 %). A total of 577,401 persons (or 5.60 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Swedish, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Sweden is at EU-28 average.

Within the last 20 years the population increase of Sweden has strongly be dominated by immigration. From 2006 to 2019 especially the southern regions profited heavily with regard to its working-age population. Without immigration, many regions (especially in the north) would have suffered from a decrease in its population aged between 20 and 64 years.

Despite the relevance of migration for labor supply, the employment rate of TCN is much lower compared to domestic population and EU-28 citizens. One relevant factor to be considered here is the lower educational attainment level of migrants, with the consecutive effects of lower income levels and a higher risk of poverty.

The pattern of education of TCN differs substantially from that of Swedish nationals: The foreign population of third countries is disproportionately represented in primary education, whereas they are underrepresented in tertiary education levels.

From a spatial point of view, the concentration of better-educated migrants is highest in Swedish cities. Provinces with a higher ratio of TCN are also characterized by higher economic growth, being more attractive for TCN on the one hand and offering more labor supply on the other hand.

The below average regional GVA growth rates, especially in northern and southern provinces is indirectly linked to immigration from abroad but preferably to internal migration from rural areas to cities and metropolitan areas. These emigration flows tend to reinforce the erosion of the economic basis, because they have a negative impact on the potential workforce and the economic attractiveness of the region. Economic performance is stagnating, accompanied by declining population figures.

As a result, governments need to invest in education on the one hand and in research and development (R&D) on the other, to enable long-term prosperity and growth. Currently the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) are estimated at 3.36 % (2017) which is a slight increase of 0.11 percentage points to 2016. But there is again a striking regional variation from densely populated areas with a high number of innovative enterprises (e.g. Stockholm) to less densely populated provinces (e.g. Norran Mellansverige or Övre Norrland).

Summing up, immigrants in Sweden play a pivotal role in reviving rural areas, and with the appropriate policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

Statistical Briefings Turkey

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for Turkey on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

TURKEY

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in Turkey

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCN) in Turkey

On January 1, 2020, a total of 1,528,271 persons with non-Turkish citizenship¹ were living in Turkey. This corresponded to a share of 1.8 % of Turkey's total population. Among non-Turkish nationals, only 11.3 % (172,989 persons; 0.2 % of total population) came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries (3,459 persons; 0.004 %). A total of 1,351,823 persons (or 1.6 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Turks, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and

3.8 %, therefore Turkey lying way below the average.

Considering the nationalities of TCN, Iraqis (0.38 %), Afghans (0.18 %), Turkmen (0.16 %), Syrians (0.14 %) and Iranians (0.11 %) are the biggest groups by citizenship. In total, more than half (59.7 %) of TCN living in Turkey belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in Turkey.

¹ Foreign population covers individuals who are holding a valid residence/work permit at the reference day and individuals who have a valid address declaration at the reference day while holding an identity document equivalent to residence permit such as international protection identity document and the individuals who have already renounced

his/her Turkish Republic citizenship and who have a valid address declaration at the reference day. Foreigners holding visas or residence permits shorter than 3 months with the purpose of training, tourism, scientific research, etc. are not covered. Also Syrians (3,671,811 as of March 21, 2021) under temporary protection are not included in the figures (see Turkish Statistical Institute 2020a).

Population Development & Population Structure

The number of inhabitants in Turkey has increased in the past and this development is projected to continue in the future. As of January 1, 2020, there were 83,154,997 persons registered in Turkey. This corresponds to an increase of 16,265,572 citizens (+24.3 %) within the last 20 years since 2000. The main cause of the population increase are high fertility rates before the 1990s. A long-term

analysis of population development since the turn of the new millennium reveals differences, though the number of inhabitants increased in 86.4 % of all NUTS 3 regions. Yalova (+85.28 %), Tekirdag (+81.39 %), Antalya (+75.55 %), Sanliurfa (+67.12 %) and Gaziantep (+62.03 %) experienced the highest population growth in the past. Eleven regions shrunk since 2001. Relative reductions were highest for Yozgat (-22.0 %), Ardahan (-19.1 %) and Kars (-11.3 %; see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2001 to 2020), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

While most discussions about changing demographic structures focus on population ageing and the sustainability of pension systems, urbanization etc., one relevant aspect is labor supply, i.e. the population aged 15 to 64 years or 20 to 64 years in industrialized economies and nations. From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking for work.

As indicates, there are regional disparities among the NUTS 2 regions in Turkey in regard to the increase of working-age population though it increased in all of them. The highest growth rates in

labor force potential are recorded in Istanbul (+5.9 %), Ankara (+2.3 %), Kocaeli, Sakarya, Düzce, Bolu, Yalova (+1.7 %), Bursa, Eskisehir, Bilecik (+1.5 %), Antalya, Isparta, Burdur (+1.5 %), Sanliurfa, Diyarbakir (+1.5 %), Izmir (+1.3 %) and Gaziantep, Adiyaman, Kilis (+1.1 %). In all other regions the labor force potential stagnated, i.e. range between +0.1 and 0.9 %.

As Figure 4 (a)-(b) indicate, the increase in the population from 2016 to 2019 within the regions is mainly caused by an increase in the Turkish population (78.6 %) whereas foreigners account for only 21.4 % of population growth. Summing up, almost all areas are experiencing an overall growth in population.

Figure 3: Working-age population 20 to 64 years; Δ 2006 to 2019

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

Figure 4: Population development by citizenship (Δ 2016 to 2019)

(a)

(b)

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (2020b), own illustration

Education and (Un)Employment

The unemployment rate in Turkey is 13.5 %, being below the EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, the southeastern region Mardin, Batman, Siirt has by far the highest unemployment rate at 29.9 % (female: 42.1 %; male: 25.7 %), followed by Van, Mus, Bitlis,

Hakkari (25.9 %; female: 27.1 %; male: 25.4 %) and Sanliurfa, Diyarbakir (23.6 %; female: 18.6 %; male: 25.3 %). Kastamonu, Çankiri, Sinop (7.7 %; 10.5 % female; 6.0 % male) and Konya, Karaman (7.9 %; 9.3 % female; 7.3 % male) are the provinces with the lowest unemployment rates (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

The tertiary education rate of the total population living in Turkey is 18.4 %. Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) Turkey has a far below-average tertiary education rate. If Turkey was EU-28 member it would approx. ranks 26th, ahead of Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %). Luxembourg (41.0 %), Ireland (40.7 %) and United Kingdom (40.6 %) rank at the top end, while the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) rank at the bottom.

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation does not hold for Turkey but for EU-28: In Turkey, those with secondary education are most affected by unemployment (14.6 %). Conversely, people with primary education have the lowest unemployment rate (13.1 %), and those with tertiary (13.5 %) rank in the midfield. Contrary results are

observed at the European level, as the risk of unemployment decreases the higher the educational level is (EU-28; Figure 6).

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level 2019 (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020d), own illustration

The abovementioned findings foster, at least for EU-28, the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment of human beings.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed. In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year olds in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). Turkey ranges with a value of 28.7 % way above the European average. In total, more than a half (55.1 %) of all early leavers are jobless but no relying statements can be made in regard to immigrational status because of missing data (Eurostat (2020e)).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

The educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median² equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income. Working persons in Turkey at primary level earn less (mean: € 3,352; median: € 2,780) than secondary (€ 4,476 or € 3,586) and tertiary levels (€ 7,566 or € 5,761; see Figure 7). Working Turkish earn less than foreigners and non-EU-28 citizens which are a subgroup of foreigners in Turkey (mean: € 4,414 vs. € 6,356 and € 6,374; median: € 3,285 vs. € 3,504 and € 3,451; see Figure 8).

The indicator ‘people at risk of poverty or social exclusion’ corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. Almost one half of foreigners (43.1 %) as well as the subgroup of non-EU-28 citizens (43.0 %) belong to this group whereas the values for the domestic population (36.4 %) are comparable low (see Table 1). Due to

² The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

a lack of data no statements about the causality can be made as this is quite surprising in regard to the comparable high income of foreigners in Turkey.

Figure 7: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2019 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020f), own illustration

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2019 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020g), own illustration

A way to calculate gross domestic product (GDP) is, to sum up, all the income earned by factors of production from firms in the economy—the wages earned by labor; the interest paid to those who lend their savings to firms and the government;

the rent earned by those who lease their land or structures to firms; and dividends, the profits paid to the shareholders, the owners of the firms' physical capital. This is a valid measure because the money firms earn by selling goods and services

must go somewhere; whatever is not paid as wages, interest or rent is profit. Ultimately, profits are paid out to shareholders as dividends (Krugman and Wells 2017).

Table 1: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty					
		At risk		Not at risk		At risk	
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	Turkey		Foreign country		Non EU-28	
Very low	Severe	1.9	1.4	7.0	2.1	7.4	2.2
Not very low	Severe	8.2	12.4	12.1	9.7	12.9	9.1
Very low	Non severe	1.1	4.8	0.1	8.4	0.1	8.9
Not very low	Non severe	6.6		3.7		2.4	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		36.4		43.1		43.0	
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		63.5	56.9			56.9
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		63.5		56.9		56.9	
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020h), own illustration

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers' social contributions) was the largest income component of EU-28 GDP accounting for 47.8 % and 48.0 % in the euro area. EU candidate country Turkey (31.3 %) lies below European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 9.0 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 59.6 % of GDP in Turkey, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. Turkish GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 679.5 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 8,230 (Eurostat 2020i).

Within 15 years Turkey's gross value added (GVA) increased by 59.9 % (real growth rate). In terms of regional GVA all provinces also recorded positive real growth, ranging from 34.1 % in Zonguldak, Karabük, Bartın to 77.3 % in Mardin, Batman, Sirtak, Siirt since 2004. The highest regional GDP per capita at current prices occurred also in Istanbul (approx. € 13,700) succeeded by Ankara (approx. € 11,200) and Kocaeli, Sakarya, Düzce, Bolu, Yalova (approx. € 10,300). As in previous years, all regions east of Bati Anadolu (approx. € 9,700) were below the national level of € 8,200 (see Table 2).

Table 2: Nominal regional GDP (2019) and real growth rate (Δ 2004 to 2019)

Region	Total		Per Capita
	GDP (in €) at current market prices	Real growth rate of regional gross value added (GVA) at basic prices (Index, 2015=100; Δ 2004 to 2019)	GDP (in €) per capita at current market prices
Istanbul	208,791	63.7	13,700
Bati Marmara	30,838	59.5	8,600
Tekirdag, Edirne, Kizilirmak	17,713	63.3	9,700
Balikesir, Çanakkale	13,125	54.5	7,400
Ege	85,817	57.2	8,100
Izmir	41,372	57.0	9,500
Aydin, Denizli, Mugla	22,799	56.9	7,300
Manisa, Afyonkarahisar, Kütahya, Usak	21,645	57.9	7,000
Dogu Marmara	78,037	60.1	9,700
Bursa, Eskisehir, Bilecik	37,733	58.1	9,100
Kocaeli, Sakarya, Düzce, Bolu, Yalova	40,304	62.0	10,300

Bati Anadolu	78,383	62.4	9,700
Ankara	62,243	62.1	11,200
Konya, Karaman	16,140	63.6	6,500
Akdeniz	70,418	58.4	6,700
Antalya, Isparta, Burdur	28,218	64.8	8,900
Adana, Mersin	25,379	57.7	6,300
Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Osmaniye	16,820	49.9	5,100
Orta Anadolu	24,425	52.0	6,000
Kirikkale, Aksaray, Nigde, Nevşehir, Kirsehir	9,252	55.5	5,800
Kayseri, Sivas, Yozgat	15,173	49.9	6,200
Bati Karadeniz	25,086	43.2	5,400
Zonguldak, Karabük, Bartın	5,968	34.1	5,700
Kastamonu, Çankiri, Sinop	4,630	48.1	5,700
Samsun, Tokat, Çorum, Amasya	14,488	46.0	5,100
Dogu Karadeniz	14,936	52.3	5,500
Kuzeydogu Anadolu	9,931	53.3	4,500
Erzurum, Erzincan, Bayburt	5,835	53.1	5,400
Agri, Kars, Iğdir, Ardahan	4,096	53.7	3,700
Ortadogu Anadolu	16,073	62.6	4,100
Malatya, Elazığ, Bingöl, Tunceli	8,685	57.8	4,900
Van, Mus, Bitlis, Hakkari	7,388	68.5	3,400
Güneydogu Anadolu	36,775	64.7	4,100
Gaziantep, Adiyaman, Kilis	14,990	67.9	5,300
Sanliurfa, Diyarbakir	12,132	52.6	3,200
Mardin, Batman, Siirt	9,654	77.3	4,200
Turkey	679,510	59.9	8,200

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration;
Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

Provinces with a high share of foreigners have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors.

145,232 work permits were granted to foreigners in Turkey in 2019. Almost all (94,68 %) permissions were given to TCNs, especially to workers from Syria (43.92 % of total permissions granted), Kyrgyzstan (7.58 %), Ukraine (4.27 %), Turkmenistan (4.22 %), Georgia (3.59 %) and Uzbekistan (3.1 %). In total, these countries account for exactly two thirds (66.66 %) of work permission in 2019. 3.55 % of all permits are given to EU-28 citizens and there is no further information available for 1.77 %.

In total, approx. 26.8 million people were employed in 2020 in Turkey. This corresponds to an increase of +3.4 % compared to 2014. More than one half (56.2 %) are employed in the service sector (15.1 million persons), where employment has increased by +13.8 % since 2014 while it decreased in primary (-13.8 %) and secondary sector (-2.6 %).

A more detailed examination of the different sectors of the economy reveals that there have also been significant shifts within the sectors: the only declines in employment were recorded in the sectors "Administrative and support service activities" (-24.4 %), "Construction" (-19.6 %), "Agriculture, forestry and fishing" (-13.8 %) and "Arts, entertainment and recreation" (-5.3 %). "Human health and social work activities" (+50.9 %), "Public administration and defence" (+42.0 %), "Real estate activities" (42.0 %), "Education" (+36.2 %), "Professional, scientific and technical activities" (+28.4 %) as well as "Electricity, gas, steam, water supply, sewerage etc." (+20.0 %), on the other hand, are among those economic sections with the largest growth rates.

Further analysis focusing on work permissions granted to foreigners in 2019 shows that more than one half (56.3 %) work in the tertiary and approx. one quarter (27.3 %) in the secondary sector whereas foreigners are of no relevance in the pri-

mary sector (0.3 %). Those with permission preferably work in “Manufacturing” (23.4 %), “Accommodation and food service activities” (19.5 %) and

“Wholesale and retail trade” (13.1 %) which account for more than 50.0 % (56.0 %; see Table 3).

Table 3: Employment by economic activity 2019

Economic Activity	Employed persons (in 1,000)	Share	Δ 14-20	Share Work permissions 2019
Primary Sector	4,716	17.6%	-13.8%	0.3%
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	4,716	17.6%	-13.8%	0.3%
Secondary Sector	7,036	26.2%	-2.6%	27.3%
Mining and quarrying	134	0.5%	0.0%	0.6%
Manufacturing	5,070	18.9%	2.7%	23.4%
Electricity, gas, steam, water supply, sewerage etc.	294	1.1%	20.0%	0.2%
Construction	1,538	5.7%	-19.6%	3.1%
Tertiary Sector	15,061	56.2%	13.8%	56.3%
Wholesale and retail trade	3,723	13.9%	3.8%	13.1%
Transportation and storage	1,209	4.5%	8.0%	1.8%
Accommodation and food service activities	1,377	5.1%	1.9%	19.5%
Information and communication	241	0.9%	6.2%	1.2%
Financial and insurance activities	315	1.2%	4.7%	0.3%
Real estate activities	291	1.1%	42.0%	1.1%
Professional, scientific and technical activities	878	3.3%	28.4%	2.1%
Administrative and support service activities	873	3.3%	-24.4%	6.6%
Public administration and defence	1,965	7.3%	42.0%	0.0%
Education	1,798	6.7%	36.2%	3.0%
Human health and social work activities	1,467	5.5%	50.9%	3.5%
Arts, entertainment and recreation	124	0.5%	-5.3%	1.0%
Other social, community and personal service activities	800	3.0%	0.0%	3.1%
Total	26,812	100.0%	3.4%	100.0%

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute (2020c), own calculations and illustration;
Turkish Statistical Institute (2020d), own calculations and illustration

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research & development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 1.06 % for Turkey (2019) which is a slight increase of 0.11 percentage points to 2017. The total

amount of research expenditures was € 7,23 billion, the largest share (56,6 % or € 4.07 billion) was financed by the business enterprise sector. 29.2 % (or € 2.12 billion) were financed by the government sector. 13.2 % (or € 923,5 millions) were financed by higher education sector and 1.9 % (or € 109.0 millions) were funded by foreign countries (rest of the world; Eurostat 2020I)

From a regional perspective (NUTS 2) Ankara (31.6 %) and Istanbul (26.4 %) account for almost 60 % (58.0 %) of total research spending. The ratio in the remaining provinces is 9.5 % (Kocaeli, Sakarya, Düzce, Bolu, Yalova), 6.4 % (Bursa, Eskişehir, Bilecik) and 5.2 % (İzmir; see Table 4).

Table 4: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(Share of Total)	
Ankara	31.6 %	0.34%
Istanbul	26.4 %	0.28%
Kocaeli, Sakarya, Düzce, Bolu, Yalova	9.5 %	0.11%
Bursa, Eskişehir, Bilecik	6.4 %	0.07%
İzmir	5.2 %	0.06%
Diğer (Other)	20.8 %	0.22%
Turkey	100.0 %	1.06%

Source: Eurostat (2020m), own calculations and illustration; Turkish Statistical Institute (2020e); own calculations and illustration

In accordance to the research & development (R&D) funding structure more than half (55.7 % or 62,305 full-time equivalent (FTE)) of the researchers work in the business enterprise sector. Approx. one third (38.4 % or 42.916 FTE) works in the higher education sector and the rest in the government sector (6.0 % or 6,672 FTE). This makes a total of 111,893 FTE. Further analysis on educational attainment level reveals that most researchers (75.1 %) have tertiary education but not doctoral or equivalent level; 23.7 % belong to the latter whereas 1.2 % have less than primary, primary, secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: R&D researchers (full-time equivalent (FTE)) by sectors of performance and educational attainment level 2017 (ISCED2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

Conclusion

This Statistical Briefings examines the economic and spatial importance and impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in Turkey.

On January 1, 2020, a total of 1,528,271 persons with non-Turkish citizenship were living in Turkey. This corresponds to a share of 1.8 % of Turkey's total population. Among non-Turkish nationals, only 11.3 % came from EU-28 (incl. UK) and EFTA countries. A total of 1,351,823 persons (or 1.6 % of total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither Turks, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share

of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore Turkey lying way below the average.

Within the last 20 years the population growth was dominated by high fertility rates of Turkish citizens, which makes Turkey a young nation (especially with regard to the developments in industrialized nations). From 2006 to 2019 all NUTS 2 regions in Turkey recorded a growth in working-age population though the development stagnates in most of the regions. As the share of immigrants is quite low, one can assume that their impact was of low importance in the past.

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MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

ECONOMIC IMPACT OF MIGRATION

Statistical Briefings United Kingdom

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Deliverable 4.2 – Statistical briefing for United Kingdom on economic impact of TCNs in MATILDE regions

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Introduction

This document presents the results of an assessment of the impact of migration and a measurement of the contribution provided by 'third country nationals' (TCNs) to the economic systems in the receiving contexts. In total, 10 statistical briefings for the MATILDE regions have been compiled, including the following countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. Each document focuses on the following dimensions of economic development: economic growth, labour markets, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Moreover, a short introduction on the relevance of TCNs in the respective country as well as the population development and structure are considered. The results of a literature review and a comparative analysis of the 10 statistical briefings are published separately.

Within the Matilde project there is a special focus on so-called 'third country nationals' (TCNs). MATILDE considers TCNs as Non EU citizens, who reside legally in the European Union (EU) and who are the target of EU integration policies. A TCN is "any person who is not a citizen of the European Union within the meaning of Art. 20(1) of TFEU and who is not a person enjoying the European Union right to free movement, as defined in Art. 2(5) of the Regulation (EU) 2016/399 (Schengen Borders Code)." (European Commission 2020a). According to this definition, nationals of European Free Trade Association (EFTA) member countries Norway, Island, Liechtenstein and Switzerland are not considered to be TCNs. TCNs cover economic migrants, family migrants, students and researchers, highly skilled migrants, and forced migrants.

UNITED KINGDOM (UK)

Figure 1: Origin and share of total population of different nationalities in United Kingdom

Source: Eurostat (2020a), own illustration

Third Country Nationals (TCN) in the UK

On January 1, 2019, a total of 6,200,181 persons with non-British citizenship were living in the United Kingdom (UK), former EU-28 member state (until 2020). This corresponds to a share of 9.3 % of the UK's total population. Among non-British nationals, 59.4 % (3,681,859 persons; 5.5 % of total population) came from the EU-28 (2013 – 2020; excl. reporting country UK) and EFTA countries (35,947 persons; 0.05 %). A total of 2,482,375 persons (or 3.7 % of the total population) were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither British, EU-28 citizens nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore the UK is lying below the average.

Data about third country nationalities are not made easily available. According to our findings Indians (0.54 %), Pakistanis (0.29 %), Chinese (incl. Hong Kong; 0.21 %), US Americans (0.23 %), Nigerians (0.14 %) and Bangladeshi (0.13 %) are the most relevant nationalities. In total, more than 40 % (41.5 %) of TCN living in the UK belong to these nationalities. Figure 1 gives an overview of the origin and the share of the different nationalities in the country.

Population Development & Population Structure

The number of inhabitants in the UK increased in the past and this development is projected to continue in the future. As of January 1, 2019, there were 66,647,112 persons registered. This corresponds to an increase of 6,862,432 citizens

(+13.4 %) within the last 20 years (e.g. before the eastward enlargement of the EU in 2004).

A long-term analysis of population development from 2002 to 2019 reveals clear regional differences. Manchester (+30.00 %), Hackney & Newham (+38.4 %) and Tower Hamlets (56.7 %) record the highest population growth rates. Though the majority of regions (95.0 %) recorded a population growth, there are also some regions suffering from a decline. Sunderland (-2.1 %), Blackpool (-2.2 %) and Sefton (-2.2 %) are among those most affected by depopulation (see Figure 2).

From an economic perspective, labor (done by human beings) is an essential element in the production of goods and services. The term 'labor force' comprises all of those who work for gain, whether as employees, employers, or as self-employed, and it includes the unemployed who are seeking work.

As Figure 3 (a)-(d) indicate, the increase in the working-age population (+2,403,200 inh.) from 2006 to 2019, i.e. longest available period, within the regions is mainly caused by immigration from the EU (+1,600,900 inh.) and from outside the EU (+254,600 inh.), though the British citizens in working-age increased substantially as well since 2006 (+ 539,900 inh.).

From a regional perspective, the areas with the highest working-age population growths are London (+18.1 %), East of England (+7.2 %), South East (+6.5 %), Northern Ireland (+6.2 %) and West Midlands. The North East (+0.8 %) and Wales (+2.4 %) recorded the lowest growth rates. Scotland and Northern Ireland grew by +4.7 % and +6.2 %.

There was an increase of labor force potential recorded in the past 15 years and this development continues in the future as working-age population is projected to increase at by +1.1 % until 2040. Half of the regions tend to grow in the future with highest percentual change in West Midlands (+5.8 %), East Midlands (+4.5 %), London (+3.5 %) and South West (+3.1 %). In Scotland (-4.0 %), North East (-3.5 %), Wales (-2.9 %) and Northern Ireland (-2.4 %) labor force is projected to shrink (see Figure 4).

The total-age dependency ratio is a measure of the age structure of the population. It relates the number of individuals who are likely to be "dependent" on the support of others for their daily living – the young (up to 19 years old) and the elderly (65 plus years old) – to the number of those individuals who are, being working age from 20 to 64 years old, capable of providing this support.

The total-age dependency ratio in United Kingdom is 72.5 %. The dependency rate is usually lower in metropolitan areas and cities than in rural regions. The key factors here are a more prosperous economy, i.e. more people in working-age, and low child ratios. Densely populated regions in United Kingdom are also characterized by relatively low rates. High dependency ratios are found in South West (79.5 %), East (77.3 %) and Wales (76.6 %) whereas lowest values are reported from London (58.3 %) and Scotland (67.3 %). As a result of ageing societies, the total-age dependency ratios will rise in the future by 10.2 pp to 82.6 % in 2040 resulting in implications/challenges for publicly funded social security schemes (e.g., expenditures for pensions).

Figure 2: Population development (Δ 2002 to 2019), NUTS 3

Source: Eurostat (2020b), own illustration

Figure 3: Working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2006 to 2019)

(a) Total +2,403,200 inh.

(c) Non-EU-28 +254,600 inh.

(b) British +539,900 inh.

(d) EU-28 +1,600,900 inh.

Source: Eurostat (2020c), own illustration

Figure 4: Projections of working-age population (20 to 64 years; Δ 2020 to 2040)

Source: Office for National Statistics (2020a), own illustration; Office for National Statistics (2020b), own illustration; Office for National Statistics (2020c), own illustration; Office for National Statistics (2020d), own illustration

Education and (Un)Employment

The tertiary education rate of United Kingdom's nationals is 39.6 %, which is slightly below that of the total population (40.6 %). Compared to the EU-28 (29.5 %) the United Kingdom has an above-average tertiary education rate. In 2020 the country ranked 3rd among the EU-28 member states for share of tertiary educated residents, following Ireland (40.7 %) and Luxembourg (41.0 %) and ahead of Cyprus (40,0 %), Finland (38.5 %) and Lithuania (37.9 %). While the Czech Republic (21.6 %), Italy (17.4 %) and Romania (16.0 %) have the lowest tertiary education rate.

Across the world, educational attainment is significantly higher in cities¹ than in towns and suburbs², which in turn is higher than in rural areas³. This is not the case for the United Kingdom where primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education are almost evenly spread around cities, towns and suburbs as well as rural areas. Approx. 40 % of the population have a university degree, i.e. tertiary education (ISCED2011 levels 5 to 8), and another 40 % hold a secondary, i.e. upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary educational (ISCED2011 levels 3 to 4) attainment level. Primary educational attainment level has low relevance as approx. only 1 out of 5 residents in UK belongs to this group. Differences of educational attainment level between British, non-EU-28 residents and EU-28 residents range within a narrow band from 0.2 pp to 6.3 pp (see Table 1; cf. Caputo, Bianchi & Baglioni 2021). In total, EU-28 (45.2 %) and domestic population (39.6 %) have a lower tertiary education rate than non-EU-28 citizens (52.1 %).

The unemployment rate in UK is 3.4 % (2019), below the EU-28 average of 6.2 %. From a regional perspective, West Midlands has the highest unemployment rate at 5.3 % (female: 5.1 %; male: 5.5 %), followed by Tees Valley and Durham

(5.2 %; female: 5.0 %; male: 5.3 %) and Northumberland and Tyne and Wear (5.1 %). Dorset and Somerset (1.8 %; 2.2 % female; 1.4 % male), Cumbria (1.9 %) and Highlands and Islands (2.0 %) are the provinces with the lowest unemployment rates (see Figure 5).

Table 1: Working-age Population by citizenship, degree of urbanization and educational attainment level 2019

Urbanisation	Citizenship	Educational Attainment Level (ISCED11)		
		Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Cities	British	19.9%	39.9%	40.2%
	EU-28	15.7%	38.3%	46.0%
	Non-EU-28	18.5%	29.7%	51.7%
	Total	19.5%	39.1%	41.5%
Towns & suburbs	British	19.3%	42.5%	38.2%
	EU-28	13.0%	44.9%	42.1%
	Non-EU-28	14.4%	31.4%	54.2%
	Total	18.9%	42.3%	38.8%
Rural	British	18.3%	41.3%	40.5%
	EU-28	13.4%	41.1%	45.5%
	Non-EU-28	15.7%	33.2%	51.1%
	Total	18.1%	41.2%	40.8%

Source: Eurostat (2020i), own illustration

In general, there is a correlation between the level of education and unemployment, according to which the well-educated are significantly less likely to be unemployed than people without a vocational qualification. This correlation can also be seen for the UK: those with primary education are most affected by unemployment (5.6 %). Conversely, people with tertiary education have the lowest unemployment rate (2.5 %), those with secondary a value of 3.5 %. Similar results are observed at the European level (EU-28; Figure 6).

In contrast, the higher the educational attainment the higher is the employment rate, i.e. 86.0 % for tertiary, 78.8 % for secondary and 64.6 % for primary level. From an immigration point of view, this observation holds for other citizenships as well, as the risk of unemployment decreases by

¹ A city is a local administrative unit (LAU) where at least 50 % of the population lives in one or more urban centres (Eurostat, 2020d).

² Towns & suburbs are areas where less than 50 % of the population lives in rural grid cells and less than 50 % of the population lives in urban centres, i.e. a cluster of contiguous grid cells of 1 km² (excluding diagonals) with a population

density of at least 1 500 inhabitants per km² and collectively a minimum population of 50 000 inhabitants after gap-filling (Eurostat, 2020e; Eurostat, 2020f).

³ A rural area is an area where more than 50 % of its population lives in 'rural grid cells', i.e. grid cells that are not identified as urban centres or as urban clusters (Eurostat, 2020g; Eurostat, 2020h).

Figure 5: Unemployment rate 2019 (20 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

Figure 6: Unemployment rate by educational attainment level (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020j), own illustration

the highest educational attainment also for immigrants. But EU-28 citizens have the highest employment rate for all educational attainment levels (89.9 %; 84.8 %; 78.8 %) while British rank second on each level (86.5 %; 79.0 %; 64.4 %). Non-

EU-28 citizens have the lowest employment rate on each level (74.5 %; 64.7 %; 51.9 %; see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Employment rate by educational attainment level and citizenship (20 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020k), own illustration

The abovementioned findings foster the theoretical conclusions by Becker (1964) that the educational level has a significant influence on the professional career and the risk of unemployment.

This theory and the empirical evidence can also be applied to the “Early Leavers from Education and Training”. This population group refers to persons aged 18 to 24 who have completed a lower secondary education and are not involved in further education or training. From a fiscal point of view, this specific group is of particular relevance as they are more likely to be (long-term) unemployed, and thus causing costs for the economy.

In 2019, 10.3 % of the 18-24 year-old in the EU-28 were part of this group (male: 11.9 %; female: 8.6 %). The UK ranges with a value of 10.9 % slightly above the European average. The share of EU-28 citizens residing in UK is above (12.5 %) and that of non-EU-28 is below (9.3 %) that of the domestic population (10.9 %). In total, approx. 50 % (45.9 %) of all early leavers are jobless, but no relying statements can be made in regard to nationality because of missing or unreliable data (Eurostat 2020l).

Income and Gross Domestic Product

As for the employment rate, the educational attainment level has a positive impact on mean and median⁴ equivalized net income, i.e. the higher the educational attainment level the higher the income.

Working persons in the UK at primary level earn less (mean: € 20,007; median: € 17,764) than secondary (€ 23,837 or € 21,120) and tertiary levels (€ 32,406 or € 28,046; see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Mean and median equivalized net income by educational attainment level 2018 (18 to 64 years; ISCED 2011)

Source: Eurostat (2020m), own illustration

Working British citizens have a comparable educational attainment level as EU-28 and non-EU-28 residents, nevertheless the mean (€ 26,892 vs. € 27,186 and € 26,439) and median (€ 22,924 vs. € 22,774 and € 19,947) equivalized net income of TCN are lower than the British ones (see Figure 9).

The indicator 'people at risk of poverty or social exclusion' corresponds to the sum of persons who are: at risk of poverty after social transfers, severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity. As non-EU 28 citizens have a higher risk of unemployment and they earn less than domestic residents and EU-28 approx. one third (31.8 %) belong to this group. EU-28

(20.3 %) and British (22.0 %) face the lowest risk of social exclusion and poverty (see Table 2; cf. Caputo, Bianchi & Baglioni 2021).

Figure 9: Mean and median equivalized net income by broad group of citizenship 2018 (18 to 64 years)

Source: Eurostat (2020n), own illustration

In 2019, compensation of employees (wages and salaries plus employers' social contributions) was the largest income component of GDP in EU-28 and the Euro area, accounting respectively for 47.8 % and 48.0 %. The UK (49.5 %) is above European average (both EU-28 and Euro area). Taxes on production and imports (less subsidies) accounted for 11.9 % (EU-28: 11.9 %; Euro area: 11.5 %). Gross operating surplus and mixed income accounted for 38.5 % of GDP in UK, 40.3 % of GDP for the EU-28 and 40.5 % in the Euro area. British GDP at current prices amounted to approx. € 2,526.6 billion in 2019 and GDP per inhabitant equaled € 37,830 (Eurostat 2020p).

Within almost 20 years gross domestic product (GDP) increased by 36.0 % (real growth rate). In terms of regional GDP all provinces recorded positive real growth since 2000, ranging from 27.6 % in Northern Ireland to 50.0 % in London. Scotland lies slightly below British average, i.e. 33.2 %. The further away we move from London, the less the economic growth. Solely North West (35.0 %) and

⁴ The median is more robust, i.e. less sensitive to outliers than the mean. This explains why the mean equivalized income is always slightly higher for each educational level.

the East of England (35.0 %) almost reach the national level of 36.0 %.

Analyzing GDP per capita reveals that all regions except for London (£ 54,686) and South East (£ 34,083) lie below the national level of £ 31,976. GDP per capita in North East (£ 23,569), Wales (£ 23,866), Yorkshire and The Humber (£ 25,859), East Midlands (£ 25,946), Northern Ireland (£ 25,981) West Midlands (£ 27,087) is less than half of London. Scotland ranks in the midfield (£ 29,660) with highest regional value in the North Eastern (£ 40,914). Southern Scotland (£ 19,937)

has the lowest regional GDP per capita in United Kingdom (see Table 3).

Provinces with a high share of foreigners have a high GDP per capita and vice versa. On the one hand, prosperous regions are more attractive to migrants; on the other hand, these regions benefit from a better availability of labor supply, i.e. greater number of working age people. In this context, one speaks of a so-called cross-fertilization, which results from the interaction of these two factors.

Table 2: Population aged 18 and over by risk of poverty, material deprivation, work intensity 2019

		Risk of poverty					
		At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk	At risk	Not at risk
Work Intensity	Material Deprivation	United Kingdom		EU-28		Non-EU-28	
Very low	Severe	1.1	0.4	0.1	0.1	2.2	0.4
Not very low	Severe	1.1	1.5	1.3	1.9	2.4	3.3
Very low	Non severe	1.9	2.4	2.0	2.0	3.2	1.7
Not very low	Non severe	13.6		12.9		18.6	
People at Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		22.0		20.3		31.8	
		Not at risk		Not at risk		Not at risk	
Not very low	Non severe		78.1		79.7		68.2
People at no Risk of Poverty or Social Exclusion		78.1		79.7		46.0	
Total		100.0		100.0		100.0	

Source: Eurostat (2020o), own illustration

Table 3: Nominal regional GDP (2018) and real growth rate (Δ 2000 to 2018)

Region	GDP (in £) at current market prices	Gross Domestic Product chained volume measures annual growth rates	GDP (in £) per capita at current market prices
North East	62,644	26.4	23,569
Tees Valley and Durham	26,286	20.5	21,882
Northumberland and Tyne and Wear	36,357	31.6	24,960
North West	207,452	35.0	28,449
Cumbria	14,028	39.1	28,118
Greater Manchester	78,918	35.8	28,059
Lancashire	39,124	33.9	26,112
Cheshire	37,427	38.4	40,207
Merseyside	37,956	29.7	24,464
Yorkshire and The Humber	141,698	29.0	25,859
East Yorkshire and Northern Lincolnshire	24,727	20.0	26,529
North Yorkshire	23,368	32.6	28,345
South Yorkshire	31,010	33.2	22,104
West Yorkshire	62,593	29.6	26,977

East Midlands	124,647	32.4	25,946
Derbyshire and Nottinghamshire	55,999	28.3	25,367
Leicestershire, Rutland and Northamptonshire	51,021	35.3	27,717
Lincolnshire	17,627	38.4	23,322
West Midlands	159,832	31.0	27,087
Herefordshire, Worcestershire and Warwickshire	40,716	37.7	30,045
Shropshire and Staffordshire	41,664	29.1	25,574
West Midlands	77,452	28.5	26,557
East of England	186,462	35.0	30,069
East Anglia	71,915	35.2	28,597
Bedfordshire and Hertfordshire	65,065	41.1	35,100
Essex	49,482	28.2	26,999
London	487,145	50.3	54,686
Inner London - West	210,224	63.0	176,015
Inner London - East	115,826	56.9	48,143
Outer London - East and North East	43,390	24.0	22,626
Outer London - South	36,356	23.5	27,910
Outer London - West and North West	81,348	41.7	38,968
South East	311,300	30.8	34,083

Berkshire, Buckinghamshire and Oxfordshire	103,321	35.7	42,915
Surrey, East and West Sussex	93,700	27.8	32,380
Hampshire and Isle of Wight	65,712	26.9	33,091
Kent	48,567	33.4	26,302
South West	158,084	32.2	28,231
Gloucestershire, Wiltshire and Bath/Bristol area	83,158	34.0	33,188
Dorset and Somerset	33,881	24.7	25,442
Cornwall and Isles of Scilly	12,555	43.2	22,096
Devon	28,490	30.7	23,858
Wales	74,906	28.4	23,866
West Wales and The Valleys	41,924	26.5	21,274
East Wales	32,982	30.4	28,238
Scotland	161,295	33.2	29,660
North Eastern Scotland	20,008	47.7	40,914
Highlands and Islands	13,786	35.7	29,372
Eastern Scotland	65,917	32.7	33,094
West Central Scotland	42,707	29.2	27,713
Southern Scotland	18,877	27.4	19,937
Northern Ireland	48,887	27.6	25,981
United Kingdom	2,124,351	36.0	31,976

Source: Office for National Statistics (2019), own calculations and illustrations

Economic structure and entrepreneurship

In general, a distinction is made between three different sectors of the economy, the primary (agriculture and forestry), secondary (manufacturing) and tertiary (services) sectors.

EU-28 citizens are overrepresented (above 7.1 %) in “Manufacturing” (11.0 %), “Wholesale and retail trade hotels and restaurants” (9.0 %), “Transport and communication” (8.8 %), “Construction” (8.7 %), “Financial and business services” (7.4 %) and “Agriculture, forestry and fishing” whereas they are of low relevance in “Energy and water” (4.5 %) and “Public administration, education and health” (4.0 %).

Non-EU-28 citizens preferably work in “Transport and communication” (5.6 %), “Wholesale and retail trade hotels and restaurants” (4.5 %), “Financial and business services” (4.5 %) and “Other Services” (4.1 %) whereas they are underrepresented (below 4.0 %) in “Public administration, education and health” (3.7 %), “Energy and water” (3.0 %) and “Construction” (2.2 %; see Table 4).

Table 4: Employment by economic activity 2016

Economic Activity	British	EU-28	Non EU-28	n.a.
Primary Sector				
Agriculture, forestry and fishing	88.3 %	7.4 %	n.a.	4.4 %
Secondary Sector				
Energy and water	91.9%	4.5%	3.0%	0.6%
Manufacturing	86.0%	11.0%	2.9%	0.1%
Construction	89.1%	8.7%	2.2%	0.1%
Tertiary Sector				
Wholesale and retail trade hotels and restaurants	86.4%	9.0%	4.5%	0.1%
Transport and communication	85.5%	8.8%	5.6%	0.1%
Financial and business services	88.0%	7.4%	4.5%	0.1%
Public administration, education and health	92.2%	4.0%	3.7%	0.0%
Other services	90.3%	5.5%	4.1%	0.1%
Total	88.8%	7.1%	4.0%	0.1%

Source: Office for National Statistics (2017), own illustration

Research and Innovation

Following the neoclassical and endogenous growth theories, technological advance is believed to be one of the major drivers of economic growth. From this perspective, there is a growing interest to investigate the link between research &

development (R&D), innovation, entrepreneurship and economic growth achieved by human capital from abroad (EU-28 and non-EU-28).

A well-known indicator provided to measure achievements of countries or regions in R&D is GERD, i.e. regional/national gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP. GERD is estimated at 2.05 % for United Kingdom in 2018

which is a slight increase of 0.05 pp compared to 2017. The total amount of research expenditures was € 41.90 billion, the largest share (54.9 %) was financed by the business enterprise sector. 26.0 % were financed by the government sector. 13.9 % were contributed by foreign countries (rest of the world) and 5.2 % and 0.6 % were funded by the private non-profit and the higher education sector (Eurostat 2020q).

Regional data is published on NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 level. The East of England has the highest ratio in 2018 (3.57 %) followed by the South East (2.26 %), West (2.07 %) and East Midlands (1.81 %). Except for Scotland (1.69 %) all other provinces on NUTS 1 level are well behind and below the all-British ratio of 1.73 %. Wales ranks last (1.08 %) with London (1.16 %), Yorkshire and The Humber (1.18 %), North (1.27 %) and West (1.43 %) doing only slightly better, see Table 5).

In accordance to the research & development (R&D) funding structure almost more than one half (54.4 %) perform research activities in the higher education sector followed by the business enterprise sector (41.9 %). The remaining are located in the government (2.2 %) and private non-profit sector (1.5 %). This makes a total of 317,472 full-time equivalent (FTE; Eurostat 2020s).

Available data for other countries has shown that employees in R&D have an above average share of foreigners compared to the total number of employed persons by economic activity.

Table 5: Intramural R&D expenditure as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) 2017

Province	Expenditures	% of GDP
	(€ mio.)	
North East	881.1	1.27%
Tees Valley and Durham	324.9	1.13%
Northumberland and Tyne and Wear	556.3	1.37%
North West	3,333.1	1.43%
Cumbria	208.2	1.37%
Greater Manchester	1,104.1	1.22%
Lancashire	357.1	0.82%
Cheshire	979.1	2.37%
Merseyside	684.6	1.60%
Yorkshire and The Humber	1,855.9	1.18%
East Yorkshire and Northern Lincolnshire	227.3	0.88%

North Yorkshire	406.6	1.55%
South Yorkshire	461.5	1.33%
West Yorkshire	760.6	1.08%
East Midlands	2,498.6	1.81%
Derbyshire and Nottinghamshire	1,751.1	2.85%
Leicestershire, Rutland and Northamptonshire	664.0	1.15%
Lincolnshire	83.5	0.44%
West Midlands	3,712.8	2.07%
Herefordshire, Worcestershire and Warwickshire	1,869.1	3.98%
Shropshire and Staffordshire	358.2	0.81%
West Midlands	1,485.5	1.68%
East of England	7,458.2	3.57%
East Anglia	4,462.4	5.47%
Bedfordshire and Hertfordshire	2,158.4	2.95%
Essex	837.5	1.55%
London	6,651.1	1.16%
Inner London - West	4,154.1	1.63%
Inner London - East	915.6	0.67%
Outer London - East and North East	145.8	0.31%
Outer London - South	190.1	0.46%
Outer London - West and North West	1,245.4	1.36%
South East	7,945.6	2.26%
Berkshire, Buckinghamshire and Oxfordshire	4,388.5	3.65%
Surrey, East and West Sussex	1,641.3	1.55%
Hampshire and Isle of Wight	1,191.6	1.65%
Kent	724.3	1.34%
South West	2,807.6	1.59%
Gloucestershire, Wiltshire and Bristol/Bath area	2,033.7	2.19%
Dorset and Somerset	318.0	0.83%
Cornwall and Isles of Scilly	49.1	0.35%
Devon	406.8	1.27%
Wales	891.6	1.08%
West Wales and The Valleys	447.9	0.99%
East Wales	443.7	1.19%
Scotland	3,058.8	1.69%
North Eastern Scotland	342.0	1.48%
Highlands and Islands	69.7	0.45%
Eastern Scotland	1,710.9	2.33%
West Central Scotland	863.3	1.80%
Southern Scotland	72.8	0.36%
Northern Ireland	808.7	1.51%
United Kingdom	41,903.4	1.73%

Source: Eurostat (2020r), own illustration

Conclusion

This Statistical Briefings examines the economic and spatial impact of immigration with special regard to third-country nationals (TCN) in the UK.

On January 1, 2019, a total of 6,200,181 persons with Non-British citizenship were living in the country, a former EU-28 member state (until 2020). This corresponds to a share of 9.3 % of the UK's total population. Among non-British nationals, 59.4 % (5.5 % of total population) came from EU and EFTA countries (0.05 %). 3.7 % of total population were third country nationals (TCN), being individuals who are neither British, EU nor EFTA citizens. By comparison, the share of TCN in EU-27 (excl. UK) and EU-28 (incl. UK) is 5.7 % and 3.8 %, therefore UK lying below the average.

Within the last 20 years the development of the population in the country has mainly been due to immigration. From 2006 to 2019 all regions profited heavily from immigration with regard to its working-age population. Without immigration, many regions would have suffered from a decrease in its population aged between 20 and 64 years.

Despite the relevance of migration for labor supply, the employment rate of TCN is lower compared to UK nationals and EU-28 citizens. One would consider the educational attainment level as relevant aspect, but in the country EU citizens as well as TCN are better educated than British people. Hence, other reasons have to be considered to explain the gap.

From a spatial point of view, the concentration of better-educated migrants is highest in cities. Provinces with a higher ratio of TCN are also characterized by higher economic growth, being more attractive for TCN on the one hand and offering more labor supply on the other hand.

The below average regional GDP growth rate, especially in diffusely populated regions like Wales and Northern Ireland is indirectly linked to immigration from abroad but primarily to internal migration from rural areas to cities and metropolitan areas. These emigration flows tend to reinforce the erosion of the economic basis, because they have a negative impact on the potential workforce and the economic attractiveness of the region. Economic performance is stagnating, accompanied by declining population figures.

Governments need to invest in education on the one hand and in research and development (R&D) on the other, to enable long-term prosperity and growth. In 2018 the national gross domestic expenditures on R&D (as a percentage of GDP) were estimated at 2.05 %, which is a slight increase of 0.05 percentage points to 2017. But there is again a striking regional variation from densely populated areas with a high number of innovative enterprises (e.g. The East and South East) to less densely populated regions (e.g. Wales).

Summing up, immigrants in the UK play a pivotal role in reviving rural areas, and with the appropriate policies, they could play an even more significant role in sustaining them.

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